

SMART ERA

Pilot needs and gap analysis/D5.1

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Executive Summary

The **SMART ERA project** is conducting pilot activities in six different European rural regions, with the aim to develop, implement and validate in real-world conditions tailored Smart Innovation Packages (SIPs) that contribute to the community engagement, digital transition and sustainable socioeconomic development of these regions.

To achieve this ambitious objective, over the last 6 months, an analysis of the current situation, challenges and needs of each pilot has been conducted, in collaboration with local stakeholders, to precisely characterize the pilots and co-define the main guiding lines of the specific action plans to be developed and implemented at local level.

This work has been done following a 4-steps process: *(i) preparation phase*, fostering coordination between pilots' partners and initiating the mapping of the different data, documents, stakeholders, regulations and initiatives at local level; *(ii) engagement phase*, launching the communication activities and initiating the involvement of local stakeholders in the different pilots' activities; *(iii) data collection phase*, studying documents and data sources available, and organizing workshops and other activities to collect feedback and data from local stakeholders; and *(iv) data analysis phase*, analyzing the collected data to define the needs, requirements, expected solutions, barriers and challenges of each pilot.

As a result, the **six SMART ERA pilots** have defined the focus of their action plan:

- **Pilot 1: Valle di Sole, Italy.** Main focus on: (i) protection and revalorization of natural and cultural assets (including forestry management); and (ii) characterization of lands and soil for agricultural use. Lesser focus on social services and slow tourism.
- **Pilot 2: Sóller/Tramuntana, Spain.** Main focus on digitalization of local economy and on boosting cooperation and data sharing between stakeholders (especially tourism and agriculture). Lesser focus on mobility and cultural sectors.
- **Pilot 3: North Ostrobothnia, Finland.** Main focus on platform economies for rural micro and small companies, providing services for rural citizens. Lesser focus on mobility.
- **Pilot 4: East Herzegovina.** Main focus on: (i) rural tourism development through increased visibility of cultural, natural and gastronomic heritage; and (ii) implementation of infrastructure, solutions and services that support sustainable tourism development. Lesser focus on digital literacy and provision of digital services for promotions, sales and marketing.
- **Pilot 5: Šmarje-Padna, Slovenia.** Main focus on: (i) sustainable mobility services and sustainable tourism development; (ii) community engagement in circular economy and in green and sustainable shared activities. Lesser focus on water management.
- **Pilot 6: Devetaki Plateau, Bulgaria.** Main focus on: (i) improving social services through implementation of healthcare centre/services for remote consultation; and (ii) economic development through tourism and remote working opportunities. Lesser focus on improvement of environment protection and smart waste management.

In all the pilots, the expectations of local stakeholders and the type of solutions and activities to be developed and implemented, are similar and can be regrouped in the following categories:

- **Improved knowledge (capacity building)**
- **Improved access to information and digital services**
- **Improved market opportunities for local/rural products**
- **Improved infrastructure for connectivity and data management**
- **Improved community development and networking (including data sharing)**

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and objective

The SMART ERA project is conducting pilot activities in six different European rural regions, with the aim to develop, implement and validate in real-world conditions tailored Smart Innovation Packages (SIPs) that contribute to community engagement and socioeconomic development of these regions.

Each pilot counts with:

- **an “orchestrator”**, a partner in charge of coordinating the activities at local level and of interacting with other pilots’ teams and WPs
- **an “activator”**, a partner in charge of connecting and engaging with the local community and stakeholders.

The underlying objective of the project (and therefore of all the pilots), is to reduce vulnerabilities and foster resilience of the participating rural areas, by upgrading and co-designing, co-developing and co-validating with local communities a set of digital and non-digital solutions, complemented by effective methods to analyse and tackle pressing socio-economic and environmental challenges and promote a smart and community-led transition pathway that will empower rural people to act for change.

The SMART ERA pilots are geographically distributed over different European countries as presented in Figure 1. Considering the different realities and characteristics of participating regions, each pilot is focusing on different aspects, issues, sectors and/or actions. The six pilots, together with their orchestrator and activators, are:

- **Pilot 1: Valle di Sole, Italy.** *Orchestrator: FBK; Activator: PAT.* Main focus on: (i) protection and revalorization of natural and cultural assets (including forestry management); and (ii) characterization of lands and soil for agricultural use. Lesser focus on social services and slow tourism.
- **Pilot 2: Sóller/Tramuntana, Spain.** *Orchestrator: ANYSOL; Activator: +CULTURA.* Main focus on digitalization of local economy and on boosting cooperation and data sharing between stakeholders (especially tourism and agriculture). Lesser focus on mobility and cultural sectors.
- **Pilot 3: North Ostrobothnia, Finland.** *Orchestrator: UOULU; Activator: C.OULU.* Main focus on platform economies for rural micro and small companies, providing services for rural citizens. Lesser focus on mobility.
- **Pilot 4: Trebinje, Bosnia and Herzegovina.** *Orchestrator: SFTH; Activator: TORS.* Main focus on rural tourism development through increased visibility of cultural, natural and gastronomic heritage of rural East Herzegovina, and on the implementation of the infrastructure, solutions and services that support a sustainable development of tourism activities in the region. Lesser focus on digital literacy of local population and provision of digital services for promotions, sales and marketing.
- **Pilot 5: Šmarje-Padna, Slovenia.** *Orchestrator: UL; Activator: ROTUNDA.* Main focus on: (i) sustainable mobility services and sustainable tourism development; (ii) community engagement in circular economy and in green and sustainable shared activities. Lesser focus on water management.
- **Pilot 6: Devetaki Plateau, Bulgaria.** *Orchestrator: DPA; Activator: SEVLIEVO.* Main focus on: (i) improving social services through implementation of healthcare centre/services for remote consultation; and (ii) economic development through tourism and remote working opportunities. Lesser focus on improvement of environment protection and smart waste management.

Figure 1 - Distribution of SMART ERA's pilots (image source: SMART ERA website)

During the first six months of the project, all pilots were asked: (i) to identify, collect and compile information about their territories; (ii) to define and detail their use case; and (iii) to consolidate their requirements, needs, expected impacts, challenges and barriers in terms of community engagement, digitalisation and rural development. The results of this work are described in the present document.

1.2 Relation to other Work Packages

The present deliverable is a cornerstone of the SMART ERA project as it will greatly influence the work to be performed within the different WPs and will have impacts throughout the whole duration of the project.

In particular, the data, analysis and information collected in this document will serve to:

- WP2 for the refinement of the multi-dimensional methodology for the smartness assessment of rural areas.
- WP3 for the co-design of SIPs and local community engagement strategies.
- WP4 for data integration and analysis, and for the definition of the technological components and services to be developed and implemented.
- WP6 for the identification of the policies, sectors and standards to be tackled and influenced through the project.
- WP7 for the definition of the local communication strategies.

1.3 Structure of the document

This document is structured in 6 major sections:

- **Section 1** is a general introduction presenting the project, the pilots and this document.
- **Section 2** presents the methodological framework used in each pilot to collect the data and define the needs, requirements and barriers.
- **Section 3** describes each pilot thoroughly, presenting the region, the partners and organisations involved, the motivation and key expected results of the pilot activities, the socioeconomic and demographic data of the participating regions, it also provides a mapping of the existing data and datasets available, a list of the cross-collaboration in place at local/regional level, as well as a description of the regulatory framework in force in each region.
- **Section 4** focuses on the needs and gaps of each pilot, describing their interests and expectations, their barriers and challenges, and also provides a SWOT analysis.
- **Section 5** presents the main axes of the individual action plans of the six SMART ERA pilots.
- **Section 6** presents the conclusions obtained from this work, summarising the overall deliverable, highlighting main aspects and take aways.

2. METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

Early on in the project, a SMART ERA task force was established to define a common template to be used by all pilot partners to collect key information. This was necessary to establish comparisons and to enable transfer of knowledge and experience among pilots. It is also important to note that there is a large variance between the “starting points” of the different pilots in terms of maturity of pre-existing technical infrastructures, number and heterogeneity of local stakeholders, digital literacy of communities, as well as environmental, socioeconomic and demographic factors.

Therefore, pilots’ partners were required to collect and fill the requested data and information, but were “free” to use the channels, tools and/or methodologies of their choice to collect the data at local level.

However, independently of the channels, tools and/or methodologies used, all pilot partners have followed a 4 steps process:

- **Step 1: Inception / Preparation.** Learning and understanding more about the SMART ERA project and what could be done as pilot activities in each territory. Mapping of the existing documents that describe the context and background of each pilot’s region. Identification and mapping of main local stakeholders.
- **Step 2: First contact.** First contact (formal and/or informal) with local stakeholders. Launch of communication activities to raise awareness and interest and engage local stakeholders in the project’s activities.
- **Step 3: Data collection.** Study of the documents and data sources available. Organisation of workshops and other activities (surveys, bilateral meetings, participation in fairs...) to collect feedback and data from local stakeholders.
- **Step 4: Data analysis.** Analysis of the collected data to define the needs, requirements, expected solutions, barriers and challenges of each pilot.

It should be highlighted that all pilots’ activities, especially the ones involving target groups and stakeholders, are conducted in accordance with the privacy rules defined in the **SMART ERA Data Management Plan** (see project’s deliverable **D1.2**). Hence, all participants to the project’s activities have been fully informed and have signed an **informed consent form** (template of this form is provided in **Annex G1**).

2.1 PILOT 1: VALLE DI SOLE

Preparation phase. The activities for Pilot 1 started with the analysis of a recent rural innovation project in Valle di Sole by the Community Activator (PAT) to get an initial sense of the potential familiarity of stakeholders in Valle di Sole with collaborative processes for creating and delivering innovative services in rural areas (see **Annex A1** for more detailed information about the methodology exploited for community engagement). PAT and the Pilot Orchestrator (FBK) then proceeded with a study of several types of documents describing the context of the Valle di Sole rural area (socio-economic reports, statistical reports) to create a common background knowledge. This informed the selection by PAT of three representative sectors in which Valle di Sole has recently activated innovation projects within the National Strategy for Inner Areas programme, namely: (i) services in support of the older population, (ii) social services in support of young generations, (iii) capacity building for local public administrators to improve collaborative practices and innovation strategies. As a feasibility study, FBK performed an internal evaluation of the three sectors and challenges selected in the previous step to understand their potential suitability to SMART ERA scope and the opportunities for digital technologies.

Engagement phase. This phase was conducted through 4 main activities:

- Engagement of a leading contact point for the Community of Valley (March 2024). The president of the Community of Valley of Valle di Sole was identified by PAT as the first leading local representative to be contacted to initiate the pilot activities. An in-person meeting was organized with the Community of Valley president, PAT, and FBK to discuss existing initiatives addressing current needs and gaps in the area. After the meeting, the president of the Community of Valley reported back to the assembly of local mayors about the possibility of framing one of their upcoming innovation initiatives within the framework of the SMART ERA research and development approach.
- Engagement of mayors of the Community of Valley (April 2024). A plenary meeting was then organized with the participation of the 13 mayors of Valle di Sole and representatives of PAT and FBK. The SMART ERA project, its opportunities and work plan, as well as inspirational examples of Smart Innovation Packages (SIPs) for rural development, were presented, followed by a brainstorming session to further explore the priorities of current needs and gaps related to the development of that local rural area. Several themes and sectors emerged as important for the development of the Valley; see **Annex A4** for a general overview of emerging themes.
- Sector identification and mission statement (May 2024). The joint meeting above was followed by an internal discussion and reflection by local mayors about the sector to focus on for the SMART ERA investigation. As an output, the assembly of mayors produced a brief document with a mission statement that presents the cruciality of landscape and environment for the multi-systemic development of Valle di Sole.
- Local core group formation (Mid-May - Mid-June 2024). The assembly of mayors of the Community of Valley agreed to select three mayors to be part of a core working group, namely the mayors of the municipalities of Caldes, Pellizzano, and Dimaro-Folgarida.

Data collection phase. To collect data from local stakeholders, the working group produced a revised document describing their interest in participating in SMART ERA, their vision of the Valley's needs, and the opportunities envisaged (see **Annex A5**). The core group was invited to a follow-up brainstorming in collaboration with PAT and FBK to deepen the analysis of needs and gaps related to the chosen environment-related sector that attract stakeholders' interests and expectations and generated a general swot analysis of the Valley. Data were also obtained from literature review. Statistical data, regional reports, and provincial strategies for Valle di Sole development were collected and analyzed by FBK and PAT.

Data analysis phase. The material collected along this multistep journey was elaborated by PAT and FBK for the initial description of the Valle di Sole pilot illustrated in Sections 3 and 4.

2.2 PILOT 2: TRAMUNTANA / SÓLLER

Preparation phase. During this phase, the community coordinator (ANYSOL) and community activator (+CULTURA) have had several bilateral meetings to organise, plan and distribute the responsibilities and work to be undertaken in the frame of the SMART ERA project. ANYSOL started with the identification and study of the main reference documents while +CULTURA initiated a mapping of the main local stakeholders. A calendar of actions was also defined for the period M1-M6 of the project.

Engagement phase. To reach the local stakeholders, both +CULTURA and ANYSOL have held various meetings (whether formal or informal) with a wide range of stakeholders from different sectors (tourism, agriculture, public administrations, associations, local businesses and producers). The aim was to raise awareness about the SMART ERA project, inform them about the pilot to be conducted in Sóller, and raise their interest to participate and engage with the project. In particular, a communication event was organized in April 2024 in the Town Hall of Sóller to officially present the project and launch the pilot’s activities.

Data collection phase. Three main methods were used to collect data for the pilot:

- **Data from literature review.** This was conducted by ANYSOL, gathering statistical data, plus studying the different reports, plans and strategies available for the region.
- **Data from survey.** A survey campaign was conducted between ANYSOL and MESCULTURA to better understand the reality and current status, needs and challenges of the local community of Sóller in terms of digitalization. The results of this survey campaign are available in **annex B1**.
- **Data from local stakeholders.** A workshop was co-organised between ANYSOL and +CULTURA to identify the needs of local stakeholders and co-define the potential digital solutions and initiatives that could be implemented in the frame of the pilot. The results of this workshop are available in **annex B2**.

Data analysis phase. Based on the data and results obtained through the data collection phase, an analysis was performed by ANYSOL to define the main types of activities and main points of interests for the pilot. These results are described in section 5.

Figure 2 - Workshop held in Sóller with local stakeholders in May 2024

2.3 PILOT 3: NORTHERN OSTROBOTHNIA

Preparation phase. During the preparatory phase, the pilot orchestrator (UOULU) and community activator C.OULU together have had several bilateral planning meetings. The meetings were used to plan and organised key responsibilities, assign the roles in community engagement, mapping the key stakeholder organisations and influencers, and to adjust and specify the contents of the pilot. The results were applied to define the final pilot case municipalities within the pilot area Northern Ostrobothnia.

Engagement phase. To engage with the key local stakeholders, C.OULU and UOULU, have contacted and discussed with regional development organisations and municipalities. Needs of the local communities were integrated to SMART ERA Pilot targets during the iterative planning phase, in where the focus of planned pilot adjusted during each iteration. The brainstorming targeted to integrate the region, its municipalities and their rural citizens needs at the pilot area to the SMART ERA piloting targets was supported by the managers of the Local Action groups. For planning and prioritisation the workshop with preplanning meeting were hold with the Local Action groups leaders. The workshop was organised in the facilities of C.OULU. Contacting the pilot municipalities was done by bilateral meetings which led to local scale adjustments of the pilot and provided strong engagement of the municipalities.

Data collection phase. Three main methods were used to collect data for the pilot:

- **Research and project reports review.** UOULU and C.OULU are leading research and regional development organisations within the pilot region. Recently produced research, analysis and development project as well as regional planning publications form together a solid information and knowledge base.
- **Focus group discussion.** A workshop with Local Action Group leaders provided updates to sub-regional and municipal development needs and trend. Workshop was organised in collaboration with C.OULU and UOULU. Workshop material was collaboratively processed to better contextual understanding of the characteristics, needs, circumstances of the region.
- **Open data and research-based data.** Key open-source statistics were collected and analysed to measure regional patterns, dynamics and trends. Also published research material was applied to outline regional needs.

Data analysis phase. Using the data and results gathered during the data collection and the engagement phase, OULU and C.OULU conducted an analytical structuring to identify the primary needs, strengths and weaknesses of the region as well as its rural citizen groups and small scale enterprises. Aim was also to analytically process and understand the operational environment of the pilot with related risks and opportunities.

2.4 PILOT 4: EAST HERZEGOVINA

Preparation phase (January - February 2024). In the preparation phase, the pilot orchestrator (SFTH) and community activator (TORS) have had several meetings to organise, plan and distribute the responsibilities and work to be undertaken in the frame of the SMART ERA project. SFTH started with the identification and study of the main activities of mapping the main local stakeholders, while the TORS was responsible for the informing and animating local communities and competent institutions and organisations for tourism in the pilot area. A calendar of activities was also defined for the period M1-M6 of the project.

During preparation phase pilot orchestrator’s and pilot activator’s efforts included:

- Identifying information sources,
- Planning event attendance and meetings with the aim of collecting more data,
- Identifying stakeholders who might provide valuable insights,
- Developing questionnaires for each identified stakeholder,
- Preparing a communication plan
- Establishing a timeline for implementing all planned activities, and
- Allocating tasks based on our available human resources.

First contacts with identified stakeholders. In January 2024, after the Project Consortium’s General Assembly meeting in Trento, the SMART ERA project was announced at local level on various platforms, outlining its goals, expected stakeholder contributions, and potential benefits for rural East Herzegovina. Among the target groups that were informed about the project and its benefits, can be highlighted: municipal mayors, tourist organisations, and relevant ministries of Agriculture and Tourism. Face-to-face meetings were held with local municipalities administrations and local tourist organisations to discuss project goals.

Data collection process (February - May 2024). The data collection process involved:

- Gathering statistics from various agencies and ministries,
- Conducting surveys at the Sarajevo Street Food Festival and the TAIEX event,
- Emailing questionnaires to local tourist and producer organisations, and
- Holding meetings with local stakeholders to discuss rural tourism development and the Cheese and Potato Day event.

At the Sarajevo Street Food Festival, 60 questionnaires (enclosed in the **Annex D1**) were collected from potential consumers about their willingness to buy local products and visit the region. At the TAIEX event, 50 questionnaires (enclosed in the **Annex D2**) were distributed to policymakers and experts, seeking their views on rural tourism development and digital innovation. Local associations were emailed detailed questionnaires (enclosed in the **Annex D3**), focusing on their visions and challenges. Meetings with local tourist organizations and administrations gathered insights on the state of rural tourism and potential digital solutions.

The inaugural Cheese and Potato Day in Bratač on May 30th served as both a promotional event and a platform for gathering information from local producers (enclosed in the **Annex D4**). The event highlighted Bratač’s cultural heritage and historical landmarks, drawing significant attendance and media coverage to the SMART ERA project, exceeding all expectations.

Data analysis (March - June 2024). Collected data were systematically analysed to conduct a SWOT analysis and identify gaps and needs in the project area. On the bases of results obtained during research phase action plan for next period was drafted. Based on stakeholder research, key expected outcomes for the SMART ERA project were defined.

2.5 PILOT 5: ŠMARJE-PADNA

Preparation phase. During this phase, the pilot orchestrator (University of Ljubljana – abbreviation: UL) and community activator (Rotunda) organised online bilateral meetings to plan and distribute the responsibilities and work to be undertaken within the SMART ERA project. UL identified the most adequate methodology for working with rural areas, whereas Rotunda proposed the possible stakeholders to work with them. Action plan for activities between the period M1-M6 of the project was presented at the first project plenary meeting too.

Engagement phase. To identify the pilot's most suitable SIP, UL proposed to use the SEROI+ methodology which combines socio-economic and environmental return on investment (SEROI) assessment with open innovation (OI). As the SEROI+ methodology supports public and private bodies in selecting, developing and designing new products and services that respond to the needs of their communities, the engagement phase consisted of two SEROI+ workshops: in Šmarje (March 2024) and in Padna (April 2024). During both workshops local stakeholders were identified, an open innovation process, based on participatory approach was conducted, good practices related to the pilot's target sectors were presented and a questionnaire on environmental education was distributed. Alongside two workshops, communicative events to present the project of Smart Era were organized too.

Data collection phase. The following methods were used to collect data for the pilot: Data from literature review: Rotunda provided statistical data for the pilot and local plans and strategies of both communities. UL collected data obtained from the SEROI+ workshops, questionnaire on environmental education and 2 reports on the digital maturity of both territories, conducted by using Territorial digital assessment tool (results in annex of the pilot). As SEROI+ methodology offers to perform SWOT analysis too, it was possible to collect data for the SWOT analysis too. During this phase UL conducted the research review of the different reports, plans and strategies available, in particular in relation to policy dimension.

Data analysis phase. The data analysis phase is based on four level analysis, resulting in three lines of results: results, resulting from the SEROI+ workshops, results from the questionnaire on environmental education, results from the Territorial digital assessment tool and the analysis, provided by the SWOT analysis.

Figure 3 - Pictures of workshops held in Šmarje-Padna

2.6 PILOT 6: DEVETAKI PLATEAU

Preparation phase. The preparation in the Devetaki Plateau region started straight after the kick-off meeting in Trento with DPA providing information about the project and its objectives to the three municipalities. Meetings were held with the mayors of Letnitsa, Lovech and Sevlievo to explain them about the possibilities that SMART ERA could provide for the development of their villages. Although the municipality of Letnitsa withdrew as an official partner in the project, they declared they would support the implementation of the project - the collection and analysis of data, the SIPs elaboration and its implementation in the 3 villages of the municipality. The Municipality of Sevlievo officially stepped in as a community activator, and the Municipality of Lovech also declared readiness to support and disseminate the project findings and results.

Engagement phase. As for the local stakeholders, Devetaki Plateau Association has over 140 members in the region - representatives of various social groups: farmers, elderly people, young families, small rural businesses, and local administrations. They were all informed about SMART ERA through DPA’s communication channels and through face-to face activities. The message delivered to them has been that it is up to the active participation of all local stakeholders to achieve tangible project results that will help the modernization of their villages.

Data collection phase. For the collection of data, two approaches were used:

- For engaging the stakeholders in elaborating the SWOT analysis a special format called Future Search Conference was used. The format is a structured interactive discussion allowing every participant to express their opinion on the internal and external factors that have influenced and can influence the area in the future. The participants (50 - 60 people) were grouped in 7 working tables that changed in the different sessions. Thus, in the first session they were able to first discuss Achievements and Challenges, which were later translated into the Strengths and Weaknesses parts of the SWOT analysis. The different tables had their own aspects that differed in some parts and overlapped in others. In the consequent session we discussed the external trends that (could) affect the development of the region in a positive or a negative way. As a result, it was obtained a broad picture containing the visions of the various stakeholder groups and that is how was defined the Opportunities and Threads parts of the SWOT.
- As for the collection of statistic data, official sources were used such as: municipal administrations data, the National Statistics Institute as well as the Local Action Group strategy and some other trusted sources of information.

Data analysis phase. The following step was to analyze all the data and to come to certain findings and directions to work on the elaboration of the SIPs.

Figure 4 - Institutional meeting with regional administrations in Devetaki Plateau

3. PILOTS PRESENTATION

3.1 PILOT 1: VALLE DI SOLE

3.1.1 Short Pilot Overview

PRESENTATION

- **Location:** Located in the Trentino region of northern Italy.
- **Geography:** Surrounded by the Adamello-Presanella, Ortler-Cevedale, and Brenta mountain ranges.
- **Climate:** Alpine climate with cold winters and mild summers.
- **Tourism and Activities:** Popular for skiing, snowboarding in winter, and hiking, mountain biking in summer. It has natural parks like Stelvio and Adamello Brenta.
- **Economy:** Mainly based on tourism, agriculture (apple orchards), and dairy farming.
- **Culture:** Rich in traditional festivals, local cuisine, and historical sites.

CHALLENGES ADDRESSED

- Creating a more balanced and greener ecosystem for rural development and activating unexpressed potential
- Combating landscape degradation
- Finding countermeasures to depopulation

TARGET SECTORS	KEY TARGET GROUPS	KEY OBJECTIVE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Forestry ▪ Agriculture ▪ Pastoralism ▪ Sustainable tourism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Local and provincial decision-makers and policy creators ▪ Organizations monitoring and managing natural parks and green areas ▪ Small businesses in agriculture, forestry, and livestock ▪ Local community (residents, associations) ▪ Businesses related to tourism ▪ members of educational institutions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The key objective of the pilot is to leverage the protection and valorization of the environment and the landscape as a driver for the sustainable development of the local economy and community. ▪ To support the above key objective, data and knowledge are essential to support the assessment, decision-making and monitoring actions. Community and stakeholder involvement is also key. ▪ The pilot opens opportunities to investigate data-driven tools to support capacity building, decision-making and the collaborative development of new policies, services, and initiatives aimed at strengthening agriculture, forestry, livestock farming, and sustainable, innovative, nature-based tourism, as well as the resident community' quality of life, and that of young generations in particular.

3.1.2 Pilot Summary

Trentino is an autonomous province in the North of Italy. Its territory is predominantly mountainous, comprising the southern part of the Alps, extending from the border with South Tyrol in the north to Veneto in the south. It has numerous valleys, typically long and narrow, adorned with forests.

The inner area of Valle di Sole - located in the north-western part of Trentino - is a remote and peripheral area with a sparse population and communities often isolated from larger urban centers

providing services (see figure 5). Valle di Sole counts 13 municipalities, with an extended mountainous area and a total resident population of 15.470 inhabitants (2022). The valley's economy is significantly based on tourism, both in summer and winter. However, the tourism impact is not homogeneously distributed within the valley, with higher concentration in the centers of Mezzana (Marilleva), Folgarida, Vermiglio (Passo del Tonale), and Peio. Other important income sources include livestock farming and forestry. In the lower municipalities, which enjoy a milder climate, the cultivation of fruit trees is also present (apple and cherry trees).

Figure 5 - Pictures from Valle di Sole - On the left, the village of Caldes. At the centre, Vermiglio in winter. On the right, the landscape.

Depopulation is related to a decreasing birth rate, worsened by emigration within the provincial territory, towards other provinces or abroad, and by the reduction in inbound migration. Other critical issues are related to the ageing of the population and urbanization in the liveliest centres, which are more attractive in terms of job opportunities, mainly linked to tourism. Accessing services is particularly challenging due to geographical constraints, and these communities have experienced a gradual decline in essential services such as healthcare, education, training, and transportation to and from other areas in the province. However, inclusion is fostered by a strong sense of solidarity and cooperation ingrained within the community.

Due to the specificities of its local development and the complex challenges it faces, Valle di Sole is one of the mountain areas part of the Italian National Strategy for Internal Areas (see Figure 6).

Figure 6 - Location of Valle di Sole

In Figure 6, on the left, a map of Italy highlighting the location of the 72 areas included in the National Strategy for Inner Areas. The red circle indicates the location of Valle di Sole (image source¹). On the right is a zoomed visualisation of the location and the borders of the 13 Valle di Sole municipalities (image source²).

3.1.3 Organizations Involved

Pilot Orchestrator

Fondazione Bruno Kessler (FBK) is a research institution located in Trento, Italy, that conducts interdisciplinary research in various fields, including information technology, materials science, social sciences, and humanities. FBK collaborates with academic institutions, industry partners, and government agencies. The FBK team involved as the Trentino pilot orchestrator includes researchers from the i3 Research Unit (Intelligent Interfaces and Interaction). i3 leverages User-Centred Design and Participatory Design approaches to define and analyse design problems, co-design solutions, and evaluate digital technologies in collaboration with the final users of such systems. The group has a long and consolidated experience in innovative processes that consider both digital and social factors and has matured expertise in working with public bodies and local administrations to boost innovation practices (e.g., EU-funded projects: INTERLINK³, NEVERMORE⁴, FAMILIES-SHARE⁵).

Community Activator

The Autonomous Province of Trento (PAT) is a regional government authority responsible for governing the Trentino province in Italy. PAT administers various public services within the province, including education, healthcare, transportation, and social services. The specific department involved in SMART-ERA is the Territorial Cohesion Office, which coordinates and defines programming and design instruments, including operational ones, to support local development actions. The office also supports the programming and implementation of the National Strategy for Inner Areas, including monitoring, evaluation, and control actions, and conducts analyses and research on territorial development interventions. In SMART-ERA, the Territorial Cohesion Office has strong connections with the local communities of Valle di Sole because of previous collaborations developed as part of the National Strategy for Inner Areas. The National Strategy for Inner Areas is a political intervention activated by Italy to promote the development of rural or mountain areas distant from the centers of provision of health, education, and mobility services. It is a place-based policy shared with the European Commission as part of the partnership agreement for 2014-2020 and 2021-2027. The interventions benefit from 50% state funding and 50% European structural funding. The Province of Trento coordinates the actions carried out in its territory through a governance committee.

¹https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Strategia_nazionale_per_le_ree_interne#/media/File:Mappa_ree_pilota_SNAI.jpg

² https://www.branding4resilience.it/?page_id=1585

³ <https://interlink-project.eu/>. See [Not et al. 2024] for an overview of the research questions investigated within the project.

⁴ <https://www.nevermore-horizon.eu/>

⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/780783>

3.1.4 Motivations and Key Expected Outcomes

Context

Issues and criticalities of Valle di Sole are, first of all, related to the ageing of the population and the difficulties in creating attractive educational and entrepreneurial opportunities for the young. The abandonment of more remote and small villages by young people for centers offering more job opportunities (mainly related to tourism) and better equipped with services is accompanied by the abandonment of traditional activities related to land use and maintenance. These phenomena have severe implications for the area, such as the degradation of landscape quality, the increase of environmental risks (such as landslides and mudslides), and the deterioration of the built environment because of the high costs of renovating old houses in the center of villages.

In general, the main problems for Valle di Sole identified in the analysis reports of the National Strategy for Inner Areas and as emerged from the activities conducted with local stakeholders are the following (*source*: Strategia aree Interne 2019 and 2016):

- Ageing population and imbalance in generational turnover.
- Limited higher education offer and concurrent outmigration of the few young graduates from the valley in search of better job opportunities: a concern for the future and the innovation of companies primarily linked to tourism in the valley.
- Weak interactions between economic sectors like tourism, agriculture, and craftsmanship; inadequate valorization of the many opportunities offered by the valley's culture, environment, gastronomy, sports, and various forms of recreation.
- Impoverishment of some productive properties (also located in visible places along road axes), ageing and obsolescence of some accommodation facilities, and poor maintenance of the housing stock of second homes due to generational turnover, resulting in decreased use by heirs and consequent deterioration.
- Abandonment of marginal agricultural areas and pastures and the resulting land management problem.
- Underdevelopment of the agri-food sector, which is very much related to a larger vision encompassing sectors like the protection and valorisation of the environment, the landscape, ecology, health, and innovative forms of entrepreneurship. The area was once dedicated to livestock farming, which ensured regular maintenance and care of the land. However, with the decline in this practice, the land now suffers from neglect, leading to increased vulnerability to rockfall, landslides, and other natural hazards. Therefore, it is crucial to restore the landscape to its former state of beauty and utility and enhance safety through risk monitoring and management.
- Distance from services located in the provincial capital.

Current situation

Depopulation in peripheral areas of the Valley and the ageing of the resident population impact the management of essential services (assistance to vulnerable population groups, school transportation, need for multi-grade classrooms, etc.) due to the fragmentation of users, difficulties in educational orientation and educational paths, leading to an increase in youth discomfort due to lack or precariousness of employment. Since the 1970s, Valle di Sole has focused on tourism, especially winter tourism, to overcome economic backwardness and isolation linked to its traditional rural mountain life. However, due to the financial and climate crisis, efforts have been made over the past decades to rethink the tourism-centred development model. There is a widespread awareness that innovation is needed in the sector and that effort should be put into improving service quality, valuing the valley's historical and environmental potential, and proposing a new, more integrated development model that harmonizes agriculture and environmental conservation.

Paradoxically, some areas of Valle di Sole experience depopulation and overtourism at the same time. In both situations, **social, environmental, and economic balance is the condition that must be achieved in order to mitigate the phenomena**. For example, the fragilities of the tourism sector in Valle di Sole are related to high seasonality, high disparity across areas (with peaks of overtourism in certain villages and under-valorisation of others), but also sensitivity to climate change (lack of snow and high temperatures hampering winter tourism), and environmental damage due to extreme weather hazards and biohazards. The gradual abandonment by the young generation of traditional productive activities related to land use further intensifies the problem of land maintenance.

For all these reasons, Valle di Sole is called to restore the value of agriculture, forestry, and natural areas subject to protection by including them in a systemic reasoning for the territory.

Limits to overcome

The general challenges related to the thematic area addressed by the pilot are the following:

- **Creating a more balanced, green ecosystem for rural development and activating unexpressed potentials.** This challenge involves:
 - Solving the lack of tools for estimating the discounted value of multi-system services related to grassland, pasture, and woodland areas and promoting this value increase;
 - Understanding which performance indicators are required for a new socio-economic and environmental balance;
 - Creating more synergies between tourism and the environment, with the promotion of natural parks, models of slow tourism and alternative circuits, which value natural resources still under-considered in the economic development processes (agri-food, nature-based experiences, water-related sports) and are more resilient to climate change;
 - More generally, filling the lack of implementation of the "green budget" concept in decision-making.
- **Combating the degradation of the landscape and its snowball effects.** This challenge involves:
 - Defining protection strategies that improve the resilience to natural hazards favoured by climate change (e.g., storms, parasites, floods, drought);
 - Improving the management of forestry, agricultural, and grazing land also with incentives and actions addressed to overcome the dualism safeguard/valorization;
 - Stopping the decrease of economic activities based on land use;
 - Reversing cultural changes and a lack of policies supporting land care by local communities.
- **Finding countermeasures to depopulation and ageing.** This challenge involves:
 - Developing awareness among the local population about the role that sustainably managed rural areas have in improving the quality of life, the resilience of rural communities, and the capacity to stay of young generations;
 - Inverting the trend of reduced work opportunities for young people;
 - Spotting light on the weakening of cultural identity and the importance of community participation.

Future desired scenario(s)

The future vision of the Valle di Sole, as emerged from local stakeholders, can be summarised in the following statement: ***The protection and valorisation of the environment as a driver for the sustainable development of the local economy and community.***

Using the words of the mayors of Valle di Sole: "The future desired scenario is one in which the environmental balance (green budget) is included in the strategic choices of local public administrations and major private players, in order to ensure authentic sustainability for local communities and businesses operating in the area. The economic sectors of tourism and crafts, which are the driving force behind the local economy, will therefore be able to include in their development plans a risk assessment with respect to the value of these assets, which are often not considered but decisive."

As explained in the Methodology section (section 2.1), the cross-cutting thematic area of the Valle di Sole pilot has emerged from a joint discussion by the 13 mayors of the Valley, who own a deep understanding of the social, economic, and environmental context of the territory and maintain a constant, open dialogue with the local communities.

Starting from the reflection that natural resources represent one of the most important assets for the valley and have historically represented one of the pillars of the cultural identity of its population, the protection and valorisation of the landscape and the environment has been identified as the lever for a multi-systemic action. The desired effect is to consolidate the "green" identity of Valle di Sole at all levels, to improve the synergies between different economic sectors (forestry, agriculture, tourism, craftsmanship), to create awareness and capacity of action in the community for joint efforts towards improving quality of life and revitalizing cultural identity and vocation, to strengthen education and entrepreneurship opportunities for young generations.

First of all, the objective of land protection resonates with the "15. *Life on land*" SDG goal included in the 2030 UN Agenda for Sustainable Development⁶ that advocates for sustainable management of natural resources, combating land degradation and preserving biodiversity. Then, the pilot purposefully intends to complement environmental "resilience" with "valorisation", as a driver for the sustainable development of the local economy and the empowering of the local community to act for a better quality of life and improved capacity to stay (addressing the SDG goals "11. *Sustainable cities and communities*" and "8. *Decent work and economic growth*").

Value proposition and expected impacts

The expected impact of the pilot is the improvement of development sustainability in its environmental, social, and economic dimensions with reference to the entire territorial area of Valle di Sole. The mayors of the valley expect to:

- Improve the **management of woodland**, agricultural, and pastoral areas, as well as of nature-based tourism solutions;
- Obtain **active participation** of local communities in the strategic choices and active contribution to the socio-economic balance of the territories with a focus on sustainability, especially from young generations;
- **Quantify** the direct and indirect impact of land conservation, monitoring, research, and enhancement actions on the improvement of the quality of life in Valle di Sole;
- Define a **methodology that allows comparison** with other projects in other sectors that are evaluated with economic parameters and referred to market prices;

⁶ <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

- Consider **environmental costs as investments** whose benefits are passed on to current and future local communities.

The pilot opens opportunities to investigate data-driven tools to support capacity building and decision-making and the collaborative development of new policies, services, and initiatives that strengthen agriculture, forestry, livestock farming, and sustainable, innovative nature-based tourism.

To support the above key objectives, data and knowledge are essential to help with the assessment, decision-making, and monitoring of actions. Community and stakeholder involvement is also crucial.

3.1.5 Socioeconomic and Demographic Data

The following data describe the socioeconomic and demographic situation of Valle di Sole. They are taken from official statistics (mainly for 2022) produced by ISPAT (Statistical Institute of the Autonomous Province of Trento) and by the Reports developed as part of the National Strategy for Internal Areas (SNAI). The full list of collected data and indicators can be found in **Annex A2**. In the following, the main relevant indices are described.

Territory and population

Valle di Sole counts a total resident population of **15.470 inhabitants**.

The overall surface is 611,53 km², with a **population density of 25.3 inhabitants per square kilometer**. The population is distributed across **13 municipalities**.

The average age of the residents is **46.7 years**, with males averaging 45.6 years and females averaging 47.7 years. The age distribution is:

- [0-15]: 13.31%
- [15-65]: 70.9%
- [>64]: 16.1%

The mortality rate (number of deaths recorded in one year/1.000 inhabitants) is 9,5, while the birth rate is 7.1. (number of births recorded in one year/1.000 inhabitants), showing a **demographic negative growth**.

The **gender distribution is fairly balanced** with 50,6% female and 49,4% male.

The population counts **6,8% of foreigners**, while the percentage is 8,4% in the Province of Trento.

This demographic data reflects an ageing population and a depopulation trend. From a demographic perspective, however, the situation does not appear critical in absolute terms but rather in terms of uneven distribution across municipalities and age groups. In the Valle di Sole, depopulation occurs in small areas and scattered settlements, which have significant value in territorial control and preservation of landscape characteristics. Areas particularly affected by demographic decline are, for instance, Rabbi, Peio, and high-altitude settlements in the municipalities of Mezzana, Commezzadura, and Malè.

Economy

The economy of the valley is driven primarily by tourism and secondarily by agriculture. These two sectors show elements of job retention and positive future prospects, but they exhibit significant seasonal variations, impacting the stability and continuity of both employment and social relationships (Report SNAI 2019).

The employment rate among the resident population was 51,3% in 2011, quite similar to the rate of the Province of Trento: 52,9% (2011).

Concerning the economic indicators, there is little disaggregated data for the Valle di Sole.

Pilot specific: Tourism, Agriculture and Environment

Tourism. As said, the tourism sector is the driving sector for the valley economy, and the area witnesses at the same time phenomena of depopulation in some areas and over-tourism in others. There are several differences among the municipalities based on various indicators. For instance, if we consider the accommodation index (Total number of beds in accommodations for tourists / total number of residents), the scores show high variability among municipalities (e.g., Municipality of Mezzana: 6.8 and Municipality of Caldes: 0,2) where higher values are associated with the higher importance of tourism for the municipality's economy. Concerning tourism intensity (that is the average number of tourists in accommodations per day / total number of residents), high variability exists among municipalities, showing that tourists are concentrated in a few areas. Indicators concerning over-tourism also stress the fact that while some municipalities show low levels of tourist presence (e.g., Caldes, Cavizzana, Croviana), other areas are particularly affected by the phenomenon of over-tourism (Dimaro-Folgarida, Mezzana).

Agriculture and environment. Concerning agriculture, the "Index of variation of agricultural farms" - which tracks the number of agricultural farms over different census years relative to the base year, 1982 – shows a significant and steady decline in the number of agricultural farms in the Valle di Sole from 1982 to 2010. A pronounced decline in agriculture is also witnessed when looking at the number of agricultural farms with livestock relative to the population over nearly three decades (number of agricultural farms with livestock per 1,000 residents: 66,3 in 1982 - 12,5 in 2010).

In the Valle di Sole, land use is predominantly characterized by forestry. This is supported by the fact that 45.5% of the total surface area is designated as protected areas (Stelvio National Park, the areas of the Noce river, and the Adamello Brenta Nature Park, which are subject to protection and preservation measures).

Other significant land uses include cultivated land and pasture. This distribution reflects the region's emphasis on conservation and sustainable land management alongside agricultural activities.

3.1.6 Data Available

The pilot in Valle di Sole will focus on the valorization of natural resources as catalysts for sustainable transitions, such as slow tourism and agri-food development, revitalizing rural areas, and enhancing residents' quality of life. A mapping of the main current data sources has been done in relation to these sectors to identify the existing datasets and sources that could be used and integrated.

- **Statistical indicators for the Province of Trento** segmented by districts (Communities of Valley) and municipalities (Source: ISPAT). The provincial office for statistical data provides an extensive range of detailed indicators that model the socio-economic context of the Province of Trento. Several indicators are segmented by district (Communities of Valley) and municipality. Annual time series are available. Several sectors are covered, such as Land usage, Environmental issues (e.g., waste production and recycling), Population, and Work Market.
- **Predictive models for selected indicators for the Province of Trento** segmented by districts (Communities of Valley) (Source: ISPAT). For a selected set of indicators, predictive models envisage the value of the indices in 10 years' time. Currently, available indicators are related to population evolution.
- **Comparison of statistical indicators of the Province of Trento with other areas in Italy** (Source: ISPAT). For a selected set of indicators, comparison is offered between the data of (i) Trentino, (ii) the adjacent province of Alto Adige and the region of Veneto, (iii) the overall area of Northern-East Italy, (iv) the region of Lombardia, (v) Northern Italy and (vi) Italy.

- **List of public services** (Source: OpenData Trentino) They provide information about available public services like schools, social and health services, associations.
- **List of points of interest and public services** (Source: OpenStreetMap) Information about points of interest and public services available in Valle di Sole have been annotated inside the Open Street Map and are available for export.
- **Data on transportation services** (Source: Gestione MITT - Mobilità Integrata Trasporti Trentino) Information about public transport infrastructure (bus lines, timetable, geo-referenced bus stops).
- **Mobility data** (source: Trentino Digitale) Daily mobility data, aggregated by bus line or ticket selling channel. Data extracted from onboard ticket check-in.
- **Real-time statistical data for the Tourism sector** (source: ISPAT). Different types of data are available for the tourism sector, such as data updated daily on arrivals and overnight stays (with restricted access), monthly and seasonal statistics, etc.
- **Real estate registry and land registry** (source: Trentino Digitale). Data on urbanization and fractionation of the land, parcels in land and buildings registry, destination/cultivation of land parcels.
- **Weather** (source: Meteotrentino / OpenData Trentino). Weather information to be utilised in field operations planning (cultivation, harvest), tourism planning, or decision-making for risk prevention.

A detailed description of the dataset identified so far can be found in **Annex A3**.

3.1.7 Cross-Collaboration(s)

The pilot of Valle di Sole will benefit and will be further enhanced by the collaboration with other projects and initiatives. We list the institutions and initiatives that might provide opportunities for collaboration in the following.

Cross-collaborations at local/regional level:

- **Fondazione De Marchi** (FDM) is an instrumental body of the Autonomous Province of Trento. Its main areas of competence are local communities' social and cultural development, emphasizing a multigenerational approach. FDM research might benefit the project consortium because of its welfare and social innovation expertise. It provides consultancy to entities and organizations for the innovation of community and mountain welfare projects and the development of organizational models for social and healthcare services. It conducts research activities, monitoring, evaluation, and impact assessment of projects and services. It also facilitates participatory design and collaborative procedures between Public Administrations and Third Sector Entities.
- **Statistical Institute of the Province of Trento** (ISPAT) prepares the provincial statistical program and its updates, the annual activity program, and the report on the activities carried out in the previous year. It promotes and coordinates the development, production, and dissemination of statistics of interest to the provincial administration within the framework of the provincial statistical program.
- **Trentino Mountain Academy**, part of TSM (Trentino School of Management), promotes individual and collective knowledge and interinstitutional cooperation for mountain use, the enhancement of the Alpine environment, and the construction of a strategic vision for the future of the highlands of Trentino. It collaborates with several local associations of professionals (e.g., Alpine Guides, Provincial Ski Masters College of Trentino, Association of Medium Mountain Guides, etc.) for training on general topics considered important for the territory.

Cross-collaboration at EU level:

- **NEVERMORE** is a 4-year project funded by the EU that is determined to support excellence in research on climate science and climate policies. Trentino, a hotspot for climate change in mountain areas, is one of the 5 case studies focusing on tourism. FBK coordinates the project and supports the local case study coordinated by the Tourism and Sports Service of the Autonomous Province of Trento (PAT).

3.1.8 Regulatory Framework

In the following, the main programs are presented, such as laws, plans and regulations affecting the rural policies both at the national and regional sectors and other regulatory frameworks developed more specifically for the protection of the environment and the well-being of the youth population.

Provincial and national policies for rural development

- **Provincial Plan for Rural Development (PSR)**. It supports the European Agricultural Fund (EAFRD) intervention for the biennium 2022-2023. The Rural Development Program is the instrument of the European Agricultural Fund (EAFRD) through which the Autonomous Province of Trento will implement interventions that guide the development of Trentino according to the objectives of EU policies and the needs of the local context ([link to the website](#)).
- **Internal areas strategy for the Valle di Sole 2019-2024**. Italy's National Strategy for “Inner Areas” (SNAI) is an innovative policy for the development and territorial cohesion to counteract marginalisation and demographic decline within “Inner Areas” throughout the country. SNAI relies on a place-based policy grounded on a new multilevel local governance for integrated local promotion and development, addressing demographic challenges and responding to the needs of territories penalised by significant geographical and/or demographic handicaps. The internal areas strategy for the Valle di Sole was established in 2016 as the second project area for the province of Trento within SNAI, initiated following the approval of the Partnership Agreement 2014-2020 for the use of European structural and investment funds ([link to the website](#)).

Other relevant policies

- **Sectoral Plans for Forest Management, within the Research and Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialisation (2021-2027)** of the Autonomous Province of Trento. The European Union has implemented the instrument of Research and Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialisation - RIS3 to improve and strengthen the effectiveness of public policies in support of research and innovation. For Trentino the objectives are: i) Enhancing the competitive strength of the Trentino economic system, ii) Promoting employment growth in the region ([link to the website](#)).
- **Provincial Sustainable Development Strategy (“SproSS”)**. In 2018, the Autonomous Province of Trento started a path to define a Provincial Sustainable Development Strategy, culminating in 2020 with the issue of the Preliminary Provincial Strategy Document (approved by Provincial Council resolution no. 2062/2020). The process ended with the publication of the Final Provincial Strategy Document in 2021 ([Link to the document](#)).
- **Measures to mitigate the damages caused by the bark beetle infestation (Bostrico)** in local forests. Financial incentives of the Autonomous Province of Trento, Resolution 1303 of 20th July 2023, to use funds allocated by law n.234 issued on the 30th of December 2021 ([Link to the initiative](#)).
- **Provincial Youth Area Plan**. Established by Provincial Law "Youth" No. 5/2007, it represents a voluntary initiative of local authorities aiming to activate actions in favour of the youth population in its broadest sense, including pre-adolescents, adolescents, young people, and young adults

aged between 11 and 29 years old. The Youth Area Plans launch a call for projects each year targeting associations, public entities, and other third-sector entities.

3.2 PILOT 2: TRAMUNTANA / SÓLLER

3.2.1 Short Pilot Overview

PRESENTATION

- **Location:** Situated on the northwest coast of the island of Mallorca.
- **Geography:** Surrounded by the Tramuntana mountain range and the Mediterranean Sea.
- **Climate:** Mediterranean climate with hot, dry summers and mild, wet winters.
- **Tourism and Activities:** Known for its citrus and olive groves, scenic train ride to Palma, hiking trails, and beach activities. The Port de Sóller is a popular tourist destination.
- **Economy:** Tourism is the main economic driver, complemented by agriculture (particularly citrus fruits).
- **Culture:** A blend of traditional Mallorcan culture with influences from various periods of history, reflected in local architecture and festivals.

CHALLENGES ADDRESSED

- **Poor digitalisation and data sharing.** Connectivity is still a major issue (no 5G, problems with WIFI). Poor offer of digital services by municipality and local companies. Lack of knowledge and competences in technology and innovation of local stakeholders. Limited availability of data, and extremely low level of data-sharing and integration between local stakeholders.
- **Limited mobility.** Sóller is situated in a remote area, accessible solely through a tunnel or narrow mountain roads. Saturation of the public transports, parkings available and road network.
- **Demographic.** “Lack of talent” and brain drain phenomenon with young people moving to larger cities in search of better opportunities. Negative demographic growth.
- **Important seasonal changes and tourism massification.** High seasonality of the tourism and agriculture sectors. High tourism flows mainly in the peak seasons generating important social issues (mobility, housing, dimensioning of public services and infrastructures, coexistence of residents and tourists,...)

TARGET SECTORS	KEY TARGET GROUPS	KEY OBJECTIVE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Tourism ▪ Agri-food ▪ Mobility ▪ Culture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Local tourism and agri-food stakeholders ▪ Local community (residents, associations) ▪ Public administration ▪ Tourists 	<p>To foster the digitalisation of the local economy and enhance the quality and availability of digital services, with the aim to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Retain the active population and improve the coexistence between residents and tourists. ▪ Increase collaboration and involvement of local stakeholders (esp. tourism and agriculture sectors) in the co-definition and co-development of new products, services, business models, policies and/or initiatives. ▪ Improve the competitiveness, distribution and diversification of the local economy through digitalisation. ▪ Improve the mobility and sustainability of the destination.

3.2.2 Pilot Summary

Sóller is a rural town located in the northwest part of Mallorca, in the Balearic Islands. Nestled in a lush valley surrounded by the Tramuntana mountain range (a well-protected UNESCO site), Sóller is a popular tourism destination and is known for its stunning natural scenery, including orange, lemon and olive groves. The town is situated approximately 30 kilometres from Palma, the capital of Mallorca, and is only accessible via a tunnel, two narrow mountain roads or a historic railway known as the *Ferrocarril de Sóller*. Sóller has a population of around 14,000 residents that counts with a significant number of foreign nationals. In addition, the town experiences important seasonal population fluctuations due to the intense tourism activity in the region. Its economy is very traditional and mostly based on agriculture and tourism. The city and its region are suffering from several socioeconomic challenges that hinder its development:

- **Demographic.** Even though the population is well-balanced in terms of gender (almost 50% of each sex), there is a brain drain phenomenon and a lack of talent with young people moving to larger cities in search of better opportunities (employment and housing). This contributes to the ageing of the population of Sóller, which is further accentuated by the fact that young people are replaced by older foreign nationals, and that the region suffers from negative demographic growth.
- **High seasonality and tourism dependency.** The local community is very traditional with an economy mostly based on agri-food and tourism. The challenge for both these sectors is their high seasonality. Sóller, like much of Mallorca, heavily relies on tourism as a primary economic driver. While tourism brings significant revenue, it also accentuates some socioeconomic challenges such as mobility, infrastructure strain, environmental concern, or the housing and real estate (influx of tourists and expatriates has considerably driven up property prices, making it challenging for locals to afford housing).
- **Digitalisation/Connectivity.** Digital connectivity is deficient (4G with shadows and no 5G, many problems with WIFI connection). Digital services offered by the municipality and the local companies are very poor. There is no disaggregated data and no data sharing among sectors and stakeholders.
- **Mobility/Accessibility.** Sóller is located in a valley, secluded from the rest of the cities of the island due to the mountain range that surrounds it. The deficiency of public transport combined with the intense influx of tourists during the high season, generate important issues of mobility, with saturation of the roads and parkings.

The pilot aims to address some of the aforementioned challenges through a digitalisation of the local industrial ecosystem, and through the development and implementation of digital services and activities that contribute to improve the sustainable development of the town while retaining the local population and enhancing the coexistence between residents and tourists.

Figure 7 - The Valley of Sóller (left) and the historical tram of Sóller (right)

3.2.3 Organizations Involved

Pilot Orchestrator

ANYSQL is a dynamic SME founded in 2014 and located in Palma de Mallorca, Spain. Recognized as an Innovative SME (*PYME Innovadora*) by the Spanish National Ministry of Economy, Industry, and Competitiveness, ANYSQL operates two main departments: European project management, whose members boast over 20 years of experience in the field, and engineering. These departments collaborate to develop successful projects across various domains.

The company specializes in strategic methodologies and projects within Research, Development, and Innovation; Agriculture; Tourism; Smart cities and destinations; and Emergencies/natural hazards, among others. Through cooperation and shared knowledge, ANYSQL crafts efficient innovation strategies tailored to the socioeconomic needs and requirements of each sector. Throughout the project, ANYSQL will further develop and enhance its data platform (NADIA), federated with SMART ERA, to improve overall features, data accessibility, and services.

Community Activator

+CULTURA is a company that works in the field of cultural management, tourism and heritage. It was founded in 2013 and its mission is to provide its clients with a unique experience to get to know the region through different eyes. +CULTURA makes the history, traditions and customs of the valley of Sóller known to both residents and visitors.

+CULTURA is committed to sustainable and quality tourism, following and fulfilling many of the objectives of the UN Agenda 2030 for sustainable development. In addition, it follows the guidelines of Orange Tourism, which is based on creative, experiential tourism and digital transformation. The development of the company is closely linked to agriculture. +CULTURA is continuously creating events in favor of the Local Products, the Tramuntana Mountain Range and Agriculture. +CULTURA is a permanent member of the Board of the *Consortium of the Serra de Tramuntana*, Friends of the Cooperative of Sóller and Members of APAEMA (Majorca Association of Organic Farmers).

3.2.4 Motivations and Key Expected Outcomes

Context

Prior to the inauguration of the Sóller tunnel in 1997, accessing the municipality was restricted to maritime routes or navigating through two narrow mountain roads situated to the south and north of the area. Nowadays, the tunnel constitutes a section of the Ma-11 highway, connecting Palma de Mallorca, the capital of the island, to the Port of Sóller, improving accessibility and transportation connections with the rest of the Island. Furthermore, it is possible to travel to the valley by an historical railway. However, the historical trains are mainly employed as a tourist attraction and are rarely used by local residents.

The economy of the Valley of Sóller is deeply rooted in agriculture and tourism, two sectors characterized by their seasonal nature. Despite their long-standing presence, there exists minimal interaction between these industries, hindering potential synergies until today. Moreover, a significant challenge arises from the departure of young residents seeking higher education, who often opt to study and pursue employment opportunities in Palma or on the Spanish mainland, contributing to a brain drain phenomenon and therefore impacting local workforce sustainability.

From a tourism perspective, the Valley of Sóller is renowned as one of Mallorca's most enduring tourist destinations. It has a great diversity of natural, cultural and historical heritage that is increasingly cherished and repurposed for tourist and educational purposes. The municipality offers

a solidified sun and beach model in Port de Sóller and has also seen significant tourist development in the center of Sóller. However, this sustained growth in tourism has brought a surge of daily visitors to Sóller, presenting ongoing challenges to maintaining harmonious coexistence between tourists and residents.

Demographically, the municipality is experiencing an imbalance in generational turnover. The death rate exceeds the birth rate (10,4 deaths compared to 7 births per 1,000 inhabitants in 2022), leading to a population decline since its peak in 2013. It is important to mention that this peak was primarily due to an influx of foreigners (non-Spanish), who nowadays make up around 18 % of the local population.

Current situation

From a technological perspective, the municipality of Sóller is characterized by poor digitization efforts from both the local administration and stakeholders across all sectors. Due to its location, the municipality still lacks 5G and reliable Wi-Fi connections. Previous digitization initiatives, such as the traffic information screen system at the Sóller tunnel intended to monitor congestion in parking lots and roads, have never functioned properly. The lack of interaction between local stakeholders extends to a deficiency in the opportunities of data sharing and digital knowledge exchange. Furthermore, obligatory data collection processes, such as those in the tourism sector, are not standardized, hindering the availability of local data joint data collection and data analysis.

From a tourism perspective, the Valley of Sóller, along with near-by villages such as *Deià* and *Valldemossa*, has become a mandatory stop for tourists visiting the Tramuntana mountain range of Mallorca. This influx of tourists has accelerated the local economy but also causes temporarily uncontrolled streams of visitors to Sóller, both for day trips and extended stays (eg, according to the Spanish Statistical Office, in April 2024 Sóller achieved the highest hotel bed occupancy rate at national level, averaging 83.1%, with this figure rising up to 87% on weekends).

As a result, uncontrolled tourism flows burden local residents by disrupting mobility, leading to traffic congestion and parking saturation. Additionally, the high demand for accommodations has fueled an increase in illegal vacation rentals within the municipality, further reducing availability in the regular housing rental market. The shortage of affordable housing and mobility issues have led to growing discontent among local residents over the last years. Consequently, in May 2024, the General Directorate of Traffic (DGT) announced emergency measures to address vehicle congestion in Sóller, including restricted access to the urban center during peak times. To tackle the illegal renting issues, Sóllers public administration assigned 25 inspectors to regulate vacation rentals. However, the operational procedures of these inspectors have proven inefficient, failing to address the root of the problem and allowing illegal rentals to persist.

In addition to the complex housing situation, other factors are impacting the well-being of the local community. There is a lack of centralized leisure and cultural offerings which are integral to the local identity. Some of the most famous festivals are the annual "*Firo de Sóller*" (reenactment of a historic battle between the Moors and Christians) and festivities around the local products such as oranges and olives.

Despite the significance of Sóllers local products, the primary sector in the municipality encounters various challenges: (i) the gradual decline of traditional productive activities among the younger generation, evident in the aging demographic of farm managers, with an average age surpassing 60 years; (ii) the effects of climate change, leading to water scarcity and directly affecting the productivity of local crops; and (iii) the competitiveness of small-scale producers is hampered by their limited access to subsidies and poor knowledge on digitalization for production and sales.

Limits to overcome

The current situation in the municipality of Sóller reveals multiple challenges and limitations affecting all of the pilot’s target sectors. Overcoming these limitations will not only support the successful co-development and implementation of the SIP for Sóller but will also ensure the creation of an innovative, smart and sustainable local economy, beneficial to the whole community.

For this reason, it will be essential to address the primary and most overarching limitation within the municipality: the lack of intra- and intersectoral cooperation among local stakeholders. Not least, since this deficiency currently leads to inefficient management of local resources, fragmented tourism/cultural offerings and poor communication, both internally and externally.

However, the lack of cooperation stems not only from an entrenched focus on individual socioeconomic ecosystems and the absence of supportive policy frameworks. It is furthermore compounded by local stakeholders' limited knowledge of innovation and digitalization opportunities as well as inadequate local provision of digital services and infrastructure, both by the local municipality and local companies.

Furthermore, addressing limitations related to the brain drain phenomenon and lack of talent is essential for ensuring the long-term retention of a resilient population. Presently, younger residents frequently relocate to Palma or the Spanish mainland in pursuit of educational and employment opportunities, motivated by restricted job prospects and a lack of affordable housing within the municipality. The limitations of the local housing market are aggravated by high demand for tourist accommodation. This heightened demand has resulted in a surge of illegal vacation rentals which in turn contributes to uncontrolled tourism flows within the municipality.

However, the uncontrolled tourism flow not only contributes to housing market limitations but also exacerbates mobility challenges within the municipality. In recent years, the uncontrolled influx of personal or rental cars of tourists led to parking and circulation issues, persisting beyond the high season. Moreover, restricted access to the municipality via tunnels or narrow mountain roads, combined with inadequate public transportation options, further compounds limitations in mobility.

Regarding limitations in housing and mobility, uncontrolled tourism flows pose a significant concern for the local community, which strives to foster better coexistence between tourists and residents. It should be noted that the municipality has made efforts to address this issue; however, these endeavors have largely fallen short of success. Consequently, the local communities' discontent not only poses limitations but also raises barriers and fosters mistrust among residents towards innovative approaches in tourism and related sectors.

Future desired scenario(s)

By overcoming the limitations and addressing the challenges and needs identified through the methodology described in section 2.2, local actors can progress towards a more desirable state. The overall envisioned scenario is an empowered rural community flourishing through the digitalization of its economy and the enhancement of the quality and availability of digital services.

In this scenario, local stakeholders collaborate both within and across sectors (tourism, agri-food, culture and mobility) to co-define and co-develop new and sustainable products, services, business models, adequate policies, and initiatives. This cooperative approach will drive the digital transformation of the local economy, enhancing its competitiveness and fostering diversification of the local offer.

The digitalization of the local economy will enable the availability and sharing of data that are specific to the territory of Sóller, enabling in turn, a better monitoring and management of the destination as a whole. This would allow, for instance, a better management of the tourist and traffic flow, or a better efficiency in the use of resources

Additionally, by addressing current mobility issues and promoting the municipality as a sustainable and smart tourist destination, the coexistence between residents and tourists will improve. The aim is to create a harmonious balance where the community feels visited, not invaded, enabling both residents and tourists to enjoy diverse cultural and touristic offerings. This approach also ensures that residents, including younger generations, have a better access to affordable housing and job opportunities within the municipality.

Value proposition and expected impacts

Throughout the project an individual SIP for Sóller will be co-developed, implemented and validated. The SIP will define Sóllers smart and community-led pathway towards an empowered, sustainable, resilient and inclusive rural community, equipped with innovative and smart solutions that increase access to services, opportunities and an adequate innovation ecosystem.

In particular, it is expected that the implementation of the SIP will contribute to:

- **Digitalization of the local economy.** This will foster data sharing across sectors and stakeholders, and therefore will enable the identification of new products, services and business models that could contribute to diversification of the local economy (promoting sectors such as agriculture, technology of culture), and a better distribution all year-round.
- **Increased knowledge and competences.** Training programs will be implemented to upskill local workforce and raise knowledge and awareness on digitalization, innovation, and sustainability, among others. This will contribute to increase the digital literacy of the population, and to ensure the success and uptake of the digital services to be provided within the municipality.
- **Increased cooperation between sectors and stakeholders** (particularly from tourism and agriculture). The project will contribute to activate and engage the local community, fostering collaboration between sectors and stakeholders that usually do not relate to each other.
- **Policy review.** The project and pilot’s activities (along with its SIP) are expected to influence policies at local level to address some of the identified challenges and needs (eg, regulation of illegal vacational houses, housing policies to better protect local residents, categorization of agricultural soils and urban gardens, better management of traffic/tourists flow...).
- **Improved sustainable development and quality of life.** The implementation of adequate policy framework, together with digital solutions and community engagement activities will contribute to: (i) foster harmonious coexistence between tourists and residents; (ii) to better monitor and manage the different socioeconomic activities within the territory; and (iii) to retain young and local population and improve the well-being of the local community.

3.2.5 Socioeconomic and Demographic Data

Territory and population

All the following “territory and population” data are official statistics from 2022 produced by the Regional Statistical Institute of the Balearic Islands (IBESTAT⁷).

As previously mentioned, the municipality of Sóller is enclaved within the Tramuntana mountain range. With a population of **13.454 inhabitants** for a surface of **42,8km²**, Sóller has an intense population density (**315 hab/km²**).

The local population is distributed among four areas belonging to the municipality of Sóller: the city of Sóller (67% of local population), the Port of Sóller (18%), l'Horta (12%) and Biniaraix (3%).

The average age of the population is **44,62 years**, a bit higher than the regional average (42,11 years), and the age distribution is:

- [0-15]: 14%
- [15-65]: 65%
- [>64]: 21%

It should be noted that the mortality rate exceeds the birth rate (10,4 deaths for 7 births per 1.000 inhabitants), causing a **demographic negative growth**.

The **gender distribution** is fairly balanced with 50,5% female and 49,5% male.

The population counts a significant amount of foreigners with **18%** of inhabitants being non-spanish.

Economy

As it happens for most of the socioeconomic indicators, there is no disaggregated data for the municipality of Sóller. The gross disposable income of households per capita of Sóller is **17.227€** (Ibestat, 2021).

Pilot specific: tourism, agriculture and mobility

In the frame of the pilot, data and statistics about the tourism, agriculture and mobility sectors in Sóller have been identified and collected. The full list can be found in **annex B3**. Hereafter are described the main relevant data.

Tourism (2024 data from the open data catalog of the Balearic Government):

- **62 tourism establishments** (hotels, aparthotel...), accounting for **1.547 rooms and 3.159 beds**, distributed between Port of Sóller (19 accommodations), Sóller (42) and Biniaraix (1).
- **623 houses** officially listed as vacation rental (tourist housing), accounting for **3.313 beds**.
- 3 travel agencies
- 4 rent-a-car companies

It should be highlighted that there is **no disaggregated tourism data** for the municipality of Sóller. A lot of statistics and data exist and are available, but only at regional and island level.

⁷ <https://ibestat.es/>

Agriculture (2020 data from the Spanish National Institute of statistics):

169 agriculture exploitations, amounting for **668,86 hectares** of fields and crops (average farm size is 4ha).

The use of agricultural soil is distributed between: arable land (4,3%), fruit farming (89%), permanent grassland for livestock (6,5%) and urban gardens (0,2%).

47 farms are dedicated to livestock: sheeps and goats (85,4%), pigs (1,1%) and poultry (13,5%)

The gender distribution is significantly unbalanced in this sector, with **73% of men for 27% women**. Same thing occurs with the age distribution, with a considerable **aging of the farmers** (close to 80% of the farm managers are older than 55; 52% are older than 65; and not even 10% are younger than 44).

- [< 25]: 1%
- [25-34]: 2%
- [35-44]: 4%
- [45-54]: 15%
- [55-64]: 26%
- [> 65]: 52%

The statistics on the **educational level of farm managers in Sóller** also highlight the needs for training and upskilling:

- 81,8% agricultural experience exclusively
- 15,9% agricultural training courses
- 0,6% agricultural vocational training
- 1,8% university and/or higher agricultural studies

Mobility: there is no open data about mobility for Sóller. Some generic data are available from some stakeholders (e.g., TIB, Historical train Sóller, Municipality), but no data is currently shared, collected and integrated. One of the objectives of the pilot will be to collect and integrate this data from different sources.

3.2.6 Data Available

The pilot in Sóller will focus on the digitalization of the local economy, focusing specifically on the tourism and agricultural sector, but also on mobility and cultural sectors. As such, a mapping of the main current data sources has been done, to identify the existing datasets and sources that could be used and integrated.

In addition to open statistical data sources, such as the national and regional institutes of statistics, the following types of data have been identified:

- **Mallorca Tourist Accommodations**, that provides a mapping of tourist accommodations in Sóller/Tramuntana.
- **Mallorca Tourist Housing**, that provides a data set of tourist housing registered on the island of Mallorca.
- **Mallorca Tourist Centers**, that provides a dataset and identification of all registered tourist centers on the island.
- **Mallorca Gastronomy and Entertainment**, a mapping of gastronomy and entertainment possibilities in Sóller/Tramuntana.
- **Mallorca Car Rental**, that provides a mapping of car rentals in Mallorca (including Sóller).

- **Mallorca Tourist Guides**, that provides a dataset of people qualified to exercise the activity of tourist guide in the Balearic Islands.
- **Mallorca “Active Tourism” companies**, a dataset of the companies that carry out recreational, sports and adventure activities registered on the island of Mallorca.
- **Tourist Intermediation Companies Mallorca**, a dataset of travel agencies, tourist mediators and reservation centers on the island of Mallorca.
- **TIB - public transport of the Balearic Islands**, mapping with real-time data of public transportation on the archipelago.
- **Sóller Air Quality**, real-time and historical data on air quality in Sóller

For each of these data sources, an identification and description of the following indicators has been performed: data owner, sensitivity, access model, short description, purpose of usage, data format, average size of the data item, volume of data, frequency of acquisition.

The results of this mapping exercise can be consulted in **annex B4**.

3.2.7 Cross-Collaboration(s)

In the frame of SMART ERA, the pilot of Sóller will benefit and will be further enhanced by the collaboration with other projects and initiatives, in particular thanks to the participation of ANYSOL in numerous European projects.

Cross-collaborations at local/regional level:

- **DISTINTIVO**. "[Distintivo](#)" is a Council of Mallorca initiative to recognize local products and services promoting the preservation of “Serra de Tramuntana”. During the SMART ERA project the initiative might provide useful insights or data concerning local products and potential rural tourism activities.
- **DIBAI-TUR**. The Digital Innovation Hub of the Balearic Islands ([DIHBAI-TUR](#)) is focused on Artificial Intelligence as a disruptive technology that will assist in the digital transformation of companies in the Balearic Islands. Possible synergies and insights for companies related to the development of Sóller can and will be exploited.

Cross-collaboration at EU level:

- **Data4Food2030**⁸. This Horizon Europe project aims to improve the data economy for food systems by expanding its definition, mapping its development, performance and impact to create new insights and opportunities. ANYSOL is the leader of the case study "Circular Economy 4 Tourism (I4DATA)" in Mallorca, which aims to improve efficiency and reduce the environmental impact of current production methods. The study involves data-sharing, analysis, and data-driven decision-making to analyze and identify sustainable business models for the local vineyard and almond sectors in Mallorca. Exploring synergies resulting from the processes of data-sharing and analysis in the agri-food sector could provide valuable insights for the SMART ERA project.
- **SPADE**⁹. The strategic objective of the SPADE project (Horizon Europe) is to develop an intelligent ecosystem to address the multiple purposes concept in the light of deploying unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs alias drones) to promote sustainable digital services for the benefit of a large scope of end users in sectors of crop production, forestry, and livestock. ANYSOL is leading one of the three open-field case studies of the project. This case study,

⁸ <https://data4food2030.eu/>

⁹ <https://spade-horizon.eu/>

located in Mallorca, focuses on potato crops and terraced crops. The terraced crops, primarily situated in Sóller, include citrus and olive orchards. This study could offer valuable insights into crop diseases, droughts, among other factors. The projects and case study findings might provide valuable insights for the target sectors of agri-food and related rural tourism in Sóller.

- **D3HUB¹⁰**. ANYSOL is leading the deployment of the EU Competence Center to support data management in Smart Destinations. The D3HUB project has six main objectives: (i) Build a knowledge support scheme to assist tourism destinations across the European Union; (ii) Provide tailor-made digital solutions and data for DMOs and tourism SMEs; (iii) Test the already developed framework through a pilot run by a critical mass of DMOs; (iv) Integrate results and learnings into a business plan to set up and sustain the Centre; (v) Upscale beyond the partnership and build a data-driven tourism community; and (vi) Implement the Centre and ensure its continuity. The experiences and results of the project, such as tailor-made digital solutions and data for DMOs and tourism SMEs, could support the development of SMART ERA pilots by identifying synergies or offering additional ideas for the SIP creation.
- **DEPLOYTOUR**. ANYSOL is leading DEPLOYTOUR, a strategic EU project that aims to develop a trusted and secure common European data space for tourism. This data space will provide the ecosystem with access to information, with an impact on productivity, greening and sustainability, innovative business models and upskilling. It will give the possibility of aligning offers to tourists' expectations, adapting service proposals to new tourist groups, predicting a high influx of tourists, and thus, allow planning of resources more efficiently, and creating new business opportunities. As DEPLOYTOUR promotes digital transition and aims to make the European tourism sector greener, sustainable and more competitive through data exploitation and digitalization, it is directly aligned with the pilot's objective, and will contribute to build a more resilient, transparent, and efficient tourism sector.

3.2.8 Regulatory Framework

A study of the regulatory framework in force in the Balearic Islands has been undertaken to make sure that the codefined plans and activities in the pilot of Sóller are aligned with the local, regional and national strategies. Hereafter are presented the main programs, laws, plans and regulations affecting the definition of the pilot action plan of Sóller:

- **Rural development program (RDP) 2023-2027**. In the Balearic Islands, the budget increased by 6% to 144 Mio. EUR compared to the last period.
- **Plan for digitalisation of the tourism sector** in general, also considering rural tourism: Modernization and competitiveness plan of the tourism sector - Spain June 2022 ([Link to document](#))
- **Strategy for the agricultural and rural world**: 2nd Action Plan 2021-2023 Digitisation strategy of the Agri-food sector and the natural environment ([Link to document](#))
- **Sustainability and circularity of tourism**: the Balearic Islands have adopted a new law on urgent measures to promote the sustainability and circularity of tourism, introducing a strategy for circularity. The strategy, which sets out a vision for 2030, puts forward measures to boost the sustainability and circularity of the tourism industry on the islands. It also aims to decrease annual tourist flows and enhance the quality of the sector.
- **Sóller Tourism Strategy Development Plan 2023** whose mission is to enhance and strengthen the identity and personality of Sóller. This document is especially relevant as it provides local insights of the situation in Sóller. In the frame of SMART ERA, the action plan

¹⁰ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/d3hub-eu-competence-centre-to-support-data-management-in-tourism-destinations/>

for the pilot of Sóller will have to be fully aligned with the objectives of this document, that are: (i) To promote the foundations for Sóller to be considered an excellent tourist destination; (ii) To turn Sóller into a tourist destination where tourism and the daily life of the residents of the town are in complete harmony; and (iii) To bring the cultural attractions and products proposed to the residents of the town themselves and increase their participation in the cultural and tourist world. More specifically, the strategic objectives of the Sóller Tourism Strategy Development Plan 2023 are:

- Creation of new quality tourist products based on cultural resources and others existing in the town, which allow at the end of the process a better positioning of the municipality of Sóller in the tourist market of Mallorca with respect to other similar destinations.
- Ensure that the entire municipality actively participates in the promotion of the tourist products created.
- Obtain greater economic, social and cultural growth for the residents of Sóller and for local businesses.
- To rescue, recognize and revalue intangible cultural heritage. (with help of research facilities)
- Draw up a Town Brand Plan for Sóller and consolidate it.
- To achieve a high level of satisfaction on the part of the resident population in terms of coexistence and the arrival of visitors

3.3 PILOT 3: NORTHERN OSTROBOTHNIA

3.3.1 Short Pilot Overview

PRESENTATION

- **Location:** Located in northern Finland, bordering the Gulf of Bothnia.
- **Geography:** Characterized by flatlands, forests, and numerous lakes and rivers.
- **Climate:** Subarctic climate with cold winters and short, warm summers.
- **Tourism and Activities:** Popular for its natural beauty, opportunities for fishing, hiking, and winter sports. It is also known for its Northern Lights.
- **Economy:** Forestry, technology, and energy production are significant. Tourism also plays a role, particularly eco-tourism.
- **Culture:** Finnish culture with a focus on outdoor life, traditional music, and festivals like the Kalajoki Music Summer.

CHALLENGES ADDRESSED

- For rural populations and tourists, it is difficult to find local well-being, maintenance and mobility service providers in rural regions due to limited markets and marketing.
- The number of microenterprises and SMEs providing services are low as the number of enterprises in the sparsely populated rural regions is low in general. The size of markets for companies may be insufficient.
- Starting platform economy-based business to rural regions needs an enough functional business model and revenue logic as well as enough large markets to operate.
- Fear of failure would prevent them from starting a business.

TARGET SECTORS	KEY TARGET GROUPS	KEY OBJECTIVE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Northern rural platform economy ▪ Digital platform services, small companies (especially well-being services, maintenance services and mobility) ▪ Tourism and seasonal living 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Service and technology microenterprises and SMEs ▪ Local community (residents, associations, public administration) ▪ Tourists ▪ Elderly ▪ Second home/cottage owners and users, remote and multi-local workers ▪ Business support service providers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ To implement a service platform economy solution to enhance rural services and markets for microenterprises and SMEs ▪ To enhance availability and quality of rural services and markets of rural small enterprises. ▪ To facilitate the connection between service providers and users.

3.3.2 Pilot Summary

The Northern Ostrobothnian pilot will focus on the service platform economy solution designed to improve both rural services and rural markets of microenterprises, small enterprises and middle-sized enterprises (MSMEs). The approach of this service platform economy-based solution is to support data-driven rural community development in terms of entrepreneurship, rural labour markets and availability of rural services. By boosting rural digital solutions for service entrepreneurship, the aim is to tackle long distances related challenges and also promote co-production of health and well-being services. Targeted service users and customer segments will be related mainly to tourism, second homes and (summer) cottages, housing for the elderly and supported housing, as well as remote workers. Smaller service enterprises will be the main business segment providing services in the platform.

The pilot area covers three rural municipalities, Alavieska, Kalajoki and Nivala, in the Nordic peri-urban area having a strong entrepreneurial ecosystem for MSMEs. Key problems are related to connecting the demand for local services to smaller-scale companies. Entrepreneurial activity in the target areas in MSME business sizes is intensive, and the role of micro and small enterprises is emphasized, so the pilot area provides promising conditions for piloting. The municipalities of Alavieska, Kalajoki and Nivala are all committed to be supporters and stakeholders in the project, and they will collaborate also via their business support services to promote the pilot activities.

Figure 8 - Pictures of Northern Ostrobothnia landscape (a) municipality of Alavieska; (b) municipality of Kalajoki; and (c) municipality of Nivala

3.3.3 Organizations Involved

Pilot Orchestrator

The University of Oulu (UOULU) is an international science university with the aim to create new scientific knowledge based on strong research and provide research-based education to build a more sustainable, intelligent, and humane world with a dedication to creating global impact and accelerating innovations. Kerttu Saalasti Institute is one of the specialized academic research institutes of University of Oulu focusing on micro-entrepreneurship, regional excellence and future production technologies. Kerttu Saalasti Institute is focused on multidisciplinary international research, the promotion of expertise and the development of responsible solutions with partners. Kerttu Saalasti institute is responsible for micro-entrepreneurship research and education at the national level in Finland appointed to the University of Oulu by The Ministry of Education and Culture.

The Smart ERA pilot orchestration - targeted to develop platform economy of rural micro-enterprises and SMEs and piloting the activities in Northern Ostrobothnia - supports well Kerttu Saalasti Institute's strategic goals: pioneering the development and implementation of new ways of working and solutions, and building an entrepreneurial society as well as in interactive partnership in building a well-being-creating and sustainable future. The Institute's research outputs are intended to be used

to strengthen business operations, and its researchers are active influencers in key regional, national and international networks.

Community Activator

The Council of Oulu Region (C.OULU) is a statutory corporation of municipalities in its region, in which every municipality must be a member. The regional council is a powerful advocate of its municipalities. The regional council seeks resources for regional development and gathers the forces of the region's actors together. The regional council markets and manages the available funding opportunities.

Smart ERA community activities are in line with C.OULU strategies (e.g. regional program and smart specialisation strategy). The project implements the regional program in terms of content. The goal of the project is to secure the competitiveness of rural and remote areas and areas suffering from demographic change by utilizing digitalization. This happens by testing and developing digital infrastructures and services (on remote platforms that work) for companies and citizens to manage competence. In addition to digital connections and services, better targeted location-specific measures are also needed, which are being piloted in the project.

3.3.4 Motivations and Key Expected Outcomes

Context

Finding different services reaching home is a challenge in rural environments due to smaller markets and longer distances. Small businesses may not have a website, or may not be well known in the markets, or may otherwise be difficult to access, even though the provided services would have demand in the markets.

Current situation

Services of small businesses are often not widely digitally marketed or reached e.g. at municipal level. Presently, marketing often relies on the local knowledge and traditional media outside tourism centres. For example, catalogues of provided services are not well available, and platform economy-based solutions popular in cities are not applied.

Limits to overcome

The new platform economy based ‘service directory/catalogues’ should be a comprehensive source of local service provider companies and should also attract users and provide an efficient place for booking and selling services. Mobility-related services could potentially be included as well. Optionally, service logistics related issues and optimisation of reaching multiple customers in efficient order could be included. The financing of the costs of maintaining the service directory and the financial logic for ensuring its functionality have to be feasibly designed, so that the platform service provider, enterprises using the platform, as well as the customers, all have a rewarding experience.

Future desired scenario(s)

The aim is to create a scenario where service providers and customers meet effortlessly through a digital platform. This platform will act as a bridge, connecting the supply and demand sides of rural services. It will have an intuitive, user-friendly interface that allows for easy discovery, booking and purchase of services. In addition, the platform can support logistical optimisation to ensure that

service providers can efficiently manage their routes and schedules to effectively reach multiple customers.

Value proposition and expected impacts

Satisfied customers in rural regions who find, reach and purchase the service they need via platform economy-based solutions. The small enterprises will get more customers and sales and will benefit from platform economy-based growth in the area. Thus, they have the potential to employ new persons and also generate more tax revenue. Overall, the regions' service levels increase, which leads to a better quality of life, higher attractiveness, and more vital economies.

3.3.5 Socioeconomic and Demographic Data

The municipalities of Alavieska, Kalajoki, and Nivala in Finland exhibit distinct socio-economic and demographic characteristics, as illustrated by recent statistics. Together, these municipalities cover a total surface area of **3,180.7 km²**, with Kalajoki accounting for the largest portion due to its significant sea area. The combined population of these regions is **25,263 inhabitants**, with Kalajoki being the most populous at 12,372 inhabitants.

Population trends from 2022 to 2023 show slight declines in Alavieska (-1.8%) and Kalajoki (-0.6%), while Nivala experienced a marginal increase of 0.2%. Population density varies across these municipalities, with Nivala having the highest at **19.8 inhabitants per km²**. The average age in these areas is slightly higher than the national average, with Kalajoki having the oldest population at an **average age of 45.3 years**.

Age distribution reveals a **higher proportion of elderly residents** (65+) in Kalajoki (27.6%) compared to the national average of 23.4%. This higher elderly population contributes to a high dependency ratio in these regions, with Nivala at the highest (82.8%).

Gender distribution is relatively balanced, with a slight male majority in Alavieska (52.8%). Birth and mortality rates indicate natural population declines in all three municipalities, with rates of natural increase being negative.

Economically, the Nivala-Haapajärvi sub-region has a lower GDP per capita (€32,314.2) compared to the Ylivieska sub-region (€36,155.9). Gross disposable income per household is also similar across the municipalities, with Kalajoki having the highest average at €45,308.

The primary sources of household income vary, with earned income being the largest component, followed by current transfers. Employment distribution shows a significant portion of the workforce engaged in service sectors across all municipalities.

3.3.6 Data Available

Some open data are available at national level. For example, **road network data** managed by Traficom is publicly accessible and offered in Esri Shapefile and GeoPackage formats. This data, updated quarterly, supports vehicle routing and logistics planning with high accuracy and coverage. Similarly, Fintraffic offers **public transport data** in the General Transit Feed Specification (GTFS) format, enabling multimodal passenger routing and public transport optimization, with updates at least annually.

Other datasets include **business registers** from Statistics Finland, which detail enterprises and are available for a fee, facilitating local enterprise collaboration. **Population grid data**, also from Statistics Finland, provides demographic insights at a 1x1 km resolution for service logistics

planning. **Data on second houses**, available under license with restrictions, helps estimate holiday season populations. **Mobility data** from Telia Finland Oyj tracks population flows based on mobile phone data, available daily under a fee-based model. Lastly, local business support organizations offer enterprise contact details through **CRM data**, accessible via mutual collaboration and updated monthly.

The data available are described in further detail in the **Annex C2**.

3.3.7 Cross-Collaboration(s)

Cross-collaborations at local/regional level:

- **OYSTER Health and Life Sciences incubator** (knowledge exchange related to platform economy based digital health and wellbeing services), funding by ERDF.
- **Naturpolis and City of Kuusamo** (Knowledge exchange related to platform economy-based initiative to enhance service string, customer journey and service design)
- **KASVA** - Sustainable growth in SMEs through regional collaboration of research, innovation, and business development services (Knowledge exchange related to the rural platform economy experiences in the context of public business services, entrepreneurs, researchers and RDI experts around the North Ostrobothnia), funding by Just Transition Funds by ERDF.
- **ClimateFood** - Climate-Smart Food via Cross-Border Cooperation has aim is to “climate-smarten” SME food businesses operating in different roles of food ecosystems in Finland (Northern Ostrobothnia, Lapland) and Sweden (Norrbotten, Västerbotten), funding by Interreg Aurora.

3.3.8 Regulatory Framework

Regional Strategies

Regional Programme of Northern Ostrobothnia 2022-2025¹¹. The Regional Programme of Northern Ostrobothnia is a comprehensive development strategy aimed at promoting long-term growth and welfare in the Oulu Region of Finland by combining a strategic plan for 2040 with actionable projects for a four-year period. The programme has an impact on local communities in several ways, e.g. economic growth, quality of life and education & skills and community engagement.

Smart Specialisation Strategy 2021-2025¹². Northern Ostrobothnia’s Smart Specialisation Strategy aims to promote regional measures that address the challenges posed by climate change, digitalization, and globalization. By identifying strengths and areas for development, the strategy aims to create innovation ecosystems that help businesses renew themselves. Key pillars include cross-sectoral networking events, cooperation between companies and research institutions, strengthening company clusters (including micro-enterprises), ensuring up-to-date education provision, and securing skilled labor.

Climate Road Map 2021-2030¹³. The Northern Ostrobothnia Climate Roadmap 2021–2030 outlines a path toward carbon neutrality for the region. It focuses on themes like smart bioeconomy, energy

¹¹ <https://www.pohjois-pohjanmaa.fi/en/development/regional-strategic-plan-and-regional-programme/>

¹² <https://www.pohjois-pohjanmaa.fi/en/development/oulu-regions-smart-specialisation-2021-2024/>

¹³ <https://www.pohjois-pohjanmaa.fi/en/development/climate-roadmap-2021-2030/>

efficiency, low-emission transport, and sustainable land use, aiming for a carbon-neutral Northern Ostrobothnia by 2030.

Innovation and Skills in Finland 2021–2027 programme¹⁴. The Innovation and Skills in Finland 2021–2027 programme supports business, energy, climate, innovation, education, and employment policies. It includes measures funded by the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), the European Social Fund Plus (ESF+), and the Just Transition Fund (JTF).

Municipal Strategies

Alavieska municipality strategy. The municipality's mission is to be a modern, child-friendly and entrepreneur-friendly municipality with good local services. The aim is for every resident to feel well and satisfied with life. The key priorities of the strategy are: 1. Resident comfort and well-being, 2. Local services, 3. Entrepreneurship and business, 4. Branding.

Kalajoki municipality strategy. Kalajoki's municipal strategy aims to transform the area into a vibrant city by enhancing the quality of life for residents and attracting investments and tourism. The four focus points are: (i) Investment enabler: Kalajoki will invest in the future, expand the activities of the Port Business Park and develop new learning environments; (ii) A supporter of everyday life and growth: the city will provide quality services for families, the elderly and entrepreneurs, and develop educational opportunities; (iii) Quality of life and housing: zoning and housing policies support the attractiveness of the city and sustainable development; and (iv) Climate leadership: Kalajoki is committed to climate-friendly solutions and promotes the use of renewable energy

Nivala municipality strategy. The Nivala city strategy focuses on enhancing the quality of life for its residents, fostering local businesses, and promoting sustainability. Key priorities include developing comprehensive services for all age groups, supporting entrepreneurship through infrastructure and financial guidance, and emphasizing cultural and recreational opportunities. The strategy also highlights the importance of digital services, environmental responsibility, and active community engagement to ensure the city's growth and resilience.

¹⁴ <https://valtioneuvosto.fi/en/-/1410877/innovation-and-skills-in-finland-2021-2027-promotes-regional-vitality-employment-and-wellbeing>

3.4 PILOT 4: EAST HERZEGOVINA

3.4.1 Short Pilot Overview

PRESENTATION

- **Location:** Southeast part in Bosnia and Herzegovina.
- **Geography:** Rural region with two geomorphological units, high mountain and low Mediterranean Herzegovina.
- **Climate:** Mediterranean with long hot summers and short winters and continental with hot summers and cold winters.
- **Tourism and Activities:** Rich in historical and cultural sites, including medieval monasteries, Illyrian, Roman, Ottoman and Austro-Hungarian architecture. Outdoor activities include hiking and exploring natural parks.
- **Economy:** Agriculture (vineyards, potato, cereals), livestock, and increasingly tourism.
- **Culture:** Diverse cultural heritage influenced by Illyrian, Roman, Ottoman, Austro-Hungarian, and Slavic traditions.

CHALLENGES ADDRESSED

- **Depopulation of the region of East Herzegovina.** The region of East Herzegovina faces significant depopulation, with many residents migrating to urban areas or abroad in search of better economic opportunities, leading to a decline in the local workforce and community vitality.
- **Lack of visibility of the cultural, natural and gastronomic heritage of rural East Herzegovina.** Efforts are needed to enhance the visibility of East Herzegovina's rich cultural, natural, and gastronomic heritage, which remains underappreciated and under-promoted, limiting its potential to attract tourists and preserve local traditions.
- **Need for increased sustainable tourism development.** Rural East Herzegovina has to successfully establish itself as a distinctive brand in the tourist market, attracting visitors with its unique blend of historical sites, scenic landscapes, and traditional cuisine, thereby fostering sustainable local development.

TARGET SECTORS	KEY TARGET GROUPS	KEY OBJECTIVE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Cultural, natural and gastronomic heritage ▪ Tourism ▪ Agriculture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Producers of local products ▪ Rural women and young people ▪ Local tourist organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ To increase visibility of the cultural, natural and gastronomic heritage of rural East Herzegovina ▪ To attract a greater number of visitors in the area ▪ To increase sales and higher income from local products ▪ To develop and promote comprehensive tourism packages that highlight the unique cultural, historical, natural, and gastronomic attractions of East Herzegovina, enhancing visitor experiences through improved infrastructure, authentic local engagements, and effective marketing strategies targeting both domestic and international tourists with increased collaboration between local stakeholders.

3.4.2 Pilot Summary

Bosnia and Herzegovina comprises 4 tiers of governance, at the State, Entity, Canton and municipal levels. Bosnia and Herzegovina shall consist of two Entities: the Republika Srpska and the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina (Federacija Bosna i Hercegovina – hereinafter FBiH) and the Brčko District. The Republika Srpska is a unique and indivisible constitutional and legal entity comprising one level of local self-government with 57 Municipalities. (*Source: European Committee of the regions*)

East Herzegovina is a micro-region in the southeastern part of Bosnia and Herzegovina with the city of Trebinje at the centre of the region, and with municipalities such as Berkovići, Bileća, Gacko, Istočni Mostar, Kalinovik, Ljubinje, and Nevesinje. Geographically and climatically, there are two relief units: low Herzegovina, characterised by altitudes below 500 meters, and high Herzegovina, where altitudes exceed 500 meters. Low Herzegovina has a Mediterranean climate with hot summers and mild winters, while high Herzegovina is predominantly mountainous with short hot summers and long cold winters. The biodiversity of Herzegovina is abundant with numerous endemic plant and animal species. East Herzegovina is the least populated region in Bosnia and Herzegovina. The population density of East Herzegovina was 14,44 inhabitants per km².

Main economic sectors in East Herzegovina are agriculture, animal breeding and electricity production. This trend of decreasing population has never stopped, it has even worsened and has reached a point where we can talk about an exodus. Highly educated people are leaving the region, as well as the younger population, which disrupted the age structure and led to depopulation, first in rural areas, and then in the entire region. Road infrastructure is very poor, as well as tourist infra and suprastructure.

Despite the depopulation, and thanks to its geographical location, the proximity of famous tourist destinations of Dubrovnik in Croatia, Herceg Novi in Montenegro and Mostar in Bosnia and Herzegovina, the interest of tourists in East Herzegovina has been growing year by year. East Herzegovina, with its centre Trebinje, quickly became a popular cultural tourism destination and remained so even during the Covid pandemic. However, outside Trebinje city, there is a rural region with seven small municipalities, all of which stay in the shadow of the centre. After visiting Trebinje, tourists struggle to identify further reasons for a longer stay. However, the area is home to authentic rural communities hosting incredible and well-preserved unique traditions that might be transformed into unique and non-replicable rural experiences with the right support and capacity building. This is indeed a region with rich food biodiversity and a preserved tradition of producing various unique food products, such as cheese in a sack as the Slow Food Presidio product, which is now on pending Bosnia and Herzegovina's list for UNESCO intangible cultural heritage. The region from a gastronomic point of view is known for its potato, honey, wines, certain unique varieties of legumes and cereals. Young people leaving the country in large numbers, and small producers, primarily women, would be the main actors of a change. Creativity and competency in digital technologies would help small producers to be more competitive and visible.

Figure 9 - Pictures of East Herzegovina landscape and local products

- (a) Mountain Velez, Municipality Nevesinje; (b) Stećci (tombstones), Municipality Nevesinje;
 (c) Cheese in a sack, Municipality Nevesinje; (d) Lake Klinje, Municipality Gacko;

3.4.3 Organizations Involved

Pilot Orchestrator

Slow Food Trebinje Herzegovina¹⁵ (SFTH) was formed in 2009 as an informal group of citizens, and since 2021, it has been officially registered as a legal NGO entity. SFTH is a member of Slow Food International which is a global organisation that aims to prevent the disappearance of local food cultures and traditions and involves millions of people in over 160 countries. SFTH currently has 50 members that regularly participate in numerous local, regional and international events.

SFTH has implemented different projects: Virtual journey on the ancestors' paths, Valorisation of legumes and cereals from Trebinje area, Pažin honey - new souvenir on Via Dinarica trail, Cheese and honey trail of East Herzegovina, NatureBosniaandHerzegovina, Day of Cheese and Potato in village Bratač and ongoing project SMART ERA.

Community Activator

The Tourist Organization of the Republic of Srpska (TORS) is a public institution established in 2005 by the government of the Republic of Srpska, primarily focused on promoting and developing tourism in the Republic of Srpska, which is an autonomous entity within Bosnia and Herzegovina. It is under the supervision of the Ministry of Trade and Tourism of the Republic of Srpska. TORS aims to develop, preserve, and protect tourist values and develop tourism in the Republic of Srpska. It carried out tasks: promotion and improvement of tourism of interest, provision of tourist information and propaganda activities of the Republic of Srpska in the country and abroad, formation and development of the information system in tourism, realisation and coordination of international cooperation in the field of tourism.

¹⁵ <https://slowfoodtrebinje.com/>

3.4.4 Motivations and Key Expected Outcomes

Context

The area of rural East Herzegovina, according to historical data, has been inhabited since the time of the Illyrians (300-50 B.C.). Throughout the ages, East Herzegovina was part of the Roman Empire, the Ottoman Empire and the Austro-Hungarian Monarchy which made it a region with an enormous cultural and historical heritage. Since the region stretches from high mountainous Herzegovina, with the high mountains of Velež, Crvanj and Zelengora, to low Herzegovina with a Mediterranean climate, the rivers Trebišnjica, Zalomka and Mušnica, and fields such as Nevesinjsko, Gatačko and Popovo polje, particularly rich in the number of sunny days and limestone, that makes it a very attractive tourist region. The agriculture of Upper Herzegovina is based on animal husbandry, the production of potatoes and cereals, while in Lower Herzegovina viticulture and the production of vegetables and Mediterranean crops are more prevalent. The most famous products of East Herzegovina are cheese in a sack, Nevesinje potato, honey, poljak beans, dried mutton, dried figs, cereals and other vegetables and wine. The most famous events in the rural areas of the region are the Mountain Bike Race “Za sirac sira” in the village Žakovo near Trebinje, available not only for professional cyclists but to all who are willing to participate (especially young people who are encouraged to participate), the main prize is the homemade dried cheese, and the Nevesinje Olympics, made up of knightly disciplines, which lasts for 150 years. In the region there is one of 17 the most beautiful villages of Bosnia and Herzegovina (received the status through the implementation of the USAID Tourism project). East Herzegovina is an area particularly affected by the emigration of young people. The lack of prospects for young people, such as the impossibility of finding a job in the region after graduating from college, the poor choice of study programs in Bosnia and Herzegovina and cheaper studies in Serbia, for example, contribute to displacement. They reluctantly (almost never) decide to stay in the countryside. The municipalities of Nevesinje, Gacko, Kalinovik, Bileća and the city of Trebinje have local tourist organisations. East Herzegovina has poor road infrastructure, poor touristic infra and supra structure, small land parcels (in average 2ha per rural household), local administrations don't pay enough attention to the protection of cultural heritage in villages, there is not enough public awareness of the possibilities that rural tourism offers. Public transportation is almost non-existent, there are no local clinics, and no shops in the villages. The elderly population is isolated in every sense.

Current situation

Despite the rich cultural-historical, natural and gastronomic heritage of the region, rural tourism is in its infancy. In the entire region, there are only six registered households that provide rural tourism services, with another 15 households that are also involved in rural tourism. The implementation of the East Herzegovina Cheese and Honey Trail project contributed develop rural tourism in the region, with eight cheese and eight honey producing households that received initial equipment and knowledge for working with guests to provide rural tourism services and activities. Through this project, an informal group of five young artists and photographers was formed to create a map of Rural Eastern Herzegovina, design visuals for the Trail and produce labels for the products offered on the trail. Local tourist organisations are active in the promotion of the entire tourist offer of the municipality where they operate, but they are not specialised in the promotion and animation of residents to engage in rural tourism. Also, they are insufficiently active in promoting local products and organising events dedicated to their gastronomic specialties. There is only one store in the city of Trebinje, Herzegovinian house, that sells local products from East Herzegovina. In the region, there are a couple of mountaineering associations, several hunting and fishing associations and a couple of associations that promote local products such as the Association of Nevesinjski potato producers, the Association of breeders of Gatački cattle and the association of women from Gacko who produce kaymak (dairy product). There are no activities in the villages (except the Nevesinje Olympics and the MTB race “Za sirac sira” in the village Žakovo in Trebinje) or events that would in

some way give importance to the inhabitants of the villages. One of the first events of this kind is an event organised by the partners in this project, Cheese and Potato Day in the village of Bratač.

Limits to overcome

Since the beginning of the project SMART ERA, have been conducted surveys of consumers and buyers of local products from East Herzegovina, collected opinions of institutions from all levels of government in Bosnia and Herzegovina on the possibilities of rural tourism development, conducted research among local actors such as local tourist organisations, producer associations and other local groups, on the basis of which we identified problems and collected their views on how to solve them. To identify problems and the possibility of finding potential solutions, we also used official strategic documents at the BiH and Republic of Srpska level, such as Agriculture and Tourism Development Strategies, as well as scientific and professional works and statistical data. Among the identified shortcomings that are listed in the SWOT analysis (see section 4.3.4), the pilot aims to tackle the following ones:

- **To raise awareness at the local level** about the possibilities offered by rural tourism in East Herzegovina and encourage the population of rural areas to engage in rural tourism.
- To contribute to the **preservation of the cultural, historical, natural and gastronomic heritage of the rural areas of East Herzegovina** and make progress in shifting resources from the state of potential to the state of tourist product which can generate additional income for the rural population.
- **To motivate and engage young people** into creative work starting from the existing youth group within Slow Food Trebinje Herzegovina that will serve as a good example for other youth in the region to see that through promotion, all regions can create their own business, which would contribute to slowing down/stopping depopulation of region East Herzegovina.
- **To improve the visibility of rural East Herzegovina** in digital media, primarily through the improvement of the already existing map of Rural East Herzegovina and throughout Smart Innovative Packages help producers of local products of excellence to reach final consumer attracting them to come in East Herzegovina like a tourist and buy products directly from producers.
- **To motivate local tourist organisations** to pay special attention to the promotion of rural Eastern Herzegovina and its heritage.

Future desired scenario(s)

Desired scenario that would like to be achieved by implementing this project in East Herzegovina would look like this:

- Increased visibility of natural, cultural-historic and gastronomic heritage of rural East Herzegovina
- Increased number of visitors in rural East Herzegovina
- Increased length of stay in rural households providing accommodation
- Increased number of rural households engaged in rural tourism
- Increased awareness of local community of necessity to preserve, renovate and further investigate cultural-historical heritage in rural areas in East Herzegovina
- Legends, myths and local know how preserved and transferred to young generation
- Young ones motivated to employ they creative knowledge for the development of rural areas in East Herzegovina
- Local tourist organisations have given special importance to the offer of the rural heritage of the East Herzegovina region
- improved tourist infrastructure (existence of information centres for tourists, camping areas, trained local guides, marked walking and cycling paths, tourist signs leading to rural households...)

- An improved existing map on the site Slow Food Herzegovina Trebinje
- Easier sales of local products through digital channels
- Increased awareness at the local level about the importance of nature conservation
- Rural East Herzegovina become branded tourist destination

Value proposition and expected impacts

Project implementation in terms of economic and social benefits in rural East Herzegovina will contribute in the following way:

- By involving a larger number of rural households in rural tourism, additional income will be generated for rural households and thus their vulnerability in the economic sense will be reduced;
- Web platform of the Slow Food can significantly enhance the visibility and attractiveness of rural Herzegovina as a unique and desirable tourist destination (Providing interactive maps and suggested itineraries that guide tourists through key cultural, historical, and natural sites in rural Herzegovina, integrating culinary stops and local experiences, featuring stories, testimonials, and profiles of local farmers, chefs, and artisans to create a personal connection with the region and its people, offering tools for tourists to book farm stays, culinary tours, workshops, and other experiences directly through the platform, facilitating forums or social media integration where tourists can share their experiences, ask questions, and engage with the local community, highlighting collaborations with local businesses, tourism boards, and cultural organisations to offer comprehensive and authentic tourist experiences.)
- The arrival of a larger number of visitors will force local authorities to invest more in road and tourist infrastructure and the preservation of cultural, historical and natural heritage
- By involving young people in creative jobs, it will contribute to reducing their desire to leave East Herzegovina
- Gathering and passing on local knowledge will make the elderly feel less isolated
- If sales channels are improved, residents of rural areas will produce more products and thus generate more income for their families
- Local tourism organisations will realise that the possibilities of generating income from tourism in rural areas are possible, so they will pay special attention to the creation of itineraries for rural areas
- Image of entire region East Herzegovina will be improved

3.4.5 Socioeconomic and Demographic Data

Territory and population

All the following data are official statistics from 2023 and 2022 open data source of the Republic of Srpska Institute of Statistics and Agency for Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina.

As previously mentioned, the region of East Herzegovina consists of the city of Trebinje and municipalities: Nevesinje, Gacko, Bileca, East Mostar, Ljubinje, Kalinovik and Berkovici. With a population of **67.664 inhabitants** for a surface of **4434.94km²**, resulting in a **sparse population density** (15 hab/km²). The local population is distributed among these areas: the city of Trebinje (41% of local population), Nevesinje (18,5%), Bileca (15,6%) and all the others (24,9%).

The average age of the population is **43,84 years**, a bit higher than the state average (41,80 years), and the age distribution is:

- [0-19]: 21%
- [19-64]: 60%
- [>64]: 19%

It should be noted that the mortality rate exceeds the birth rate, causing a **demographic negative growth**. The **gender distribution is fairly balanced** with 50,5% female and 49,5% male.

Economy

Given that there are no disaggregated data on the gross domestic income by municipalities/cities in the Republic of Srpska, the only available data are at higher level:

- For the Republic of Srpska (data from 2022), GDP is 12,975.00 KM or **6,634 EUR per capita**.
- For Bosnia and Herzegovina (data from 2022), GDP is 12,656.00 KM or **6,471 EUR per capita**. (source: www.irbrs.net)

Pilot specific: tourism and agriculture

Tourism (source: 2023 and 2022 data from the open data source of the Republic of Srpska Institute of Statistics, Ministry of trade and tourism of Republic of Srpska):

- 53 tourism establishments (hotels, aparthotel, food and beverage...), accounting for 2925 beds, distributed between Trebinje (43 accommodations), Nevesinje (2), Bileca (4), East Mostar (1), Ljubinje (1), Kalinovik ana Berkovici (0), Gacko (2).
- 247 houses officially listed as vacation rental (tourist housing), accounting for 724 beds.
- 2 travel agencies
- 2 rent-a-car companies
- 35 licenced tour guides

There is statistical data for each of these municipalities in the Eastern Herzegovina region (number of beds, overnights, tourist tax income, employees in tourism...).

Agriculture (source: 2022 data from the Republic of Srpska Institute of statistics and Labour Force Survey from 2022)

- 54 thousand persons employed in agriculture in Republika Srpska.
- The number of persons employed in agriculture accounts for 13.3% of the total number of employed persons.
- Number of business entities in the agriculture sector in Eastern Herzegovina municipalities is 107.
- The gender distribution is significantly unbalanced in this sector, of the total 830 persons employed in agriculture, there are only 191 women (77% of men, for 23% women).

Mobility: there is no open data about mobility for East Herzegovina. Some generic data is available from some stakeholders (e.g., bus operators, Municipality), but no data is currently shared, collected and integrated.

Detailed table available in **Annex D5**.

3.4.6 Data Available

As the pilot of East Herzegovina will focus on increasing visibility of gastronomic, natural and cultural heritage of East Herzegovina with the aim to attract a greater number of visitors in the inner territory which will contribute to easier selling of local products, needed data are related to agriculture and tourism. In addition to open statistical data sources, such as the state and regional institutes of statistics, the following types of data have been identified:

Ministry of agriculture, forestry and water management of Republic of Srpska and Agency for agricultural payments:

- data related producers and agricultural production in EH
- data related subsidies and measures for development of agriculture and rural areas
- data related law and sub-law legislative acts

Ministry of trade and tourism:

- data related number of tourists visiting area
- data related subsidies in tourism
- data related laws and sub-law acts

Local tourism organisations:

- data related local actors dealing with tourism
- data relating state of art of cultural heritage

Associations of local producers, women’s associations, mountaineering associations and other relevant local stakeholders such as folklore associations, youth associations etc.

For each of these data sources, an identification and description of the following indicators has been performed:

- The entity or individual responsible for the data.
- The level of confidentiality and potential impact of data exposure.
- The method and conditions under which the data can be accessed.
- A brief overview of the data content.
- The intended use and applications of the data.

3.4.7 Cross-Collaboration(s)

Project NatureBosniaandHerzegovina, duration 2021-2024, Financed by Italian Agency for international development (AICS), and implemented by Italian NGO CISP. Under this project, SFTH is responsible for: (1) mapping of local communities in the neighbouring protected areas of Blidinje and Sutjeska, assessing their attitude to the exploitation and conservation of the natural resources of the two parks; (2) mapping of local businesses related to the direct or indirect exploitation of the natural resources of the Parks - stock breeding, plant cultivation and processing of milk, meat and fruits/grains; (3) training local business operators in sustainable behaviour and understanding the added value that stems from their connection with the protected areas; (4) Creating sustainable tourism offers and promoting it via Slow Food Travel and other relevant channels.

The contacts and data collected from this project will be used to identify local stakeholders, problems and potential solutions.

Developing Sustainable Tourism (Turizam) in Bosnia and Herzegovina, duration 2020-2025, Financed by US Agency for International Development, implemented by Chemonics International. The project supports the BiH tourism sector's recovery from the negative impacts of the pandemic by fostering collaboration among all levels of government, industry, and community stakeholders. This five-year \$20 million project is implemented by Chemonics International. TORS as a tourism related public institution in the Republic of Srpska has been collaborating since the beginning with the project dealing with several issues regarding tourism development in the region. SFTH closely collaborates on various aspects of development with the USAID Tourism Development Project in Bosnia and Herzegovina, primarily in the field of rural development. In 2020. USAID has started implementation of the project Development of sustainable tourism in Bosnia and Herzegovina within the framework of which the initiative mapping of the Most Beautiful Villages of Bosnia and Herzegovina was launched, modelled on the Federation of the Most Beautiful Villages of the World,

a project initiated by France in 1981. Through this activity, 17 of the most beautiful villages of Bosnia and Herzegovina have been mapped so far, and one of them is Bratač in the municipality of Nevesinje in the region of East Herzegovina. (<https://tourism-villages.unwto.org/>)

In addition, SFTH has implemented the **East Herzegovina Cheese and Honey Trail project**, which is the first implemented project that presents traditional local products as tourist attractions of the region.

In the area of Eastern Herzegovina, in the period after 2005, the Italian non-governmental organisation UCODEP implemented the **Taste Herzegovina project** through which it renovated several mini-cheese makers for making cheese from the bellows according to the old recipe.

Slow Food International has implemented the **ESSEDRA project** which began in December 2012 to promote rural development and that of small-scale producers in the Balkans and Turkey, through the reevaluation of traditional dishes, products, native species, and the promotion of local food biodiversity.

3.4.8 Regulatory Framework

In the Republic of Srpska there is a **Strategy for the development of agriculture and rural areas for the period 2021-2027**. In this Strategy within the general objective Revitalization of rural areas, specific objective Economic revitalization of the village is defined as a measure Support for rural and agritourism development projects. Based on the objectives defined in the Strategy, the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management of Republic of Srpska has allocated financial means for agritourism projects in 2022. Users who used these funds mostly spent them on equipping and adapting accommodation in agritourism.

Ministry of trade and tourism of the Republic of Srpska have a **Strategy for tourism development for the period 2021-2027**. In this Strategy as priority tourist resources in the Republic of Srpska, among others, are listed: agrotourism, food and beverages, festivals and events, observing nature, and so on. Further, Spatial development of tourism in the Republic of Srpska envisages six tourist zones, and tourism clusters with certain specificities are defined on their basis in terms of resources, experiences, activities and attractions. For each of the six clusters are given specific recommendations for the development of tourist products, which will be further elaborated within the framework of priorities and measures related to this strategic goal. East Herzegovina belongs to the Trebinje touristic zone. Priority 6 for the Trebinje tourism cluster states: Authentic gastronomic offers, including wines and handicrafts be included in the tourism value chain. Thematic culinary activities and manifestations offer to tourists a unique opportunity to have a closer contact with the local culture and in a fun atmosphere discover more about it. "Slow Food Trebinje" is a promising example of these kinds of experiences. Tourists want to taste characteristic food that reflects tradition, heritage and the culture of a place and which preserves its traditional forms of agriculture and cultural heritage.

Legal acts outlining rural tourism in the Republic of Srpska are:

- **Law on Tourism** (Official Gazette of Republic of Srpska no. 45/17, 16/23)
- **Law on hospitality** (Official Gazette of Republic of Srpska no. 45/17, 01/24) and
- **Law on Agriculture of the Republic of Srpska** (Official Gazette of Republic of Srpska no. 7/06, 20/07, 86/07, 71/09)
- The Law on Hospitality, in Article 13, which defines Forms of catering services and types of catering services objects recognizes the object of rural tourism as a special category. Rural tourism facilities are subject to accommodation categorization. The register of rural tourism facilities is managed by the Agency, which manages the Register of Agricultural Farms for the Ministry of Agriculture.

- On the bases on Law on Hospitality is adopted **Rulebook on the conditions for the provision of catering services in rural tourism facilities** ("Official Gazette of the Republic of Srpska", no. 15/20) which elaborate in details conditions which must be met by rural tourism facilities in order to engage in this activity.
- On the basis of Articles 23 and 11 of the Law on Hospitality, the **Rulebook on the appearance and content of standard plates for marking the categories of hospitality facilities of the hostel and rural tourism types** was adopted ("Official Gazette of the Republic of Srpska", number: 17/24).
- **Law on Agriculture**, in Article 20, which defines Support for supplementary activities on agricultural farms, states: Support for supplementary activities on the agricultural farm is intended for the production of traditional products from rural areas and the spread of agrotourism and eco-rural tourism, the processing of primary agricultural products into products of greater added value, as well as for the direct sale of agricultural products and other activities that can generate higher income on the agricultural farm.

Some of the municipalities of East Herzegovina (Trebinje, Gacko and Nevesinje) are in the process of adopting a rural development strategy for their area.

3.5 PILOT 5: ŠMARJE-PADNA

3.5.1 Short Pilot Overview

PRESENTATION

- **Location:** A small settlement in the Littoral region of Slovenia.
- **Geography:** Rolling hills and valleys with vineyards and olive groves.
- **Climate:** Mediterranean climate with warm summers and mild winters.
- **Tourism and Activities:** Known for wine tourism, local culinary experiences, and outdoor activities like hiking and cycling.
- **Economy:** Predominantly agricultural, with a focus on viticulture and olive oil production.
- **Culture:** Rich local traditions, wine festivals, and a blend of Slovenian and Mediterranean influences.

CHALLENGES ADDRESSED

- **Need for new sustainable mobility services**, especially for older groups on one hand and children and teenagers on the other hand due to lack of public transport service.
- **Need to raise awareness and knowledge** about territorial sustainable development strategy, underscoring the importance of environmental protection.
- **Need for increased involvement and participation of the local population** in green and sustainable shared activities, in particular in relation to mobility.
- **Need to improve the circular economy** in a manner of connecting main target sectors into a functional operating, long-lasting mobility service.

TARGET SECTORS	KEY TARGET GROUPS	KEY OBJECTIVE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sustainable mobility ▪ Circular economy ▪ Rural Tourism ▪ Environmental education 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Local community (Associations) ▪ Local administration & local political apparatus & municipality level (Koper) ▪ Mobility service providers (local, regional & national) ▪ Local tourism and agri-food SMEs ▪ IT infrastructure providers ▪ Tourists 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ensuring targeted novel solutions and services would be aimed to primarily improve connectivity to urban areas of coastal cities of Piran and Koper, accessibility and attractiveness of the area, create new public places, encourage shared activities in recreational areas, as well as create new jobs (e.g. sustainable tourism and farming). These solutions will function as a functioning digital ecosystem.

3.5.2 Pilot Summary

Šmarje is located in the Municipality of Koper in the Littoral region - Slovenian Istria of Slovenia. The village area covers the surface of approximately 7 km² and has a population of nearly 915 residents. The elevation is 289 m up to sea level. It is situated right in between the coastal urbanised cities and the rural area of Slovenian Istria. The village has been historically known as an important and strategic crossroads in the rural area of Slovenian Istria that on one side connects more than 20 neighboring villages in the region, but also three neighboring countries i.e. Slovenia, Italy and Croatia.

Padna is a village located in the rural area of Coastal Region of Slovenia in the Municipality of Piran and is situated on the end of the ridge, with steep slopes of terraces, where ‘cultura mista’ type of crops is grown. Economy of the village is strongly based on services such as trade, accommodation, and transport that are generated by activities at the port of Koper. In the port of Koper also tourists cruise ships have their stopping point. Both communities have an important historical and strategic role within the whole region of Slovenian Istria.

Šmarje offers several public services such as elementary school, medical assistance, post-service, food supply etc. Most families are complementary agri-households with their own land. In the last 20 years, new houses have been built by people who have emigrated from coastal urban areas or other regions of Slovenia. The village has been subjected to several development projects and initiatives since 2005 and has been approved as Smart Village in 2020. Due to available public services and infrastructure, the village of Šmarje represents an important social rural development center that should be maintained also in the future, with its rural lifestyle including traditional architecture, services, farming, natural and cultural heritage, and finally human resources. On the other hand, the village of Padna is facing similar challenges, but in comparison to Šmarje is more focused on tourism – it already has an operating tourist info center that offers electric bike rental. Like Šmarje, Padna was also part of the smart village initiative and has had links with the EUSALP (EU Strategy for the Alpine Region) and LAG „Istra“.

Due to the exodus in the middle of the 20th century, the population of the area weakened, following a massive farmland abandonment. Only in the last 25 years, the rural lifestyle seems to become attractive again, hence young families decide to remain in the rural area or even immigrate to this area. Unfortunately, a large part of traditional local heritage has been lost. Therefore, the only way to preserve the traditional elements is to create conditions to keep young people in the land through a good combination of traditional elements and a new modern lifestyle, which follows the principles of sustainable development.

However, the region faces several challenges: lack of sustainable mobility services, especially for the older groups due to lack of public transport service and a relatively weak involvement of the local population in green and sustainable shared activities, such as circular economy.

It is expected that by ensuring targeted novel solutions and services aimed to primarily improve connectivity, accessibility and attractiveness of the area via holistic and above all-inclusive approach, based on the participatory, bottom-up approach, will result in creation of new public places, shared activities in recreational areas, as well as in creation of new jobs (e.g. sustainable tourism and farming).

The pilot aims to engage the main local stakeholders to work on ICT tools for the purposes of development of the mobility application for intergenerational use and agri-environmental and consulting services to support local investments in rural areas. Participatory open innovation approach will result in generating additional revenue for raising the local quality of life with regard to the most vulnerable groups of people

Figure 10 - Pictures of Šmarje-Padna landscape

(a) Padna village with Šmarje in the background; (b) View of Padna village

3.5.3 Organizations Involved

Pilot Orchestrator

University of Ljubljana (UL) is a public higher education and research institution, founded in 1919. It has more than 38,000 students and employs more than 6,000 university teachers, researchers, assistant professors and professional and administrative staff at 23 faculties and three arts academies. The University of Ljubljana is renowned for its high-quality social sciences, natural sciences, humanities and technical study programmes, which are prepared in accordance with the Bologna guidelines. Declaration. University researchers and research groups are engaged in scientific research and their research and scholarly activities are characterized by cutting-edge projects in the arts, sciences and technology at home and abroad around the world.

Laboratory for Telecommunications of the University of Ljubljana has immense expertise in professional education at the ICT, CISCO network solutions, Apple products and mobile application development on platforms Android and iOS. They deliver off-the-shelf training, customized programs and ICT skills harmonization projects within organizations, groups and other stakeholders. They also run the CISCO Networking Academy and operate as an Apple Regional Training Centre. In addition, they are experts in multimedia learning and knowledge management for organizations through the E-CHO+ platform, where e-content production, testing users and employees, management through e-learning and video multimedia products. A significant part of the group is involved in research and development of concepts and new digital products and services for rural development. In this manner, alongside with a broad experience in working in rural areas, Laboratory for Telecommunications of the University of Ljubljana will be able to orchestrate support in further pilot development.

Community Activator

Središče Rotunda, Koper, so.p. (ROTUNDA) is a non-governmental, non-profit, non-political organization, offering various activities in the field of non-formal education and active citizenship for 20 years. It also has a status of social enterprise. From the very beginning the organization has been working as a promoter in the field of lifelong learning, information and counseling. Its main activities are: (i) promoting creativity, innovation, entrepreneurship among youth, and encouraging the empowerment and participation of youth in the processes and decisions that affect their lives; (ii) activities as the leading partner of two Local Action Group (LAG Zelena Istra, FLAG Feral), a public-private partnership funded from three EU funds (the two partnerships currently have 150 members,

of which 54 are organizations that are predominantly sustainable organizations); (iii) strengthening the role of NGO's and Social enterprises within the region with numerous activities. Conducting professional meetings and presentations of various industries, as well as organizing various events, offering technical and software support and connecting with the Gymnasium Koper and University of Primorska.

Rotunda is specialized in quality and practical skills courses, research and lectures which are suited for youth and the general population.

3.5.4 Motivations and Key Expected Outcomes

Context

Changes in social structure within the pilot due to exodus in the middle of the 20th century. Following a massive farmland abandonment, the population of the area weakened. Only in the last 25 years, the rural lifestyle has become attractive again, hence young families decide to remain in the rural area. On the other hand, the communities are experiencing processes of immigration to communities' neighbouring areas. All of these processes present various challenges, in particular the need to renew existing community's services which are not meeting the demands of the growing population and at the same time, missing the needs of the elderly. As research shows that digitalization can help rural areas to overcome such challenges in rural areas (Stojanova et al., 2022), both pilot's communities have started collaborating with different initiatives connected with digitalization, for example in a project of Smart Villages.

Current situation

According to the data of the Sustainable Urban Strategy of the City of Koper 2030 (2020), the infrastructure in the area is satisfactory and the situation in the countryside has noticeably improved in recent years. However, the countryside (compared to the coastal part) is still disadvantaged, especially in terms of public transport, communal facilities (wastewater management), services for the population (health, social care, education, etc.). Currently, the pilot is focusing on sustainable public transport, which would be tailored for different age groups, alongside with their specific characteristics. However, the developed solution, which will follow three levels of the so-called SIP (smart innovation package), i.e. technological, non-technological and provision of business models, accompanied with policies, will take into account distinctive socioeconomic and demographic data characteristics of both pilots. Both communities have expressed the need to connect the smart dimension of mobility to rural (sustainable) tourism and circular economy and sustainable lifestyles. Both communities have experience in connecting different levels of the SIP, for instance, during COVID-19, Šmarje, together with University of Ljubljana, developed a business model of virtual rural tourism within the rural digital innovation hub, Divina wine hub (Cvar et al., 2024). On the other hand, Padna is focused on cycling tourism and has established electric bike rental.

Limits to overcome

Even though both pilot's communities have experience in cooperating with different European projects, more involvement of the local population in green and sustainable shared activities, such as the circular economy, environmental education, sustainable, and smart transport. For this to achieve, UL and Rotunda will work on creating trust of the local population, by introducing qualitative methods, in particular, SEROI+, which, due to its open innovation principle, encourages co-creation and underscores the sentiment of the population that its voice matters. Due to a gap between the level of municipalities and some of the stakeholders, regarding their cooperation, UL and Rotunda will actively work on connecting sectors of transport, agriculture and circular economy, tourism,

together with sustainable lifestyles. In terms of knowledge on already existing good practices (digital solutions, business and policy models), the partnership between UL and Rotunda will aspire to present what works via workshops presentations. Last but not least, the pilot will need to overcome the limits of non-uniform data sets, aspiring to create an innovative community-based data approach to rural digital ecosystems (Trilar et al., 2023). Following the analysis, conducted via Territorial digital assessment tool (representatives of both communities, Andrej Medved and Denis Goja conducted the survey), both pilot’s communities could do better in dimensions of “open data” (see **Annexes E1 and E2**).

Future desired scenario(s)

The pilot aims to engage the main local stakeholders to work and cooperate on ICT tools for the purposes of development of the mobility application for intergenerational use and agri-environmental and consulting services to support local investments in rural areas. The lack of active cooperation between local stakeholders can be characterised as one of the main inhibiting factors of sustainable rural development (Mevlja & Podmenik, 2021), so it is expected and above all, desired, that this will enable increase in trust between local stakeholders, new job opportunities and generate additional revenue for raising the local quality of life with regard to the most vulnerable groups of people.

Value proposition and expected impacts

The value proposition of the pilot relies in the development of a sustainable and functioning service, which will be co-created in intense collaboration with the local population, and which will trigger:

- **Enhanced Connectivity** (a) Reduced Isolation: Improved transportation options reduce the isolation of rural communities, connecting both communities better to urban centers (elderly and teenagers), healthcare, education (in particular children to extra school curriculum activities), and employment opportunities b) Interconnected Networks: Integration of various transportation modes (buses, ride-sharing, cycling, etc.) into a seamless network;
- **Increased Efficiency and Reliability** (a) Optimized Routes: Use of real-time data to optimize routes and schedules, minimizing wait times and maximizing coverage; b) Predictive Maintenance: IoT and data analytics can predict vehicle maintenance needs, reducing downtime and improving reliability.
- **Cost-Effectiveness** (Shared Resources: Ride-sharing and carpooling reduce individual costs and overall demand for private vehicles.
- **Environmental Sustainability** (a) Reduced Emissions: e.g. optimizing routes to reduce fuel consumption; b) Promotion of Green Transport: Encouraging cycling and walking through better infrastructure and integration with other modes of transport.
- **Improved Quality of Life** (a) Accessibility: Better transportation access to essential services like healthcare, education, and shopping, improving the overall quality of life for rural residents. b) Inclusive mobility: Ensuring transportation options are accessible to all, including the elderly and disabled.
- **Economic Development** (a) Job Creation: Direct and indirect job creation through the development, maintenance, and operation of the platform. b) Local Business Support: Improved transport can boost local businesses by increasing foot traffic and accessibility and manage tourism, especially within the Šmarje community;

In regard to expected impacts, the pilot’s results are expected to produce the following network of impacts:

- **Social impact** (a) Community Integration: Stronger connections within and between communities, fostering a greater sense of inclusion and social cohesion; b) Health and Safety: Better access to healthcare facilities and reduced accident rates due to safer, more reliable transport options.

- **Economic impact** (Productivity Gains: Reduced travel time and better access to jobs and markets can boost productivity and economic activity.
- **Environmental impact** (a) Lower Carbon Footprint: Reduced reliance on personal vehicles and increased use of shared and public transport options lead to lower emissions b) Sustainable Practices: Encouragement of more sustainable living practices through accessible green transportation options via circular mobility, promoting environment education (results of the questionnaire on the status of environmental education, Annexes 5).
- **Technological impact** (a) Innovation and data utilization: Encourages the adoption of new technologies and better utilization of data to enhance service delivery; b) infrastructure development: e.g. digital networks
- **Policy and governance impact**, resulting in stipulation of policy instruments and facilitating public-private Partnerships to encourage collaboration between public entities and private companies, leading to innovative and effective solutions.

3.5.5 Socioeconomic and Demographic Data

Territory and population

Šmarje, is an important village in the Municipality of Koper in the Littoral region of Slovenian Istria. The village area covers the surface of approximately **7 km²**. It is situated right in between the coastal urbanised cities and the rural area of Slovenian Istria. All data are official statistics from 2023, obtained from the Statistical Office of Slovenia (<https://pxweb.stat.si/SiStat/en>).

Population size is **915 inhabitants** with population density of **283 hab/km²**. The average population age is **44,5 years**, with the distribution as follows:

- [0-15]: 16,5%
- [15-65]: 61,5%
- [>64]: 22%

The gender distribution is balanced, with 49,18% females and 50,82% males.

Population on a municipality level (Municipality of Koper) is in slight decline, with the rate of natural population increase being **-2,2**.

Village Padna is located in the rural area of Coastal Region of Slovenia in the Municipality of Piran and is situated on the end of the ridge, with steep slopes of terraces. The village area covers the surface of **2,91 km²** and has a population of **188 residents**. Population density is **64,8 hab/km²** and the average population age is **47**, with the following distribution:

- [0-15]: 8,5%
- [15-65]: 64,4%
- [>64]: 27,1%

In Padna, the gender distribution is very balanced, with 50% females and 50% males. The rate of natural population increase on a municipality level (Municipality of Piran) is **-6,9** indicating that population is in decline.

Economy data

On the pilot level there is no available data for economy, however, it is possible to get data on a municipality or regional level. GDP on the regional level (Coastal-karst statistical region) was **26.074 €/inhabitant** in 2022 (SURS, 2022). Within the two municipalities, there were 6.893 registered

companies in total in the municipality of Koper and 2.670 in the municipality of Piran. Across the region, there were 3.468 registered companies in the agricultural sector (farms).

Pilot specific: Mobility and Tourism

The data from the City of Koper's Sustainable Urban Strategy 2030 (2020) indicates that the area's infrastructure is adequate and that things have significantly improved in the countryside recently. However, rural areas still have disadvantages over the coastal area, particularly when it comes to public transportation, communal facilities (like wastewater management), and public services (including health, social care, and education). Pilot Šmarje-Padna is focusing on sustainable public transportation and development of mobility solution that would be customized for various age groups based on their unique needs.

Data on mobility in the pilot region is rather scattered. Within the scope of activities conducted in the pilot region, a survey on environmental education was disseminated, addressing, among others, availability and usage of public transportation. Results showed that the majority of inhabitants do not use public transportation at all, with very small percentages stating they use it rarely or that they use it regularly. Participants emphasized the need for an alternative service that functions on demand, rather than based on timetables, which currently fail to address people's needs, resulting in very low usage of existing transportation services.

For village Padna it was possible to obtain data on the number of vehicles passing through Municipality of Piran, at the entrance to the village Padna. The data was captured by the MHP50 preventive radar board. The analysis made for the period from 05.05.2024, 00:00 to 03.06.2024, 23:59 registered 40.672 measurements and recorded 14.306 transports (data obtained from the Municipality of Piran).

In the pilot area of Padna, it was also possible to obtain data from the Tourist information center of Padna regarding the rental of e-bikes (6 e-bikes are available for renting). Regarding tourism data, community activators were able to obtain data on numbers of visitors from cruise ships for the pilot village Padna. In total, over the year 2023, 60 ships arrived in Padna, accounting for 5.760 visitors (source: Tourist agency AtlasExpress Portorož, 2023).

For the pilot region Šmarje, the situation is similar, mobility, tourism and other specific data is scattered and difficult to obtain, therefore, a lot of data for this village is still missing. As stated in the action plan, pilots are working towards establishing a closer relationship and cooperation with both municipality representatives and research institutions, which will enable further access to data, especially pilot specific.

Socio-Economic and demographic data table (statistic data) can otherwise be found in **Annexes E**.

3.5.6 Data Available

Pilot P5 Šmarje-Padna will primarily focus on the topic of smart mobility. Other related topics will also be addressed such as circular economy, rural tourism and environmental education. Apart from the Statistical office's open data, following sources have been identified as relevant for the further data collecting and development of pilot activities:

- **Tourist board Portorož** - Data (data collection starting from 2017) on tourist arrivals in accommodation in the village Padna where three accommodation providers are operating with a total of around 40 beds.
- **Arriva Slovenija LLC** (transport company operating public transportation in the region) – Timetables of public transport: buses departing from/arriving to Šmarje and Padna.

- **Municipality of Koper and Municipality of Piran** – Available data on cycling routes in both municipalities (possibility to obtain data specific to pilot areas) + other relevant data related to mobility, circularity and tourism.
- **Smart Agro Grape digital platform for winegrowers** (developed within the scope of Smart Agro Grape national project, where UL was a lead partner) – environmental data collected from vineyards in the region through sensor infrastructure. Data can be used as an insight into the Šmarje’s agriculture area of a particular winemaker.

Table with available data sets can be found **Annexes E**.

3.5.7 Cross-Collaboration(s)

In the frame of SMART ERA, the pilot will benefit, and its activities will be further enhanced by the collaboration with other projects and initiatives, in particular due to University of Ljubljana’s active role in numerous European projects:

SMARTCOMMUNITY¹⁶ (Interreg Alpine Space): Due to a central focus of one project’s dimension on policy, the project is relevant in terms of connecting it to the aspect of policy makers (EUSALP); the other aspect is the learning potential from the good practices from the project’s pilot. The project aspires to fully embrace the benefits of digitalization and smart transition in order to create a functional, transnational community in the Alps, within the EUSALP AG5 Smart Alps network. UL is the project’s LP.

CODECS¹⁷ (maximising the CO-benefits of agricultural Digitalisation through conducive digital ECoSystems, Horizon) is focused on “sustainable digitalisation” with the goal of improving the collective capacity to understand, assess and foresee the full range of benefits and costs of farm digitalisation, and to build digital ecosystems that maximize the net benefits of digitalisation. Relevance for the SMART ERA project is to be specifically found in the good practice of the living lab approach and the underlining importance of the qualitative methods.

Digital Rural¹⁸ (Interreg): This project aims to improve policies for Smart Villages and rural digital transformation, with UL acting as a project’s policy advisor. Being the policy advisor in the project which will focus on improving policy instruments, following a parallel double learning process: on one hand, bottom-up approach to define the digital policy assessments; and on the other hand, a top-down approach to implement those innovative policies learned in the interregional exchange. In this manner, the relevance is having the opportunity to get an insight into how to make investments more effective in order to accelerate the implementation of the Smart Village concept, and decrease the digital gap with urban areas.

CODIL¹⁹ (Interreg): UL is acting as the project’s LP. The project aims to improve regional innovation policy instruments to better support the emerging distributed-team innovation model. A synergy between the both projects can be found in particular two aspects, i.e. policy dimension and the importance of supporting adequate innovation models with appropriate digital skills.

On the national level, the project **Smart Agro Grape**²⁰ needs to be mentioned. Also run by the UL, the has developed a digital platform for wine growers to implement common environmental approaches to reduce the environmental impact of agriculture, offering a network of nearby

¹⁶ <https://www.alpine-space.eu/project/smartcommunity/>

¹⁷ <https://www.horizoncodecs.eu/>

¹⁸ <https://www.interregeurope.eu/digital-rural>

¹⁹ <https://www.interregeurope.eu/codil>

²⁰ <https://smartagrogrape.si/>

winemakers. The project’s technical solution was nominated for best innovative solution, so-called UL’s rector award and is an overall example of how to introduce digital solutions to rural areas.

Rotunda, the project’s community activator, has listed two projects for potential cross-collaboration: **Revitas**, which was focused on stopping the degradation of the Istrian countryside by protecting the cultural heritage and promoting integrated development and tourism products and creating a cross-border tourist destination and promoting the sustainable development of tourism in the Istrian countryside. The project established a network of info centers, joint cross-border education and cultural exchanges, which ensured the additional development of human resources in the cross-border area and the exchange of experience on the development potential of Slovenian and Croatian Istria. The project will enable the flow of tourists from urban areas to the countryside (with the help of the info center in Padna). With an integrated tourist offer, the tourist season will be extended, which will be reflected in cross-border economic activity, a very important part of which is tourism. Whereas the second project, listed by Rotunda, is **HERA - Sustainable Management of Adriatic Heritage Tourism** (IPA ADRIATIC), deals with some of the main challenges in the field of culture and tourism, having direct link to the SMART ERA project.

This pilot is underlining two other stakeholders: **Urban city centers: Center Uporabnih Predmetov – CUP** due to its framework on the circular economy, highlighting the importance and role of environmental education and, in particular, intrinsic motivation. The other stakeholder is **Municipality of Bale** (CRO) due to the pilot’s cross-border status. Municipality of Bale is renowned for its entrepreneurial experiment, Mon Perin. Mon Perin is a trade association and a company of the same name, founded in autumn 2005 by the citizens of Bale, the municipality and the “friends of Bale”, which includes Croatian citizens who do not live in Bale, but were willing to invest capital in the project. The municipality and the local population have retained a majority in the ownership structure with profits being invested in the community, ensuring a balanced development of the municipality. This is a practice, interesting due to unique community engagement and management of development strategy.

3.5.8 Regulatory Framework

P5’s activities are taking place at four main levels: 1. Local (both communities); 2. The level of municipalities (in Slovenia there are 212 municipalities, their activities are defined by the Law on Municipalities); 3. National and 4. International (mainly, focusing on the EU).

Municipal strategies

- **Local Development Strategy (LDS) LAG Zelena Istra (Green Istria) 2021-2027** is regarded as a key component, with its focus on (social) innovation, which is perceived as indispensable in solving social and environmental challenges. LDS’s focus is otherwise on sustainable tourism, agriculture and local provision, cultural heritage, environmental protection, social and educational sectors and the development of smart villages. The strategy follows the intention for a green transition and achieving carbon neutrality by 2050, in accordance with the European Green Deal and links itself with national and regional strategies, and follows the objectives of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union. It is also coordinated with the *Long-term vision for EU rural areas*, *Slovenian Development Strategy 2030* and the *Regional Development Program of the Coastal-Karst Region for the period 2021–2027*. LDS is supported by funds from the *European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)* and the *European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD)*.
- **City of Koper’s Sustainable Urban Strategy 2030** is an integrated sustainability strategy, consisting of development programmes and policies, focusing on the urban area. Via this policy instrument, the municipality pursues the objective of improving the quality of urban

space and life in the city, and enhancing culture and identity. The Koper 2030 Sustainable Urban Strategy is also the strategic basis for the implementation of the European Union's urban policy for the period 2021-2027, as implemented in local urban communities.

National strategies

- **Slovenian Agricultural policy strategic plan 2023-2027** knowledge transfer and investment in extension services are essential to promote the sustainable development of agriculture and forestry for the integration of new technologies and production practices. It also aims to maintain viable rural areas and rural economies by promoting employment in agriculture, the agri-food sector and other related sectors. A strong emphasis is on creating a supportive environment for young farmers and enabling sustainable business development in rural areas:
- **Digital Inclusion act:** The act aspires to reduce the digital divide and increase digital inclusion for all citizens.
- **Slovenian smart specialization strategy (S5)** is focusing on the green transition, which is understood as "an innovative, low-carbon, digital and knowledge-based transformation of the economy and society". This gives smart specialisation a sustainable character and is promoted under the acronym S5.

International strategies

- **European Cohesion policy:** Slovenia is divided into two cohesion regions, with Cohesion Region West Slovenia (CRWSS) classified as a developed region and Cohesion Region East Slovenia (CRES) as a less developed region, which results in different levels of co-financing from the European Union.
- **EUSALP:** EUSALP co-creates the future of Europe by translating sectoral policies on a regional scale, enabling the best ideas to happen in a sensitive natural and multicultural Alpine area. By balancing innovative solutions in a healthy environment, EUSALP is shaping the future together. Slovenia holds the Presidency of the EUSALP from January 2024 until December 2024. During its term, the Slovenian Presidency will focus on 3 thematic priorities: circular economy, quality of life for young people in the Alps, water-smart society.
- **EUSAIR:** The EU Strategy for the Adriatic-Ionian Region (EUSAIR), which addresses the common challenges of the region and strengthens stakeholder cooperation for economic, social and territorial cohesion. The EUSAIR strategy is based on four thematic pillars: blue growth, connecting the region (transport and energy connectivity), environmental quality and sustainable tourism. In addition to these, it includes two cross-cutting areas: 1. Research, innovation and SMEs; 2. Capacity building, including communication.

3.6 PILOT 6: DEVETAKI PLATEAU

3.6.1 Short Pilot Overview

PRESENTATION

- **Location:** Situated in northern Bulgaria.
- **Geography:** Karst plateau with numerous caves, rock formations, and waterfalls.
- **Climate:** Temperate continental climate with hot summers and cold winters.
- **Tourism and Activities:** Famous for its caves, such as the Devetashka Cave, and natural landmarks. Activities include caving, hiking, and wildlife observation.
- **Economy:** Largely rural with agriculture, small-scale farming, and eco-tourism as main economic activities.
- **Culture:** Rich in folklore, traditional crafts, and historical sites, reflecting Bulgaria's diverse cultural heritage.

CHALLENGES ADDRESSED

- Decreased quality of life in the area
- Demographic collapse
- Lack of access to adequate healthcare and education services
- Fewer economic opportunities

TARGET SECTORS	KEY TARGET GROUPS	KEY OBJECTIVE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Healthcare ▪ Waste management ▪ Tourism ▪ Public services ▪ Citizen participation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Local communities (especially elderly people and young families) ▪ Farmers ▪ small businesses ▪ Tourists and visitors ▪ Public administrations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Encourage and motivate young people to live in the villages ▪ Improve the quality of life in rural areas, and in particular improve access to health services ▪ Improve the conditions for entrepreneurship and business development ▪ Promote sustainable tourism development

3.6.2 Pilot Summary

The Devetaki Plateau is situated in the middle of Northern Bulgaria. Its territory is included in the Natura 2000 National Ecological Network. The cultural and historical heritage is also an invaluable asset - local folklore, local cuisine and rituals, vernacular architecture. Residents, however, are disadvantaged in terms of information and participation due to their remoteness from municipal centres and towns. They have no link to the city councils and no influence on decision making.

According to statistics, the majority of residents in the region are over 65-year-old retirees. Greater efforts in terms of engagement, and communication are required. Another smaller segment of the community has lately emerged: younger families (30-50 years old) who have opted to take advantage of the region's potential and launch their own small businesses, primarily in tourism and agriculture. In order to further develop the region's potential and make it attractive both for and visitors of different ages, some steps are necessary to make their voices heard in decision making.

Figure 11 - Pictures of Devetaki Plateau

(a) The Devetaki Cave, one of the “diamonds” in the Devetaki Plateau crown; (b) The Old Mill, recently renovated by DPA as an Information and Training Centre; (c) “The Stairs” cave, a treasure, newly discovered to the world; (d) “Jazz Under The Stars of The Devetaki Plateau” - a unique fest of music and nature organised for ten years now by DPA on a meadow between two villages

3.6.3 Organizations Involved

Pilot Orchestrator

Devetaki Plateau Association (DPA) is a Bulgarian non-for-profit legal entity, established in 2008 to stimulate the development, improve the quality of life and promote the region of Devetaki Plateau. The organization unites the people living in nine villages on the Devetaki Plateau: Agatovo, Brestovo,

Devetaki, Gorsko Slivovo, Kakrina, Kramolin, Krushuna, Karpachevo, Tepava. The main activities of Devetaki Plateau Association are aimed at preservation and development of the regional resources, increasing the capacity of local people to manage natural assets and make the Plateau an attractive place for tourism, outdoor recreation and learning. We already have 140 members from various backgrounds and occupations – farmers, cultural figures, young people, local authorities, retired people, NGOs and businesses, united and motivated to work for the sustainable development of the region. Municipalities of Sevlievo, Letnitsa and Lovech are partners of the Association, supporting our projects and initiatives.

Community Activator

Sevlievo Municipality, situated in Bulgaria, is the local governing body overseeing the Sevlievo municipality. They provide public service, regulatory authority, and resource allocation while actively engaging with residents and stakeholders. With expertise in local governance, infrastructure development, and community planning, they aim to collaborate in the pilot program to address community challenges and enhance residents' well-being.

3.6.4 Motivations and Key Expected Outcomes

Context

The Devetaki Plateau is situated in the middle of Northern Bulgaria and has a population of 4.000 inhabitants. The region covers 9 villages which are situated in 3 different municipalities. Although close to each other, they had not worked together until the establishment of the Devetaki Plateau Association. The territory is included in the Natura 2000 National Ecological Network and it has a great potential in terms of natural resources and biodiversity. The cultural and historical heritage is also an invaluable asset - local folklore, local cuisine and rituals, and vernacular architecture.

Current situation

Residents, however, are disadvantaged in terms of services due to their remoteness from municipal centres and towns. Young people have left searching for jobs and educational, health and cultural services. Schools, kindergartens and any kind of activity addressed to children and pupils are rare and unrewarding. The situation is similar with health services. The nearest hospital is at least 1 hour away which can be fatal in certain cases. According to statistics, the majority of residents in the region are over 65-year-old retirees.

At the same time, another smaller segment of the community has lately emerged: young families (30-50 years old) who have opted to take advantage of the region's potential and launch their own small businesses, primarily in tourism and agriculture. They are willing to invest in the region's development; however, they need to have better access to services like education, out-of-school activities and health care in order to stay in the area and also attract other people of their age.

Limits to overcome

The Future Search Conference organized at local level in the frame of the SMART ERA project, provoked a deep analysis of the limitations and challenges the local community faces. They are rather objective and they concern all or most rural areas in Bulgaria, but some of them can also be addressed smartly at the local level.

- **The unstable political situation in Bulgaria** (the country has gone through 6 rounds of national elections over the last 3 years) leads to delays in EU - funding programs and to some serious obstacles to intermunicipal (regional) cooperation.

- **The poor infrastructure** (roads, water supply) due to the lack of structured and visible national policy for the development of rural areas is a challenge for the local inhabitants but also a limitation for tourism development.
- **There is no strategy for sustainable development, especially, for smart waste management** at municipal or at regional level. The region needs measures to be taken for protecting the environment to the benefit of the local community, of the tourists, and of the future generations.
- **There is no working strategy and no European or national funding** for small rural tourism businesses, leading to a low rate of investments in the region.
- **The health, educational and cultural services are not accessible** due to the remoteness of the villages from the municipal centres and big towns.
- **There are not enough cultural and other social events** - for the elderly, for the children and for the young people which is one of the reasons for the continuous negative demographic trend.
- **The region still lacks modern approaches for the development of smart tourism:** no data on tourist flow, characteristics, length of stay, and financial revenues from tourism. There are still no local integrated tourist products and local tourist guides (including digital ones) to put the region firmly on the tourist map of Bulgaria and Europe.

Future desired scenario(s)

After consulting representatives of local stakeholder groups, in order to improve the overall quality of life in the villages in the Devetaki Plateau, the objectives they formulated are in the following directions:

- Improve access to health services in the region
- Sustainable development of the rural area with a special focus on waste management
- Encourage and motivate young people to live in the villages by offering a broader scope of cultural and educational services
- Foster community - lead rural tourism development

Value proposition and expected impacts

Throughout the project one or two SIPs for Devetaki Plateau will be co-developed and implemented. The expected impacts for P6 are:

Improved access to health services in the region through the use of telemedicine. Using the advantages of modern technology and stepping on successful practices in other countries, the access to health services would improve in a way that they can get medical advice and basic care faster and with no need to travel. This has been pointed out as a major need at the Future Search Conference held to discuss needs and expectations of the local community. By developing a SIP addressing this objective, the expected impact would be mainly on the local people, a big part of them aged 65+. In addition, young people, and especially, families with kids will also benefit from the SIP. General practitioners in the nearing towns will feel the effect of it, too, by increasing their capacity in technology application and use, and by decreasing their workload in the hospitals and health centres. Last but not least, implementing the SIP will increase the popularity of the region by promoting it as one of the first places in Bulgaria applying telemedicine.

Provide a smart system for separate waste management. This is an issue of public significance with a potential impact on the community, the environment, and the tourism development. A broader impact can be seen in contributing to the global measures fighting climate change. The social dimension of the SIP would be in changing the mentality of local people by informing and training them on the environmental footprints threads and on their role in combating pollution. Information and training campaigns will be held to tackle those issues. The environmental aspect of this SIP is undisputable. A good point would be the possibility of disseminating the SIP in all the other villages

of the three municipalities, which will multiply the impact substantially. The impact on tourism development is also significant: the SIP will help modernizing and separating waste collection which will make the villages even more attractive as a natural and cultural destination. In the case of selecting this issue to co-create and implement a SIP, it will include technological and analogue elements. It will be an excellent example of co-creation since it will require the active participation of citizens, local authorities, environmental specialists, and businesses.

Foster community - lead rural tourism development. This is a segment that DPA has been working on continuously for years and has also come from the consultations with the local stakeholders as a logical recommendation. A SIP in this direction shall include a technological solution: data collection, organisation and analysis. The data will be taken from the three municipalities, from the local tourism businesses, and from the tourists. The SIP will support all the stakeholders in the development and the provision of tourist services and infrastructure to improve their performance. In the long run, the SIP will foster the development and the promotion of the Devetaki Plateau as a smart tourist destination.

Encourage and motivate young people to live in the villages by offering a broader scope of cultural and educational services. This sector is by no means less significant as it would impact the young generation in a region with a rather negative demographic status. They are still a small segment in the population of the 9 villages, however, the focus in the future shall be put on them. It will include technological and conventional elements. Establishing cooperatives for education and animation of the kids outside the kindergartens and schools is a possible element of the solution and the SIP. Online tools and gamification can be a part of the technological proposal.

3.6.5 Socioeconomic and Demographic Data

Territory and population

The total Devetaki plateau area is **330,345 km²**. The population size of the Devetaki Plateau is **1.936 inhabitants** with a population density of **5,86 inhab/km²**.

The gender distribution is almost equivalent with **47% males and 53% females**. Women live longer than men.

The data of the last count - down held in 2021 by the National Institute of Statistics, shows the following age distribution:

- [0-19]: 12%
- [20-34]: 13%
- [35-64]: 30%
- [+65]: 45%

As seen in the above chart, 45% of the whole population is 65+ years of age. The number of people in active age is 611 or 30%, young people (20 - 34 years) are 13 %, and children up to 19 years are 12%. There is no trusted data on average age.

The number of companies registered in the nine villages is 95 according to the National Registry Agency. There is no official public data on the sectors they operate but most of them are in agriculture, farming and tourism.

In general, it shall be mentioned that there is a lack of data available, and there are almost no disaggregated data at regional/local level.

3.6.6 Data Available

The lack of data available at local and regional level is a reality and a concern for P6. However, several open databases and sources for statistical data that are available at national level. Here are listed the most relevant ones:

- **National Statistical Institute²¹ (NSI)** of Bulgaria: The NSI is the primary source for official statistics in Bulgaria. It provides data on demographics, economy, education, health, environment, and more.
- **Open Data Portal of Bulgaria²²**: This portal offers access to a wide range of datasets from various government ministries and agencies. The data covers multiple sectors including agriculture, education, environment, health, and transport.
- **Bulgarian National Bank²³ (BNB)**: The BNB provides statistical data related to finance and economics, including information on monetary policy, banking, and financial markets.
- **Eurostat**: As a member of the European Union, Bulgaria contributes to and utilizes Eurostat, which provides comprehensive statistical data for all EU member states.
- **Trade Register and Register of Non-Profit Legal Entities**: Managed by the Registry Agency, this database provides information on businesses and non-profit organizations in Bulgaria.

3.6.7 Cross-Collaboration(s)

DPA has been working continuously for the sustainable economic, environmental and social development of the nine villages in the region for over 15 years now. All the association's projects have been directed towards improving the social and economic well-being of the local community and the development of tourism in the Devetaki Plateau. This has been done with the active participation of the local people and the stable support of the three municipalities.

2023-1-BG01-KA220-VET-000157210, Interpretation INHERIT, comes for "Heritage Interpretation through Digital Storytelling for Experiential Tourism Development in Rural Areas". The major objective of this ERASMUS+ project is to enhance the skills and the compatibility of tourist destinations, of the local entrepreneurs and organizations in the tourism sphere. The project is implemented by DPA together with its long-term partners, the Village of Kato Drys (Cyprus), the Lisov Museum (Slovakia), Tetra Solutions (Bulgaria) and Natural Walks (Spain). Within the project the partners work on the development of a training course - “Experiential Tourism” and they will train trainers and local tourism service providers in the 4 countries. In addition, each of the partners will elaborate local tracks and attractions which will be digitalized and incorporated in a Digital portfolio of heritage interpretation stories, heritage trails and thematic quests. DPA is the project coordinator and is responsible for the wholesome project implementation and the achievement of results.

RURAL BUSINESS ACADEMY is another project of Devetaki Plateau Association, supported financially by America for Bulgaria Foundation (2020 - 2024). The Project supports the rural businesses and foster the economic development of local communities in the Devetaki Plateau and other rural areas in Bulgaria. Activities included the renovation of an old mill in the region and turning it into a cultural, information and training center. DPA developed a curriculum and delivered training courses to increase the capacity of small and starting businesses in Bulgarian villages, followed by elaboration of business plans and development of new services to guests and tourist in the area. Co-creation and community involvement have been a horizontal characteristic of the whole project

²¹ <https://www.nsi.bg/en>

²² <https://www.opendata.government.bg>

²³ <https://bnb.bg/>

implementation, including meetings in the villages to discuss priorities and project ideas which have later been implemented by DPA, the municipalities and local volunteers.

Academy for Democratic Communities (ACADEMO) EUV/89 (2023 - 2025). The initiative is implemented within a regranting project of Open Society Institute - Sofia funded under the Citizens, Equality, Rights and Values Programme (CERV) of the EU. The DPA is transferring its experience and rural development approaches in 10 rural areas all around Bulgaria. Activities include training, community building and activating, public discussions on finding priorities and solutions for the development of the different villages and rural areas.

3.6.8 Regulatory Framework

The regulatory framework that governs the activities of the Municipality of Sevlievo as well as the other municipalities is the **Bulgarian Local Government and local administration Act**²⁴ and some other acts and regulations that provide for various aspects of local governance. The municipality is responsible for public services such as education, healthcare, social care, infrastructure, and environmental protection, waste management policy included. It also implements national policies and strategies in these areas. The Municipal Council, composed of elected members, makes decisions on local regulations and budgets. The municipal administration, led by the mayor, executes the decisions of the Municipal Council and manages the day-to-day operations of the city.

An important framework document that sets regional policy goals and priorities is the **Integrated Development Plan (IDP) for Sevlievo Municipality (2021-2027)**. Its key Elements are:

- **Strategic Alignment.** It aligns with higher-level documents such as:
 - Integrated Territorial Strategy for the North Central Region (NUTS 2)
 - National Spatial Development Concept (2013-2025)
 - National Development Programme "Bulgaria 2030"
 - Municipal Master Plan of Sevlievo (until 2035)
- **Focus Areas.** It prioritizes sustainable development, equal opportunities, and social inclusion, and emphasizes integrated territorial investments and partnerships with neighboring municipalities.
- **Tourism Development.** It includes a municipal tourism development program aligned with regional and national strategies. Despite the absence of a regional strategy for Gabrovo, it incorporates measures to support local tourism activities.
- **Integration with Other Sectors.** The IDP of Sevlievo considers sectoral plans at the municipal level, including environmental infrastructure, health and social services and tourism.

In the Waste Management sector, the Municipality of Sevlievo is a part of the operation of the **Regional Waste Management Program**, that contains the following priorities:

- **Environmental Protection and Human Health:** Aims to prevent or reduce the harmful impact of waste generation and management.
- **Bio-waste Prevention and Utilization:** Focuses on preventing bio-waste generation and promoting separate collection and utilization, tailored to different settlement types.

In summary, the IDP of Sevlievo Municipality (2021-2027) is a comprehensive plan aimed at guiding the region's development in a sustainable, inclusive, and strategic manner, with specific attention to tourism and waste management. As far as SMART ERA is concerned all the four sectors proposed for SIP elaboration and implementation are fully in line with the Municipality strategies and priorities.

²⁴ <https://www.cik.bg/upload/57770/Local+Self-government+and+Local+Administration+Act.pdf>

At national level, Bulgaria is a part of the **EU Rural development program** which can be a source for funding for a part of the elements. Two local action groups (LAG) have been established in the area - **LAG Letnitsa - Lovech**, and **LAG - Sevlievo** with a focus on the development and improvement of the living environment in the villages. However, the new Program period has been delayed for almost 2 years now due to the political situation in Bulgaria, which hinders a lot of potential initiatives in the area.

3.7 PILOTS’ COMPARISON

The comparison of some basic indicators highlights the large differences between the SMART ERA pilots. For instance, in terms of area tackled by the pilots, the range goes from reduced surface of a municipal territory (such as P2 and P5), selected pilot municipalities together, or related sub-regions or other most relevant available regional level (P1, P3 and P6) to a whole and large region (such as P4).

Figure 12 - Surface of the SMART ERA pilots

In terms of population, two realities can be observed: scarcely populated regions from one side (such as P1, P3, P4, and especially P6), and densely populated pilots on the other side (with special mention to P2). It is worth mentioning that the two most dense pilots (P2 and P5) are the ones addressing mobility issues.

Figure 13 - Population and population density of the SMART ERA pilots

The demographic statistics related with age average and age distribution, highlights the ageing problem and loss of young population mentioned by all the pilots. This is particularly concerning in P6 where 45% of the population is above 65 years old.

Figure 14 - Age average and age distribution of the SMART ERA pilots
 (*) for P3, age range is slightly different, with figures corresponding to [0-14], [15-64] and [+65]

The percentage of foreign population of each pilot also reveals clear differences with three pilots largely under the EU-average of foreign nationals (P1, P3 and P4), one pilot within the EU-average (P1), and two pilots clearly above the EU-average (P2 and P5). It should be noted though, that for some of these pilots, local data were not available, and that national/regional data were taken instead (case for P4 and P6).

Figure 15 - Percentage of foreign population in the SMART ERA pilots

The analysis of the economic data, and in particular the GDP per capita, also highlights large differences between pilots. From the six pilots, only two regions (P1 and P3) are above the EU average (32k€/hab).

Figure 16 - GDP per capita of the SMART ERA pilots

4. NEEDS AND GAPS

4.1 INTEREST AND EXPECTATIONS

4.1.1 Pilot 1: Valle di Sole

The priorities identified by the mayors of Valle di Sole involved in the needs and gaps analysis are the following:

- **Identifying and calculating the value of the ecosystem services related to the landscape of Valle di Sole.** A significant challenge is to include the landscape, the value of agriculture and forestry, and the value of protected areas in the development strategy for Valle di Sole.
- **Raising awareness of the local community** in environmental assets and their opportunities and educating young generations. It is crucial to develop educational actions to address the lack of awareness of local communities, especially the generations born in the '70 and '80 and the younger generations.
- **Developing slower tourism**, connected to local dynamics. The tourism sector in Valle di Sole faces several challenges, including high seasonality, significant disparities across different areas (with some villages experiencing over-tourism while others are underdeveloped), and sensitivity to climate change (such as lack of snow and high temperatures affecting winter tourism). A tourism model that prioritises sustainability, that is less focused on skiing, and that integrates more deeply into valley life is needed.
- **Developing the productive potential of the area related to the agri-food sector.** Developing the agri-food sector is crucial for ensuring the long-term sustainability of the territory and the maintenance of local traditions and community values. The agro-food sector could also be a significant contributor to youth employment.
- **Enhancing the health and well-being** of living in a place with these characteristics.

As mentioned in the document developed by the mayors of Valle di Sole that will be part of the working group in SMART ERA, the expected outcomes of activities are the following:

- Improve the management of agricultural and pastoral areas.
- Encourage active participation of local communities in the strategic decisions of relevant authorities, enabling stakeholders to weigh diverse inputs and contribute to the socio-economic balance of the territories from a sustainability perspective.
- Quantify the direct and indirect impacts of conservation, monitoring, research, enhancement, maintenance, and use actions on silvo-agricultural-pastoral areas to improve the overall quality of life.
- Develop a methodology that allows comparison with other projects in different sectors evaluated with economic parameters and market prices.
- Consider environmental costs as investments that yield benefits for both current and future local communities.

In general, the economic evaluation of ecosystem services related to agricultural and forest areas is expected to increase local population awareness of land's role in improving quality of life. This will lead to a better understanding and acceptance of conservation measures and greater responsibility in their present and future management. The expected impact of the research is the enhancement of sustainability in its environmental, social, and economic dimensions, considering the entire territory of Valle di Sole.

4.1.2 Pilot 2: Tramuntana Sóller

Based on the results obtained from the data analysis and from the feedback from local stakeholders, the interests and expectations for P4 in Sóller depend on the sector and issues tackled. These are presented here below.

General interests and expectations

- Foster cooperation among different sectors: agriculture, tourism, mobility and culture: Involve and bring together the different socio-economic actors of the municipality to strengthen or establish new relationships, alliances and synergies between actors and sectors that do not usually share much between them.
- Initiate data-sharing and cross-collaboration between sectors and local actors to investigate and create new, sustainable business models for the Valley of Sóller and to support data-driven decision making.
- Need for public policies and services adapted to the reality of Sóller (control of vacation rentals, classification of urban orchards/gardens, management of the flow of tourists and mobility within the municipality...).

Tourism sector

- Implement an integrated and more automated system/tool for collecting and monitoring tourist data in Sóller (to obtain standardized and disaggregated data).
- Implement training programs or courses for companies and other local actors on data and technologies.
- To be able to understand more precisely how tourists 'consume' the destination of Sóller (what they visit, what they buy, who, when, how...).
- Implement more personalized activities, particularly activities for children (children's activities are the primary demand of tourists since tourism in Sóller is family-oriented). There are two main types of tourists in Sóller: (i) those who spend their entire vacation in the municipality in one of the hotels or vacation rentals; (ii) tourists who only come for the day. Day-trip tourists request locker services to store their bags/backpacks while they enjoy the beach.
- Need to better inform tourists about the reality of the tourist destination of Sóller, in order to influence their behavior and improve coexistence with residents. Therefore, communication and awareness-raising campaigns are still very necessary.

Agricultural sector

- Improve the orchard/garden management and commercialization practices of smallholders and urban garden owners by providing guidance through workshops and courses. Topics covered would include how to maximize yield from the garden, identifying tasks suitable for amateurs versus those best left to professionals, common plant diseases during summer and winter seasons, direct-sales strategies, and more.
- Initiate data-sharing and cross-referencing data sets from farmers engaged in direct sales and sales of organic products with the aim to improve data-based decision making and create new business models. A website with an interactive map can improve the visibility of active local farmers and their available products for residents and tourists.
- Find innovative and legal solutions to facilitate the reception of subsidies and assistance for smallholders and urban garden owners.
- Ensuring better integration of data between supply and demand, with this information accessible in a visual and user-friendly manner through an app or platform. This allows both farmers and the agriculture cooperative of Sóller to better anticipate the demand for local products.

- Addressing the issue of water scarcity, it is crucial to have more data on the availability and usage of water in the municipality. Particularly, there is a need to conduct studies to understand firsthand how much water currently enters Sóller from its various sources. Through sensors, it would be possible to monitor the rate at which different water reserves located in the municipality (such as wells, *s'affareig*, etc.) are being filled.

Mobility sector

- Being able to predict traffic congestion and parking saturation in advance within the municipality. Therefore, a system should be integrated with an app for tourists, allowing them to adjust their travels accordingly to avoid traffic jams and queues (it can also be linked with the currently unused traffic information screen system).
- At the same time, there is a need to provide more information to tourists about the reality of tourism in Sóller/Mallorca, so that they can adjust their behaviour and enjoy their stay without exacerbating the existing overcrowding issues.
- From the authorities and public administrations, there is a need to learn to better manage overcrowding and to have more data and information to efficiently redirect the flow of tourists throughout the territory.

Cultural sector

- Create new products/services and improve tourist distribution throughout the municipality by developing "cultural packages" that include access to the historical train and various museums in Sóller. There is already a successful package combining the train, railway, and a boat trip to *Sa Calobra*, which is very popular among tourists. This cultural package would build on the 'art train' initiative, using the train to transport visitors to various museums and cultural sites in the municipality (Can Prunera, Casal de Cultura, Balearic Museum of Natural Sciences, Botanical Garden, Museum of the Sea, etc.). This package would provide good alternatives for tourists on rainy days and help diversify the tourist offer, making it more comprehensive and sustainable (reducing car traffic within the municipality).
- Augment visitor numbers of less visited places by signing agreements between museums and local schools to organize visits and promote the museums among the local population.
- More than 50% of the local actors indicated during the survey campaign (see **annex B1**) that they would like to have improved leisure and cultural digital services. It is essential to develop a website or an app that integrates and centralizes all tourist, leisure, and cultural offerings for both tourists and residents. This system should provide real-time information to offer personalized recommendations to users (based on their profile, availability, weather, etc.). In addition to socio-cultural offerings, this system could provide information on the condition of the beaches, where to buy local products, and places to visit.

4.1.3 Pilot 3: Northern Ostrobothnia

The Northern Ostrobothnian rural region including pilot areas (municipalities of Alavieska, Kalajoki and Nivala) have need of better home reaching services for tourists, elderly, second home/cottage owners and users, remote and multi-local workers. At the same time, local service providing microenterprises and SMEs need and would benefit from new customers and larger markets. Platform economy-based solutions (e.g. Foodora, Uber and Wolt) have provided significant new markets for food and mobility services in urban areas, but needs for the rural areas are somewhat different for provided services and potentially also for the platform applied.

The rural platform economy pilot of Northern Ostrobothnia will implement a service platform economy solution to enhance rural services and markets for microenterprises and SMEs to enhance availability and quality of rural services and markets of rural small enterprises. The digital market platform will connect better services providers and users. For rural populations and tourists, it is difficult to find local well-being, maintenance and mobility service providers in rural regions due to limited markets and marketing. The approach will support data-driven rural community development in terms of entrepreneurship, rural labour markets and availability of rural services. By boosting rural digital solutions for service entrepreneurship, the aim is to tackle long distances related challenges and also promote co-production of health and well-being services. Targeted service users and customer segments will be related mainly to tourism, second homes and (summer) cottages, housing for the elderly and supported housing as well as remote workers. Smaller service enterprises will be the main emphasized business segment providing services in the platform.

4.1.4 Pilot 4: East Herzegovina

The interest of P4 relies in the promotion of the natural, cultural and gastronomic rural values of East Herzegovina to attract a greater number of tourists into the rural areas of the region. This will result in the creation of new sources of income for the local rural populations. By involving young people in creative activities in East Herzegovina, it will contribute to reducing the trend of leaving the village and the entire region.

In the frame of SMART ERA, P4 will use the SIPs (and in particular digital media) to achieve its goals. Some of the SIPs that could contribute to P4's visions are described hereafter:

- Smart solutions that enhance connectivity, such as high-speed internet access and mobile applications for tourism information and booking, can help rural areas attract more tourists and improve the overall visitor experience.
- Smart solutions that promote sustainable tourism practices, such as waste management systems, energy-efficient infrastructure, and eco-friendly transportation options, to preserve the natural environment and cultural heritage of rural areas.
- Enhanced Visitor Experience in a term of smart technologies that enhance the visitor experience, such as virtual reality tours, augmented reality apps for historical sites, and interactive maps showcasing local attractions, can attract more tourists and encourage longer stays in rural areas.
- Expectations for smart solutions that facilitate the diversification of tourism offerings in rural areas, such as agritourism experiences, outdoor adventure activities, cultural festivals, and culinary tours, to appeal to a broader range of visitors and increase tourism revenue.

The expectation for P4 is that the smart solutions will empower local communities to participate in tourism development and benefit from its economic opportunities, such as online platforms for local artisans to sell their products, community-based tourism initiatives, and crowd-sourced cultural heritage preservation projects.

4.1.5 Pilot 5: Šmarje-Padna

The conducted SEROI+ sessions (held on 22.3.2024 and 25.4.2024), demonstrated the high level of enthusiasm of both communities of the pilot due to a high level of participants (considering the scale of both communities). Expectations in both communities are high - both communities wish for a permanent service that would make their lives easier and for the better. The results of the first session have highlighted the following general interest and expectations:

- Development of a functioning, sustainable rural mobility service, which would be organized as a social enterprise and would be adjusted/customized for both communities; moreover, it would be adjusted to different target groups (elderly, children, teenagers, tourists)
- The developed service would operate by the principle “on the demand”
- Its development would include a very well thought network of stakeholders, i.e. policymakers, municipalities (in Slovenia, local politics and development of services is very much dependent on the level of municipalities), service providers, investment capital also in the form of donations or sponsorship
- The development of this particular service would follow already existing good practices in Slovenia, and will actively work with a network of stakeholders (identified via SEROI+ methodology; See **annex E6**)

As sustainable mobility is central to this pilot, the first SEROI+ session put all the focus on this particular thematic area. Thus, the focus of the second SEROI+ session on 25th April, was to think how to connect other thematic areas into the development of the digital solution of sustainable mobility. Again, 3 groups were formed and the following exceptions/solutions can be identified:

- connecting the service to cycling by arranging adequate infrastructure (infrastructure, maps, QR codes, proper marking of bikes...); connecting it with the stakeholder network of municipalities, local communities, CZP, Laas, identify target groups (in particular tourists and restaurant owners, local farmers: in Padna olive makers and in Šmarje winemakers);
- connecting the service to sustainable (rural) tourism;
- connecting the service to community “open air” events, e.g. “open kitchen”; such community event would be organized several times per year (but not during high tourist season to avoid overcrowding in the context of sustainability, as a reward for volunteers (as a token for them) and presentation of the local farmers
- connecting the service to water monitoring for the purposes of pursuing sustainable boutique style rural tourism, e.g. cycling, but also other activities, restoration of old sources, irrigation intakes and construction of new reservoirs is advised; again a whole ecosystem of stakeholders would be needed: Municipal investments, OPPN and MOPE, together with inclusion of experts to provide the necessary studies; it is expected that these actions would be beneficial for local communities and creation of energy cooperatives (sv. Anton).

4.1.6 Pilot 6: Devetaki Plateau

Facing the different limitations and gaps, the expectations of the local community actors in P6 are grouped as follows:

Improved access to health services in the villages in the region of the Devetaki Plateau. For the last twenty years, specialists in various fields have been investigating the use of telecommunications and computer technologies to improve health care. At the intersection of many of these efforts is telemedicine — a combination of mainstream and innovative information technologies. As defined in the US National Library of Medicine, “Telemedicine is the use of electronic information and communications technologies to provide and support health care when distance separates the participants”.

In the case of the Devetaki Plateau, modern solutions for tele - medicine shall be explored and their financial parameters considered. Local doctors from the surrounding towns can be approached, consulted, and motivated via training in new technologies. They shall also be invited to promote, inform the local community, and raise public awareness on how to use the modern services. The DPA and the Municipality of Sevlievo shall actively communicate the new technological solution to the community in the region and will further disseminate and multiply it in some of the other 48 villages of Sevlievo and Lovech municipality.

Sustainable development of the rural area with a special focus on waste management.

Discussions with the local stakeholders demonstrate their interest in sustainable development of the region and preservation of natural resources. There is an expectation that an innovative system is elaborated in the villages to help introduce separate waste collection, composting and recycling. Some of the initial steps in this direction may include: (i) Study different smart solutions on waste management throughout Europe; (ii) Organise one or more discussions on the possible solutions with representatives of the local community, the 3 municipalities, the local producers that fabricate waste, and the companies that provide separate waste collection and recycling in the nearby towns; (iii) Analyse and systemize the outcomes and recommendations from the discussions and define the elements of a SIP; (iv) Together with the project partners review the results, make a draft of the SIP and see which elements require technological solutions, which are more “analogue”, and which of them necessitate some business models; (v) Discussion with the stakeholders (co-design) on the proposed solutions as elements of one SIP; and (vi) Information and communication campaign as a start of the application of the SIP.

Encourage and motivate young people to live in the villages by offering a broader scope of cultural and educational services. Towards this objective, the DPA and Sevlievo Municipality shall explore possibilities for providing out - of school activities, cultural events, and working with children. Gamification is what can be applied here - various technological solutions linked to the cultural and natural resources of the region. The cultural calendar of the DPA shall be broadened including events in which more local people take part.

Foster community - lead rural tourism development. The expectation in this sphere is to gather, organise and analyse trustful information on various aspects of tourism development:

- From the municipalities and the local businesses: Number and type of accommodation places; Number and type of restaurants and shops; Length of stay; Revenues from tourism in the municipalities and in the business, etc.
- From the tourists and visitors: Number and kinds of tourists and visitors in the region; Places of interest visited; Tourist services/ attractions bought or visited; Evaluation on the quality of services; Advertisement sources the tourists use, etc.

Having this data collected and systemized will help DPA and the three municipalities make prognoses, analysis, hence - improvements and modernization in the development and offering high quality innovative tourist services.

4.2 BARRIERS AND CHALLENGES

4.2.1 Pilot 1: Valle di Sole

Economic barriers and challenges

- Different economic sectors have conflicting interests (economic, social, and environmental) and internal dynamics that may differ considerably. These conflicts may create tensions and hamper the establishment of a trade-off solution accepted by all. For this reason, it is essential to involve different stakeholders in a collaborative and inclusive approach to create a shared vision that goes beyond short-term revenue.
- The change advocated by the pilot involves a systemic approach that is novel for many local stakeholders and public administrators. It requires training and capacity building.

Technological and infrastructural barriers and challenges

- The analysis of the current context has led to the emergence of the scarce use of quantitative data by decision-makers, who usually resort to qualitative data and direct contact with the community and stakeholders to monitor local problems and phenomena. They have recognized, however, that the availability of objective and understandable data about local resources and production would greatly improve their capacity to make strategic decisions. The use of data (provided with user-friendly digital tools) would also enable more effective comparisons with other related territories or competitors.
- More generally, one barrier to the decision-makers envisioning innovative solutions for rural development may be represented by the low awareness of the potential role of technology. To overcome this barrier, initiatives to increase knowledge about technological opportunities are required.

Legal barriers and challenges

- Legal issues were not explicitly mentioned by the mayors, but the relevance of the project action and its legal framework could certainly lead to the highlighting of obstacles and challenges of a general nature. From this point of view, there exist constraints imposed by the legislation regarding:
 - state aid in the case of granting contributions for economic activities (with the criteria that provide exemptions from prior notification to the EU Commission by category, by amount, and in the case of SGEI);
 - public administration contracts and tenders for the identification of suppliers of goods, services or supplies and for consultancy contracts;
 - granting of public goods or services (in particular the jurisprudence of the Court of Justice).
- As regards the challenges to be faced and resolved, the need emerges for the actors involved to implement a "functional" organisational architecture for sound and correct financial administrative management in line with the European Regulation on the subject and with the provisions of the HORIZON manual.

Challenges related to gender

- Challenges related to gender were not explicitly mentioned by the mayors. However, these constraints or challenges are not believed to have a significant impact on the project action.

Ethical barriers and challenges

- Establishing a vision for a fair and just development of the valley is a challenge because it requires a commitment to overcome disparities across different municipalities and types of stakeholders, to value the quality of life of the community in its entirety (as contrasted to the economic benefit of a few), and to include Nature as a "stakeholder" with its own rights to be protected. However, the current governance body of Valle di Sole (the assembly of mayors that rules the Community of Valley) has elaborated a joint document that clearly states the required commitment.

Other barriers and challenges

- Local stakeholders also mentioned as a possible barrier the low managerial preparedness to exploit new opportunities, i.e., to embrace new risks (e.g., slow tourism initiatives) as a change to a wealthy status quo (e.g., intensive tourism).

4.2.2 Pilot 2: Tramuntana Sóller

Economic barriers and challenges

- Given the extensive subdivision of agricultural plots in the municipality, the Agricultural Cooperative of Sóller plays a crucial role in supporting local agriculture. However, the cooperative itself lacks the resources to adequately support and supply all farmers during each season.
- The local population scarcely visits the museums of the municipality, and outside of the high season, these museums receive minimal foot traffic while other tourist attractions are over-saturated.
- The wealth of the municipality is not equally distributed among the territory, its sectors and stakeholders, resulting in a handful of businesses concentrating the large majority of tourist incomes. This also results in few local stakeholders retaining all the power and decision-making for the whole territory, which also exacerbates the tensions and lack of cooperation between local stakeholders.

Technological and infrastructural barriers and challenges

- No centralized tool for collecting tourism data. All establishments are required by Law 8/2012, of 19 July, on Tourism on the Balearic Islands (and due to heavy bureaucracy) to provide data and statistics, but there is no uniform system in place, resulting in a lack of standardized data collection. Therefore, there is no disaggregated tourism data for Sóller available (only at the regional level).
- No data sharing or cross-referencing of data occurs between sectors or even between actors within the same sector. This is primarily due to a significant deficiency in understanding the value, potential, and utilization of data among local actors. Additionally, there is a lack of awareness regarding existing technologies and solutions. This lack of knowledge is further compounded by the workers' lack of competence in technology-related matters. Need for training of local actors on digitalization, technologies and innovation issues (questionnaire result: Local actors see the “Lack of training and knowledge of users on the use of technology” as the main challenge in Sóller in terms of digitalization).
- The mobility problem that Sóller is experiencing is partly due to the deficiency of public transport in Mallorca, which has an impact on a rate of cars per inhabitant much higher than the national and European average (Mallorca: 902 cars/1,000 inhabitants; Balearic Islands: 756 cars/1,000 inhabitants; Spain/EU: around 520 cars/1,000 inhabitants).
- In order to adequately supply local products to all individuals within the municipality (both residents and tourists), it is essential for the Agricultural Cooperative of Sóller to have forecasts and estimations (cross-referenced with real time data) of the population capacity in Sóller. This allows for advance orders of oranges and other local products from farmers, ensuring better service delivery.
- There is a lack of centralized cultural information. Within the municipality itself, there are several websites, platforms, calendars, and cultural agendas. However, the information is not cross-referenced or integrated; it is scattered. This results in some cultural sites in the municipality lacking visitors (e.g., museums of Sóller, botanical garden), while others experience overcrowding and tourist saturation (e.g., Sóller railway/train)

Legal barriers and challenges

- Due to the topography of Sóller, many agricultural plots are of small dimensions and are not classified as production areas but as 'urban gardens.' As a consequence, these farmers cannot be considered professionals in the sector, are ineligible for subsidies, and cannot legally sell their products. This reality hampers the promotion of agriculture among young

people, as the few who engage in it must also pursue other parallel occupations (often as gardeners for foreigners with second homes on the island). Furthermore, it exacerbates the prevalence of an underground economy (with a significant amount of work conducted off the books).

- The current restrictions in place in Spain, and more specifically in the Balearic Islands, impedes the large uptake of drone technologies in agriculture. Spraying applications, which is the most sought application by farmers, are not allowed in the archipelago, and it is forbidden to fly drones over 10kg. In addition, the valley of Sóller is located within the Tramuntana mountain range, which is a UNESCO protected site, complicating even more the bureaucracy to be authorized to fly drones.

Challenges related to gender

- According to the latest agriculture census (2020), the agriculture sector in the municipality of Sóller is still predominantly male, with 73% of farm managers being men and only 27% being women. Given the high average age of farmers in Sóller and the lack of generational renewal, it is crucial to understand why young women (and young farmers in general) are not getting more involved in local agriculture.

Ethical barriers and challenges

- Tourists often lack awareness of local realities and are unwilling to adapt their behaviour; they tend to exhibit impatience and high expectations, requiring instant access to everything. This is causing increased tensions between tourists and the local population.
- There is a large percentage of foreign population in Sóller (18%), dominated mostly by French, British, Germans, Swedish and Italians. The profile of these international residents is usually of high-income and advanced age (+50 years old). This is causing two main social issues: a perception of loss of cultural identity by local population, and a tremendous increase in property prices ²⁵that is also contributing to the loss of young people to other more affordable cities and villages. The increase of real estate prices is further exacerbated by the large number of second houses belonging to foreigners (not considered residents). In summary, there is a gradual shift happening where younger, financially disadvantaged locals are being replaced by older, wealthy foreigners.

Other barriers and challenges

- Mass tourism in the valley of Sóller leads to discontent among both tourists and residents. The overcrowding results in mobility issues throughout the municipality, including a lack of parking opportunities and traffic jams. The presence of illegal vacation rentals further aggravates the situation. While the services and infrastructure of Sóller are designed based on the population quota and tourist accommodations' capacity, the significant prevalence of illegal vacation rentals disrupts the balance, estimated to represent almost 30% of the tourist offer. To address this issue, the public administration recently assigned 25 people to inspect and regulate vacation rentals. However, it has been observed that the operational procedures of these inspectors are inefficient, failing to address the root of the problem and allowing illegal vacation rentals to persist.

²⁵ According to statistics published by one of the largest online real estate platforms in Spain ([Idealista](#)), the average price per m² in Sóller for properties listed on their platform reached its highest price yet in May 2024, at 4,530€/m², marking a **266% increase** compared to ten years ago.

- Additionally, there is a lack of effectiveness on the part of local and regional administrations in monitoring and managing tourist flows. Although there have been initiatives to develop apps aimed at helping tourists make the most of the island's resources while avoiding overcrowding, such solutions have yet to yield significant results and remain under development (e.g., Palma App). The Sóller City Council initiated a project to install traffic information screens at the main entrances to the municipality, aiming to indicate the level of congestion in parking lots and roads. However, despite the physical implementation of the screens, the system never functioned properly
- The aging of farmers and the lack of generational renewal pose pressing challenges. Currently, the average age of farmers in Sóller is over 60 years old. Within 5 years, the vast majority of local farmers will be retired, with no one to replace them.
- With climate change, the shortage and scarcity of water have become particularly concerning issues directly impacting the quality, productivity, and profitability of crops.
- There are not many workshops being organized apart from a few regular ones such as those organized by the Agriculture Cooperative of Sóller during the orange or olive seasons. There is potential to increase and better distribute the number of workshops and socio-cultural activities throughout the year.

4.2.3 Pilot 3: Northern Ostrobothnia

Economic barriers and challenges

The number of microenterprises and SMEs providing services are low as the number of enterprises in the sparsely populated rural regions is low in general. The size of markets for companies may be insufficient, and skills and willingness of companies to join to provide services via platform economy is unclear. Starting a platform economy-based business to rural regions needs a viable business model and revenue logic as well as sufficiently large markets to operate.

Technological and infrastructural barriers and challenges

There are no technological or infrastructural challenges due to extremely high availability and coverage of mobile internet, and the target customers have largely smart phones, including the elderly. Also, digital and data infrastructure as well as e.g. road and address data have very high quality and availability.

Legal barriers and challenges

The pilot area covers three rural municipalities, Alavieska, Kalajoki and Nivala, in the Nordic peri-urban area having a strong entrepreneurial ecosystem for MSMEs. Key problems are related to connecting the demand for local services to smaller-scale companies. Entrepreneurial activity in the target areas in MSME business sizes is intensive, and the role of micro and small enterprises is emphasized, so the pilot area provides promising conditions for piloting. The municipalities of Alavieska, Kalajoki and Nivala are all committed to be supporters and stakeholders in the project, and they will collaborate also via their business support services to promote the pilot activities. Platform economy-based mobility services for social and health care related travel are not easily integrated to subsidies provided by the Social Insurance Institution of Finland (Kela).

Challenges related to gender

Half (49 %) of the Finnish respondents in the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor survey²⁶ thought that fear of failure would prevent them from starting a business. While 38 % of men feared failure, 56 % of women thought the fear of failure would prevent them from starting a business. However, women's entrepreneurship compared e.g. to Sweden, Norway, and the Netherlands was seen as the strength of Finland. The fear diminished slightly with greater age, but region, education, and household income had little impact on the fear of failure.

Ethical barriers and challenges

UOULU, C. OULU, or the stakeholders did not identify any ethical issues related to the piloting. A high standard related to the GDPR in piloting must be followed. Also, ethical problems related to some platform economy enterprises, e.g. low income or entrepreneurial risks of employees working as entrepreneurs, have to be considered carefully in designing the pilot and its revenue logic.

²⁶ Björk, P., Saarela, M., Kotavaara, O., & Muhos, M. (2022). Global Entrepreneurship Monitor 2021–2022 Finnish report. <https://www.gemconsortium.org/report/global-entrepreneurship-monitor-20212022-finnish-report>

Other barriers and challenges

Finland’s strong points in Global Entrepreneurship Monitor survey were the availability of financing, entrepreneurship education in school, research and development transfer, access to infrastructure and women’s entrepreneurship compared to Sweden, Norway, and the Netherlands. Finland’s weak points were lack of support to entrepreneurship in cultural and social norms.

4.2.4 Pilot 4: East Herzegovina

Economic barriers and challenges

- The region of East Herzegovina, with the exception of the city of Trebinje and the municipality of Gacko, belongs to the underdeveloped area of Republika Srpska.
- Competing with well-established tourist destinations within the region is challenging for East Herzegovina, especially because those destinations have more developed infrastructure and marketing budgets.
- Insufficient funding and investment opportunities are also some of the obstacles to the development of tourism infrastructure, marketing campaigns, and other initiatives necessary to attract visitors and compete effectively in the tourism market.
- Dependence on seasonal tourism also leads to revenue fluctuations, with businesses struggling to generate sufficient income during off-peak periods.
- Developing and maintaining new and modern infrastructure and tourism infrastructure, such as roads, accommodations, and recreational facilities, can be costly, particularly in rural areas with limited existing infrastructure. Financing these investments while ensuring affordability for tourists and profitability for businesses can be a challenge.
- Investment from the side of private stakeholders is very limited due to high bank interest rates, limited dedicated credit lines for agriculture, the absence of credit lines for tourism projects, as well as the risks and reluctance of private individuals to engage in such ventures.

Technological and infrastructural barriers and challenges

- Inadequate infrastructure such as poor roads, poorly connected by public transport or with no public transport lines at all, infrequent departures, and weak connections between the cities of Eastern Herzegovina and connections with other parts of Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Serbia or Montenegro. The only good connection through Herzegovina is the regional road that connects Mostar with Trebinje via Ljubinje.
- Regarding tourist infrastructure there is a bad or non-existing tourist infra and superstructure (touristic info points, tourists' signalisation, camping sites....), limited accommodation options and a lack of solid internet connections. In some remote mountain areas, there is a frequent shortage of electricity and water supply.
- Lack of effective marketing and promotion strategies leads to low visibility of East Herzegovina as a tourist destination, both domestically and internationally.
- Limited access to funding for rural tourism development projects can constrain the region's ability to invest in necessary infrastructure, marketing, and training programs.
- Balancing the development of tourism infrastructure with the need to preserve the region's cultural heritage and natural environment can be a challenge.
- There is also a lack of skilled personnel in hospitality, tourism management, and related sectors that hinder the quality of services provided to tourists.

Legal barriers and challenges

- Several laws and regulations govern this area. Currently, the Amendments to the Law on Hospitality have been in force since the beginning of the year, which has somewhat complicated the previous legal framework, and we are trying to find a way to overcome these obstacles. In many cases, this area is regulated by the Ministry of Agriculture, based on examples from countries far more developed in this area of tourism. However, this is not the case in the Republic of Srpska.

- There is no law or any sub law act drafting agritourism. The only legal act regulating one segment of Agrotourism is Rulebook²⁷ on the conditions for the provision of catering services in rural tourism facilities which elaborate in details conditions which must be met by rural tourism facilities in order to engage in this activity.
- In the coming period, we will try to find a way to simplify engagement in rural tourism to increase the number of service providers.

Challenges related to gender

- According to the 2013 census, the number of men and women was approximately equal with a slight advantage in favour of women in the municipalities that are the project area. But, an unofficial common fact is the situation in the villages regarding gender is different. Women do not want to marry in the countryside, so the number of unmarried men is much higher in rural areas.
- When it comes to the number of women like holders of agricultural households, majority of holders are men. In Republic of Srpska there is 20% of women who are holders of agricultural households. One possible obstacle to equality is the traditional mindset prevalent in these areas, which assumes that agricultural households are predominantly led by men as heads of households.
- In the tourism sector, both in larger tourist centers such as Trebinje and smaller ones like Gacko, a large number of women work in tourist enterprises. Additionally, in villages, women are primarily responsible for making homemade authentic products, maintaining households, welcoming and communicating with tourists. From this perspective, they require training for specific skills in providing tourism services, but we believe there is a good foundation for further improvement.

Ethical barriers and challenges

- All project activities should ensure that tourism development initiatives actively involve and benefit local communities, including women, local residents, and marginalized groups, which can help address inequalities and promote ethical tourism practices. One of the challenges is to try to integrate principles of gender equality and ethical practices into environmental conservation efforts, such as promoting women's involvement in sustainable resource management and eco-friendly tourism initiatives.
- Another challenge is to ensure that tourism-related benefits, such as income generation opportunities and access to infrastructure and services, are distributed equitably among different gender and socio-economic groups within East Herzegovina's communities. The challenge is also to ensure that tourism development is environmentally sustainable, minimizing negative impacts on natural resources and ecosystems.

Other barriers and challenges

- Only 6 households registered for agritourism in whole region East Herzegovina.
- A small number of producers of local products
- Some local products are disappearing
- Local animal race Hercegovacka pramenka in the way of extinction
- A small amount of money intended for agritourism
- Banks have no credit lines for agritourism development

²⁷ Official Gazette of the Republic of Srpska", number 15/20

4.2.5 Pilot 5: Šmarje-Padna

Economic barriers and challenges

Sustainability of the developed solution is most pressing: in economic terms - making sure that the developed service will be in regular everyday use within the identified pilot with a long-term impact on both communities. In this regard, the challenge is to enable revenue share which will provide long-term sustainability of the developed service. Therefore, analysing existing good practices is key, as this will enable to develop a solid business model that will follow the principle of social entrepreneurship; e.g. donations, volunteering (drivers), circular economy (variety of options).

Technological and infrastructural barriers and challenges

“Digital know-how” - provision of a regular technical assistance; importance of the human capital dimension; according to the DESI 2023 report, Slovenia falls behind the EU average on human capital and basic digital skills. Even though, data shows that the Šmarje community does not have the problem of retention of the IT talent. Regarding data aspect, it is important to state that currently, no centralized tool for collecting data regarding the mobility exists - only different dispersed data sets are available. In terms of the so-called infrastructure dimension, the challenge will certainly be how to create a good, solid relation between the local level and municipality level in terms of providing a long-lasting developed service: from (if needed) physical space, needed for operating the service, to - in relation to the economic dimension - provide financial stability for the operating level of the service. To sum up, a combination of the following dimensions, i.e. physical, know-how, community motivation and support from the policy makers (both levels: municipality level and national level) will be needed to make provide and ensure sustainability of the developed solution, making sure, that the pilot will serve the needs of the communities of Šmarje and Padna.

Legal barriers and challenges

The developed service will need to consider the challenges of data ownership and management of insurance policies for drivers and passengers. In regard to additional co-creation of the cycling routes, taking into account the challenge of private property insurance will be needed. To sum up, it will be necessary to ensure that the platform complies with all relevant laws and regulations, including those related to data protection, labor rights, and environmental standards.

Challenges related to gender

Encouraging more women to work in the ICT sector. However, in Slovenia, there is a particular challenge of low digital skills among elderly women. In terms of the ICT female specialists, Slovenia, following the DESI report 2023, has improved slightly. The share of female ICT specialists remains the same as last year's at 17%, below the EU average of 19%, which is sth. this service will take into account. The developed service will - among other target groups - in particular address the challenge of providing mobility assistance to elderly women (widows, who do not have their driver license, cars etc.), as they are usually a target group that is most affected by the absence of public transport in rural areas.

Ethical barriers and challenges

The ethical dimension is multilayered and consists of the following elements: (i) Data aspects (collecting only the data that is necessary for the functioning of the platform to avoid unnecessary intrusion into users' privacy; data protection with the necessary security measures; (ii) Accessibility and inclusivity in relation to the (rural) digital divide: a) access to technology: Ensuring that the platform is accessible to all, including those who may not have access to smartphones or the internet;

b) user interface design: designing the platform to be user-friendly for people with varying levels of digital literacy, including the elderly and disabled; (iii) Equity in service provision in relation to the affordability: making sure that the services provided are affordable for all socio-economic groups, avoiding exclusion based on financial capability; (iv) Social impacts: employment concerns: Ensuring that the platform creates new job opportunities and provides training and support for those affected by displacement; (v) Ethical use of technology: algorithmic bias and in this manner, ensuring that the algorithms used in the platform are free from biases that could lead to unfair treatment of certain groups or individuals, resulting in transparency: making the decision-making processes of the platform transparent to users, allowing for accountability and trust.

4.2.6 Pilot 6: Devetaki Plateau

Economic barriers and challenges

For the last 10 years, the Devetaki Plateau has been developing as a tourist destination. There has been a transition from solely agriculture as an economic profile to tourism as an emerging business opportunity and alternative. Small rural businesses have been started to offer accommodation, food, and other services for tourists. The DPA and the three municipalities have invested resources in small tourist infrastructure and advertising and the region is already a fact on the tourist map of Bulgaria. However, there is no obligation for the local authorities to collect and process data and it is difficult to analyse the development of the tourist services. This is a barrier to analyse and assess the tourist services offered by the local businesses, the tourist flow size and type, and to target the business resources and the marketing efforts accordingly.

Technological and infrastructural barriers and challenges

In all the nine villages of the Devetaki Plateau the service of waste collection exists and it is organised by the municipalities. However, waste is not separated. Our analysis shows there is a lot of glass, plastic and even - organic waste that is all collected in one place. There are no separate collection bins, no separate depositories in the municipalities and all waste goes to the regional landfills. Another issue is the low level of knowledge and culture among the local residents in the significance of separate waste management. The households do not or rarely collect waste separately or have composters for the organic waste. A technological solution to monitor various types of garbage and to optimise separate waste collection is needed to respond to the community needs.

Legal barriers and challenges

Telemedicine is still not a priority for Bulgarian policy. There is neither a strategy nor national legislation to help regulate steps in this direction. At the same time, the majority of patients and potential patients have probably used the telephone to get medical advice or information and a growing number of them have personal computers and software that allow them to use medical databases and sources. The same with doctors and nurses: most of them have probably used the telephone to discuss patient care; many have participated in continuing medical education by teleconference; and some specialists such as radiologists are gaining considerable experience with the transmission of images for consultation purposes. However, it would be a challenge to convince the health authorities and practitioners of the need and the effectiveness of telemedicine. It will also take time and effort to work with the local communities: information campaigns and capacity building for using the modern technologies will be needed. A SIP in this sphere would provoke positive public discourse and a follow - up result might be drafting regulations to facilitate the dissemination of the pilot's experience in other regions of Bulgaria.

Challenges related to gender

Demographic data shows women are a majority in the villages (%) as compared to men. The SIP or SIPs will influence positively most of the population, especially, Telemedicine and Intelligent waste management. Efforts related to education, information, and training, as well as co-creation and participation will be directed in a balanced way to men and women.

Ethical barriers and challenges

As far as the ethical dimension is concerned, there are several aspects:

- Collecting and processing data regarding the health status of the population in the villages might be considered delicate. All necessary measures for the protection of this kind of data shall be taken.
- The same is the situation with the data collected from tourists. Thus, the surveys will be done anonymously and with their definite agreement. Data regarding incomes from tourism should be accessible for it is a part of the municipal budget which by law is a public document.
- Measures shall be planned towards making the telemedicine service accessible for the whole community notwithstanding their age, gender, technological capacity. Training and information campaigns shall be designed to assure that.

4.3 SWOT ANALYSIS

4.3.1 Pilot 1: Valle di Sole

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Valuable environmental and natural resources. The natural heritage includes: the Dolomites (UNESCO World Heritage); water resources (e.g. rivers, lakes, glaciers); forest canopy (covering almost 70% of its surface); protected areas (Stelvio National Park, the Noce river, and the Adamello Brenta Nature Park). ▪ High tourism potential ▪ Educational institutions ▪ Strong social and financial capital ▪ Very high levels of renewable energy production ▪ Human values (value of work, commitment, effort, constancy) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Loss of cultural identity ▪ low awareness of the peculiarities of the territory ▪ Winter tourism exposed to climate change risks. ▪ Modest attractiveness for new generations ▪ Lack of capacity to manage resources entrepreneurially ▪ Lack of awareness of the new potentials ▪ Uneven development across different areas ▪ Depopulation and ageing population
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Landscape restoration and enhancement of environmental resources ▪ Increase intra- and inter-sector relationships (e.g. tourism, agriculture, etc.) ▪ Need to open the comparison of the area with other territories ▪ Unique Tourist Promotion Agency in Val di Sole ▪ Rail connection with urban areas is underutilized, but has enormous potential 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mass tourism and difficulty in transitioning to quality (slow) tourism, which would require high investments and yield low short-term profits ▪ Conflicts between sectors (agriculture vs. tourism) and within the same sector ▪ Competition with other territories (e.g. Alto Adige) ▪ The GDP is higher than in other areas: aversion to risk and difficulty in promoting change

4.3.2 Pilot 2: Tramuntana Sóller

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Unique strategic location ▪ Diversity of resources (natural, landscape, cultural, heritage and ethnological) with tourist potential ▪ Destination well known by tourists and with a strong presence within the tourism distribution channels ▪ Tourist routes promoted by the government ▪ Mature business network rooted in the territory ▪ Increase in the supply of regulated holiday homes and the number of tourists staying overnight in the municipality. ▪ Strong and active associative network (170 registered, active associations) ▪ Institutional commitment for the socio-economic dynamization of the municipality through tourism and initiatives already undertaken 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ High urban pressure ▪ Gentrification of the port and town centre ▪ Poor network of social facilities ▪ Uncontrolled tourism flows that lead to problems in mobility, raising numbers of illegal vacation rentals and resident/tourist discontent. ▪ Poor data and tech knowledge and infrastructure hinder effective resource management. ▪ None or little cooperation among sectors ▪ Poor offer of digital services by municipality and local companies ▪ Ageing of farmers with no generational renewal ▪ Brain Drain Phenomenon/Lack of Talent
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ International recognition of the Mallorca brand ▪ Positive forecast of growth in tourism worldwide ▪ Changes in demand’s tastes and habits: new products, markets and segments (intra- and intersectorial) ▪ Growth in the number of tourists staying in legal tourist homes ▪ Specific competences of municipalities, including provision of information and promotion of tourist activities of local interest and scope. ▪ Sources of funding at European, national, regional and island level, for rural development projects. ▪ Development of new technologies applied to tourism (smart tourist destinations), agri-food and related sectors. ▪ Diversification of the “sun and beach” offer ▪ Potential of tourism products such as cultural, archaeological, cycling, religious and natural tourism. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Increased competition between destinations and products. ▪ Poor management of tourist information within communication channels. ▪ Increase in the offer of tourist accommodation in the rural area of Mallorca. ▪ Limited access to public funding sources and lack of continuity of projects due to political changes in public institutions ▪ Unshared and uncoordinated vision among tourism actors. ▪ Socio-economic instability in a globalized economy. ▪ Increased impact of climate change on tourism and agri-food sector (e.g. water scarcity)

4.3.3 Pilot 3: Northern Ostrobothnia

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Strong entrepreneurial ecosystem: Intensive entrepreneurial activity and a high share of active micro-enterprises and SMEs. ▪ High level technological infrastructure and citizens ability to use it: Excellent mobile internet and high-speed broadband coverage, high-quality digital and data infrastructure, and a high digital readiness also within the elderly. ▪ Committed Stakeholders: The municipalities of Alavieska, Kalajoki, and Nivala are fully supportive and involved in the project. ▪ Good capability to communicate with local communities via municipalities and Local action groups. ▪ Entrepreneurial education is developing and increasingly available. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Limited Market Size: Size of population and the absolute number of microenterprises and SMEs is low due to the sparsely populated rural regions. ▪ An aging population and a weakening economic dependency ratio. ▪ Current enterprises are not widely skilled in digital marketing and platform economy. ▪ Resource Constraints: Potential issues in maintaining and financing the service directory platform. ▪ Entrepreneurial Hesitation: Uncertainty in the skills and willingness of companies to adopt platform economy-based business models.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Opportunities for young and starting entrepreneurs ▪ Better services in rural regions ▪ Larger markets for service-oriented rural micro-enterprises and SMEs. ▪ Increased life quality enables to retain population. ▪ Reduced pressure on services for the elderly, increased trust to society’s ability to take care. ▪ Tourism and remote work growth, which may again boost demand for local services. ▪ Integration of NGOs’ and citizens’ volunteering and support services for the elderly, which may also help to reduce loneliness. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Criminal usage of the platform, risk of home intrusion and phishing of personal information. ▪ Decline in population and too small absolute size of the market. ▪ Economic viability and challenges in ensuring a sustainable business model and revenue logic for the platform. ▪ Competition from urban-centric platform economy solutions that may not fit rural needs perfectly. ▪ Regulatory obstacles and integration issues with existing subsidies and regulations. ▪ Deterioration of the business environment for small and part-time entrepreneurs in relation to policies and legislation.

4.3.4 Pilot 4: East Herzegovina

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Rich natural, geological, cultural, historical and gastronomic heritage (e.g. cheese in a sack on preliminary list of intangible cultural heritage of UNESCO), including narrative heritage (legends and myths), folklore heritage (e.g. <i>gusle</i> instrument and <i>Ganga</i> singing), and rich local know-how. ▪ Region with the largest number of educated population per total number of inhabitants ▪ Motivated group of young artists and photographers ▪ The first thematic gastronomic route in Bosnia and Herzegovina - Cheese and Honey Trail of Eastern Herzegovina ▪ One of the officially declared most beautiful villages in Bosnia and Herzegovina - Bratač is located in East Herzegovina ▪ Pristine nature due to the absence of major sources of pollution, counting with many natural sources of drinking water ▪ Close to major tourist cities and airports such as Mostar and Dubrovnik ▪ Local population has basic knowledge about using the Internet ▪ The Ministry of Agriculture has an incentive measure for the development of rural tourism ▪ The city of Trebinje has several faculties 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Emigration of young people from the region and unfavourable age structure in rural areas ▪ Poor road infrastructure, there is no highway, bad regional and rural roads ▪ Bad or non-existing tourist infra and superstructure (touristic info points, tourists' signalisation, accommodation facilities, camping sites....) ▪ Existence of border crossings and long waiting times at the border in the season ▪ Rural areas have no tradition of tourism entrepreneurship ▪ Unfair payment to producers for agricultural products in the distribution chain ▪ Local producers little focused on the production of the final product (they mainly sell raw materials such as selling milk to dairies) ▪ Only basic health services available in most municipalities of the region ▪ there are no shops, kindergartens, or cultural facilities in the villages ▪ Unplanned construction in the villages spoils the typical appearance of the region ▪ Local knowledge is disappearing, because with the death of the old, there is no one to inherit some local crafts and knowledge ▪ Neglect of maintaining cultural and historical sites ▪ Local communities and local tourist organisations invest little and have an insufficiently clear vision of the development of rural tourism ▪ Only 6 producers registered for agritourism in the entire region ▪ Local authorities too focused on electricity production ▪ Only a few producers have accommodation in the rural areas of the entire region ▪ Weak knowledge of foreign languages of the population of the region ▪ Large areas of uncultivated plots and neglected pastures ▪ Lack of targeted training for the rural population to engage in rural tourism ▪ The rural population has no pension, which creates a feeling of abandonment of the system

Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Opening of pre-accession negotiations for Bosnia and Herzegovina to join the EU ▪ Availability of funds from the EU and other donors ▪ The Republic "gets" a vision of how to legally frame rural tourism ▪ Increased demand for local products ▪ Growing trend of tourists looking for a vacation in untouched nature ▪ Construction of the airport in Trebinje ▪ Willingness of consumers to buy local products directly from producers ▪ Large expatriated population who wants to spend their vacations in their place of origin ▪ Existence of two mountain camps Volujak and Lebršnik 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The willingness of local producers to venture into rural tourism ▪ Questionable image of the country (the whole of Bosnia and Herzegovina is still associated with war) ▪ Uncontrolled construction of buildings that do not fit into the landscape and architecture of the space (example of solar power plants) ▪ Further deterioration of cultural and historical sites in rural areas ▪ The unstoppable trend of displacement in the region ▪ Insufficiently developed awareness at the institutional level about the importance of rural tourism development ▪ Lack of qualified workforce in tourism, who find jobs en masse in the Croatian coast because they are better paid ▪ For the local population, engaging in rural tourism is embarking on an adventure into something completely unknown to them ▪ Outbreak of animal diseases

4.3.5 Pilot 5: Šmarje-Padna

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Pilot’s openness for digital solutions and previous collaboration of local partners in EU projects (Interreg, Laas, Horizon etc.) ▪ Local communities known for their enthusiasm and open mindedness ▪ Renown winemakers in Šmarje with mature winemaking tradition and fertile soil ▪ Well-established network of Šmarje winemakers, who are working with IoT in winemaking production ▪ Established rural digital wine hub, Divina Hub in Šmarje ▪ Tested business model of virtual wine tasting in Šmarje ▪ Long tradition of quality olive growers in Padna ▪ Padna’s focus on cycling recreational roads ▪ Padna has quality water resources ▪ Quality, boutique-oriented tourism in Padna ▪ Established tourist centre in Padna, with the possibility of renting e- bikes ▪ the pilot understands that digitalization is not just a technical process, but is a socio-economic and cultural process as well, thus is well aware that inclusion of different stakeholders is needed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Complicated administrative processes at municipal and national level - not user friendly for farmers for instance ▪ Poor mobility service to urban areas of Piran and Koper ▪ Lack of data ▪ Phenomenon of “seasonal residency”, in particular in Padna, with seasonal residents not being interested in engagement with the local community ▪ Difficulties in securing investment capital and finding financial resources ▪ Lack of collaboration with research-educational institutions ▪ Lack of financial resources ▪ Lack of suitable jobs in rural areas ▪ High real estate prices, inaccessibility of real estate for the local population (e.g. young people, farmers) ▪ Weak general cooperation between local stakeholders, absence of a unified development vision ▪ Uneven access to social services in rural areas
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Cooperating with other projects, cross-border and interregional integration, learning about good practices and finding financial sources via these project (different mechanisms) ▪ Putting more focus on boutique, not mass style tourism ▪ Creating an ecosystem that would connect local food producers with the sustainable mobility service ▪ Creating a closer relation to the municipalities’ representatives ▪ Encouraging villagers to work on digital skills ▪ Strengthening of connection or exchanges between rural areas and coastal (urban) centers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Not being able to find resources for the continuation of the developed service (economic sustainability) ▪ Mass tourism (cruise ships) ▪ Lack of motivation to address systemic issues, e.g. complicated administrative process ▪ Inadequate spatial planning ▪ Reducing the amount of trips or mobility (due to new habits related to climate change). ▪ Negative natural growth ▪ Emigration (especially of young people), brain drain ▪ Increasing pressures of (transit) traffic, tourism on rural areas

4.3.6 Pilot 6: Devetaki Plateau

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Devetaki Plateau region established as a tourist brand/ destination ▪ Growth in tourism and popularity of the rural area ▪ Strong community uniting 9 villages and 3 municipalities ▪ High quality accommodation/ guest houses ▪ Existence of cultural calendar - new cultural events, renaissance of traditional crafts and art ▪ Good potential for tourism development - natural, cultural, historical ▪ Start of the elaboration of digital trails and storytelling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Poor capacity for project preparation and management ▪ Health and social services are not accessible ▪ Lack of qualified and motivated personal in tourism ▪ Lack of integrated/ digital tourist products packages ▪ Lack of guides (including, digital ones) ▪ Lack of organised data for tourism development in the municipalities
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ New Local Action Group and Strategy ▪ Young families settling in the region ▪ Good internet access - an opportunity for home office, digital nomads, digital services ▪ Great potential for rural experiential tourism (nature, culture and history, quality guest houses, attractions) ▪ A niche/ interest towards alternative/ experiential tourism at hand ▪ Partnership and coordination of the efforts of Devetaki Plateau Association and the three municipalities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of funding for village infrastructure (roads, water, waste management, etc.) ▪ Poor inter-municipal cooperation due to unstable national policy ▪ Poor infrastructure (roads, water supply) ▪ No EU - or state funding for rural areas (delay of programs, no measures for rural tourism) ▪ Limited access to education services ▪ Not enough cultural and social events - for elderly, children and young people ▪ Demographic decline

4.3.7 Comparison Between Pilots

Based on the previous SWOT analysis, the main similarities and differences can be identified regarding the rural development potential and challenges of the six pilots’ regions.

Similarities

Strengths

- **Environmental and Natural Resources:** All regions have valuable natural resources and heritage, which are crucial for tourism. Examples include the Dolomites in Valle di Sole, cultural and natural heritage in Sóller and East Herzegovina, and the scenic landscapes of the Devetaki Plateau.
- **Tourism Potential:** High tourism potential is a common strength across the regions. They each have unique attractions that draw visitors, from historical sites to natural beauty and cultural events.
- **Community Engagement and Local Networks:** Strong local networks and community engagement are evident, particularly in Sóller, East Herzegovina, and Devetaki Plateau. These networks support tourism and local development initiatives.

Weaknesses

- **Ageing Population and Depopulation:** All regions face challenges with ageing populations and youth emigration, which threaten long-term sustainability.
- **Economic Constraints and Lack of Funding:** Funding issues and economic constraints are significant weaknesses. For example, lack of investment capital in Šmarje-Padna and poor funding for infrastructure in Devetaki Plateau.
- **Digital and Technological Gaps:** Limited digital services and technological infrastructure are common issues, affecting effective resource management and business operations.

Opportunities

- **Development and Diversification of Tourism:** Opportunities exist to diversify tourism offerings and develop new tourist products. This is seen in Sóller’s potential for cultural and natural tourism, and in the niche tourism potential in Devetaki Plateau.
- **European Union and External Funding:** Many regions can leverage EU and external funding for rural development projects, such as East Herzegovina and Šmarje-Padna.
- **Enhancing Intra- and Inter-Sectoral Relationships:** Strengthening relationships between sectors like tourism and agriculture can boost overall development, an opportunity noted in Valle di Sole and Sóller.

Threats

- **Climate Change:** The impact of climate change poses a threat to tourism and agriculture, as noted in Valle di Sole and Sóller.
- **Economic and Political Instability:** Unstable political situations and economic instability are threats, particularly in East Herzegovina and Devetaki Plateau.
- **Competition and Market Challenges:** Increased competition between destinations and products is a common threat, especially for regions like Sóller and Valle di Sole.

Differences

Strengths

- **Technological Infrastructure:** Northern Ostrobothnia stands out with its high level of technological infrastructure and digital readiness, unlike the other regions.

- **Unique Cultural Heritage:** East Herzegovina has a particularly rich cultural and historical heritage, with notable sites from various historical periods and a strong narrative heritage.
- **Established Digital Solutions:** Šmarje-Padna is noted for its established digital solutions in winemaking and tourism, which is a unique strength compared to other regions.

Weaknesses

- **Gentrification and Urban Pressure:** Sóller faces high urban pressure and gentrification, issues that are less prominent in the other regions.
- **Administrative and Bureaucratic Challenges:** Complicated administrative processes are significant in Šmarje-Padna, posing a unique challenge for local stakeholders.

Opportunities

- **Youth and Entrepreneurial Opportunities:** Northern Ostrobothnia highlights opportunities for young entrepreneurs and improving services in rural regions, which is a less emphasized opportunity in other regions.
- **Cross-Border and Interregional Integration:** Šmarje-Padna emphasizes opportunities for cross-border and interregional cooperation, which is not a primary focus for the other regions.

Threats

- **Infrastructure and Service Accessibility:** Devetaki Plateau faces specific threats related to poor infrastructure and limited access to health, social, and educational services, which are not as prominently highlighted in other regions.
- **Regulatory and Policy Challenges:** Northern Ostrobothnia faces unique threats related to regulatory obstacles and integration issues with existing subsidies and regulations.

5. ACTION PLANS

5.1 PILOT 1: VALLE DI SOLE

The context analysis of Valle di Sole revealed that the local community is facing several challenges related to an ageing population, which is decreasing in numbers also due to modest attractiveness for new generations; a gradual decline of cultural identity with a consequent abandonment of traditional economic activities related to land use and preservation; an economy mainly driven by tourism which presents fragilities and stress elements.

The initial investigation with the local decision-makers of Valle di Sole revealed that the valorisation of the environment can provide a step toward the sustainable development of the local economy and community. What is needed is to:

- Improve the capacity of action (for example, with data-driven tools to support decision-making);
- Support the collaborative development of new policies, services, and initiatives strengthening the economic valorisation of natural resources;
- Ideate educational and participatory actions to raise local communities' awareness of the value and opportunities of natural heritage.

Based on the collected data and carried out analyses, the initial action plan for P1 will be focused on:

- **Identify specific actions** to be experimented within SMART ERA.
- **Extend the core work group** with other local stakeholders closely related to the pilot scenarios.
- **Create awareness in the local stakeholders** about opportunities offered by data, technology, SIPs planning and reusability.
- **Define a detailed pilot action plan** with the local stakeholders and decide how to engage the community.
- Incrementally **co-design a SIP** that addresses the selected scenarios.
- Experiment with the **co-delivery** of the designed SIP and its **evaluation**.
- Implement **communication and outreach activities** for residents and visitors.
- Provide **policy recommendations**.

5.2 PILOT 2: TRAMUNTANA SÓLLER

The analysis of the data collected for the pilot of Sóller revealed the reality of some problems in the municipality, caused by the massification of tourism, by the aging of the population, by the lack of data, digitalization and data sharing, and by the lack of knowledge and lack of cooperation between local entities and actors.

More specifically, the results have shown:

- Lack of data to improve decision making and/or to develop new products/services. This goes along with the lack of deployed infrastructure (such as sensors or integrated data platform).
- Need for training of local actors on issues of digitalization, technologies and innovation.
- Need for integrated systems, both for data collection and analysis (especially for tourism and mobility sectors), and for the marketing and promotion of products and services (agriculture and cultural sectors).
- Need for public policies and services adapted to the reality of Sóller (control of vacation rentals, classification of urban gardens, management of the flow of tourists and mobility within the municipality...).
- An intangible but crucial point is the need to better inform tourists about the reality of the tourist destination of Sóller, in order to influence their behavior and improve coexistence with residents. Therefore, carrying out communication and awareness campaigns continues to be very necessary.

In consequences, the action plan for P2 will focus on:

- Promote **cooperation** and **data sharing** among local stakeholders.
- Provide **training** and enhance the **digital skills** of local stakeholders.
- Deploy **technology** (sensors, platforms...), and develop and implement **tailored digital services** (apps, dashboards, marketplaces...) to be co-defined by local stakeholders.
- Provide **policy recommendations**.
- Implement **communication and outreach activities** for residents and tourists.

5.3 PILOT 3: NORTHERN OSTROBOTHNIA

The data collection and analysis phase enabled to identify key characteristics and factors affecting the pilot. Strengths include a robust entrepreneurial ecosystem, advanced technological infrastructure, committed stakeholders, effective local communication, and well organised entrepreneurial education. Weaknesses involve a limited market size, aging population, partly insufficient digital marketing skills, resource constraints, and potentially entrepreneurial hesitation. Key opportunities are related to young entrepreneurs, improved rural services, expanded markets, enhanced life quality, increased tourism and remote work, and integrated support services for the elderly. Again, threats include platform misuse, population decline, economic viability challenges, competition from urban-centric solutions, regulatory obstacles, and a deteriorating business environment for small entrepreneurs. Work will continue with the following actions:

- **Phase 1: Establishment of a core working group.** Supported by the analysis, the next step is to establish a core working group. This group will consist of motivated individuals from BSOs and municipalities who are committed to taking the project forward. Workshops will be organised to facilitate discussion and set clear objectives.
- **Phase 2: Strengthening Motivation and Commitment.** With the core group in place, it is time to engage the wider community. Local events and meetings will be organised to strengthen the motivation and commitment of all stakeholders. These events provide a platform for entrepreneurs, BSOs and municipalities to share their thoughts and ideas. The events are instrumental in fostering a sense of unity and common purpose. They also provide an opportunity to gather feedback and refine the project objectives.
- **Phase 3: Co-creating and rewriting the pilot aims.** The core group, with feedback from the community, will begin the process of co-creating and rewriting the pilot objectives and activities. Workshops will be held to ensure that the revised plans are inclusive and meet the needs of the municipalities and BSOs.

5.4 PILOT 4: EAST HERZEGOVINA

On the base of conducted research in P4, and after analyzing collected data, some facts are very prominent such as:

- sparse population, as much as three times lower than the average for Republika Srpska
- poor road infrastructure
- underutilised vast cultural, gastronomic and natural heritage in rural areas of the EH
- the locals don't have a tradition and experience in tourism entrepreneurship
- local administrations and tourist organisations have rather poor vision of rural tourism in EH.

On the basis of the collected data and carried out analyses, action plan for P4 will be focused on:

- work with local tourist organizations on the elements that focused on **branding EH as rural tourism destination**
- work with local producers, women's associations and young ones on the rising awareness of possibilities offering by engagement in **rural tourism entrepreneurship**
- **rising awareness** on necessity to preserve local cultural, natural and gastronomic heritage
- branding rural EH like a new rural touristic destination
- work on **media promotion** of rural EH heritage
- provide support in improving the **visual identity and sales of local products** and to train interested local people on the basics of rural tourism

5.5 PILOT 5: ŠMARJE-PADNA

Following the two conducted SEROI+ workshops and analysis of data of both pilot communities, the need to develop a multilayered, modular sustainable mobility service has been underscored. In particular the elderly, children and teenagers are target groups which, according to analysis, need an adequate mobility service that would connect them to urban areas of Piran and Koper. Due to Šmarje and Padna unique characteristics, i.e. Šmarje’s world renown winemakers and Padna’s focus on tourism (cycling), with fairly good water resources, villagers proposed to create a service, that would connect mobility to principles of circular economy and tourism and would result in a service that would appreciate the importance of taking care of the environment, i.e. environmental education.

More specifically, the results have shown, that the communities would like to obtain a functioning, sustainable rural mobility service, which would be organized as a social enterprise and would be customized for both communities. The service would operate by the principle “on the demand”, and its development would include a very well thought of network of stakeholders, i.e. policymakers, municipalities (in Slovenia, local politics and development of services is very much dependent on the level of municipalities), service providers, investment capital also in the form of donations or sponsorship. The development of the service would follow already existing good practices in Slovenia due to understanding cultural specifics and existing digital skills.

In the manner, the action plan for Šmarje-Padna pilot will focus on:

- **promoting cooperation** and focusing on **addressing the challenge of data**, needed for the development of the service
- providing **training** and enhance the **digital skills** of villagers and municipality workers
- identifying possible education (university level) bodies that would help to **map out the pilot** status
- creating more intense working relation with the policy bodies (municipality level) to provide a more **fertile policy environment**, if possible, to work on policy recommendations / instruments
- working on **development and deployment of digital solution/service** that would be sustainable on a long run and widely used by the communities

5.6 PILOT 6: DEVETAKI PLATEAU

After consulting the three municipalities and representatives of local stakeholder groups, in order to improve the overall quality of life in the villages in the Devetaki Plateau, the objectives they formulated are in the following four directions:

- **Improve the access to health services** in the villages in the Devetaki Plateau
- Stimulate sustainable development of the area and diminish environmental footprint by introduction of **intelligent waste management system**
- **Foster community-led rural tourism development** and establish the Devetaki Plateau as a smart tourist destination
- **Encourage and motivate young people to live in the villages** by offering a broader scope of cultural and educational services

The Action plan would vary in accordance with the specific one or two directions selected out of the above four. In this regard, the steps the Devetaki Plateau Association and the Municipality of Sevlievo plan in the short term, are as follows:

- **Collect further data and information** related to health status, telemedicine practices, waste management companies and solutions, where possible;
- **Foster community engagement and cooperation**, and organise discussions with the three municipalities, the local stakeholders and related companies to assess and prioritise the four directions by means of relevance, feasibility, impact, and resources;
- Communicate with the SMART ERA partners the prioritised topics and **define the potential SIPs** to work on;
- Initiate the **definition and development of the SIPs** with the active involvement of the municipalities and the local stakeholders.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The work initiated by the SMART ERA partners under WP5 to identify the needs and gaps of the six pilots have shown:

- **Large heterogeneity of the different pilots** in terms of socioeconomic development, digitalization, maturity and sustainability, but also in terms of climates, geographies and cultural backgrounds.
- Great disparity in the **availability and quality of data** among pilots, sectors and stakeholders. Some pilots/sectors simply do not have data available or lack integrated and/or disaggregated data.
- The first community engagement activities have highlighted the **difficulty to reach some specific target groups** (e.g farmers), and the profound **needs for training and knowledge** on areas such as digitalization, innovation, sustainability and/or circular economy among others.
- All the participating regions have **significant tourism potential**, but they need to diversify and enhance their offerings to attract different market segments and reduce dependency on seasonal tourism.
- **Ageing populations and youth emigration** are common issues. As a result, the different regions need targeted strategies to retain and attract young people, such as improving job opportunities and quality of life.
- **Strong local networks and community involvement** have been identified by all pilots as critical assets. Local action groups are being implemented throughout the project and shall support the development of initiatives and improve local governance.

Despite the geographical, demographic and socioeconomic heterogeneity of the different pilots, clear similarities can be observed in the expectations of local stakeholders with the SMART ERA project and the type of solutions and activities to be developed and implemented:

- **Improved knowledge** (capacity building)
- **Improved access to information and digital services**
- **Improved market opportunities** for local/rural products
- **Improved infrastructure** for connectivity and data management
- **Improved community development** and networking

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8. ANNEXES

All annexes **A** are related to Pilot 1 Valle di Sole/Trentino

All annexes **B** are related to Pilot 2 Tramuntana/Sóller

All annexes **C** are related to Pilot 3 Northern Ostrobothnia

All annexes **D** are related to Pilot 4 East Herzegovina

All annexes **E** are related to Pilot 5 Smarje-Padna

All annexes **F** are related to Pilot 6 Devetaki Plateau

ANNEXES A – P1 VALLE DI SOLE

- Annex A1. Research methodology followed in Valle di Sole
- Annex A2. Statistics of Valle di Sole
- Annex A3. Datasets available in Valle di Sole
- Annex A4. Results of brainstorming with mayors
- Annex A5. Document elaborated by the mayors of Valle di Sole

Annex A1 – Research methodology followed in Valle di Sole

During the preparation of the SMART ERA project proposal, the rural area of Valle di Sole was selected as a meaningful representative of Alpine mountainous areas facing geographical and economic isolation and experiencing negative demographic trends. Valle di Sole is one of the 72 inner areas in Italy that participate in the National Strategy for Inner Areas, a political intervention activated to promote the creation of multi-level local governance for the development of disadvantaged rural or mountain areas. Given its geographical and socio-economic characteristics and its openness to governance innovation, Valle di Sole was considered a good candidate for participating in SMART ERA pilot activities.

Given that Valle di Sole is not a member of the project consortium, the engagement of local stakeholders required a gradual process of involvement aimed at empowering them with the capacity to be active leaders of the pilot. This was considered an important requisite to make sure the pilot was **representative of realistic governance dynamics** for contexts where the local public authority aims to promote rural development.

The methodology for setting up the needs-and-gaps analysis phase of the pilot progressed along the steps and substeps presented here below. The chosen workflow, with a top-down engagement of key representatives of public organizations related by a dependency relationship (i.e., provincial government → Community of Valley (i.e. assembly of mayors) → municipalities (mayors) → other local stakeholders and the community), reflects practices that facilitate the political advocacy of co-innovation initiatives within the hierarchical structure of Italian public administration [Leonardi and Not, 2023]²⁸.

●.1.1. Preparation phase (January - February 2024)

The activities of the Trentino pilot started with an **analysis of a recent rural innovation project in Valle di Sole** by the Community Activator (PAT) and its presentation to the project consortium for comparison with similar initiatives in the other 5 pilot areas (at the SMART ERA kick-off meeting). The aim of the analysis was to get an initial sense of the potential familiarity of stakeholders in Valle di Sole with the collaborative processes for creating and delivering innovative services in rural areas. The questions addressed included who participated in the sample process, how collaboration was structured, and which critical aspects were observed.

The Community Activator (PAT) and the Pilot Orchestrator (FBK) then proceeded with a **study of several types of documents describing the context of the Valle di Sole rural area** (socio-economic reports, statistical reports) to create a common background knowledge.

The study of the context informed the **selection by PAT of three representative sectors** in which Valle di Sole has recently activated innovation projects within the National Strategy for Inner Areas programme. The existence of initiatives applied to specific sectors was considered evidence of concrete needs and gaps for the territory. The emerged sectors included (i) services in support of the older population, (ii) social services in support of young generations, (iii) capacity building for local public administrators to improve collaborative practices and innovation strategies.

As a feasibility study, FBK performed an internal evaluation of the three sectors and challenges selected in the previous step to understand **their potential suitability to SMART ERA scope and the opportunities for digital technologies**. The pros and cons of the different sectors were

²⁸ [Leonardi and Not, 2023] Leonardi Chiara, Elena Not, Matteo Gerosa, and Roberta Lotti. A Case Study of Cross-Organizational Co-Design with Public Bodies: Opportunities for a Collaborative Platform. In Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Communities and Technologies, pp. 6-11. 2023.

discussed with the PAT to identify concepts and hypotheses for a narrative to be used for the initial local stakeholders' engagement.

●.1.2. Engagement of a leading contact point for the Community of Valle (March 2024)

In the autonomous province of Trento, municipalities are grouped into "Comunità di Valle" (literal translation: Communities of Valley), an intermediate administrative level aimed at aggregating important administrative functions to improve efficiency and efficacy, especially in remote areas, including very small villages. Each Community of Valle is ruled by the assembly of mayors of the area, who elects a president chosen among the mayors. The president of the Community of Valle of Valle di Sole was identified by PAT as the **first leading local representative to be contacted to initiate the pilot activities**. A phone call between PAT and the president introduced the scope and aim of the SMART ERA European project and the related opportunities for remote rural areas.

This was followed by an in-person **meeting involving the president of the Community of Valle**, PAT (3 representatives), and FBK (1 representative) for deeper clarification (14 March 2024). During the discussion, the president mentioned other existing initiatives aimed at addressing current needs and gaps, such as special hands-on programmes for vocational education of young students; aggregation centers for teenagers providing educational activities on digital media literacy; applications of telemedicine; sustainable mobility solutions, especially in support of tourists during high tourist seasons. After the meeting, the president of the Community of Valle reported back to the assembly of local mayors about the possibility of framing one of their upcoming innovation initiatives within the framework of the SMART ERA research and development approach.

●.1.3. Engagement of mayors of the Community of Valle (April 2024)

A plenary meeting was then organized with the participation of the 13 mayors of Valle di Sole, 3 representatives of PAT and 4 representatives of FBK (18 April 2024). A PowerPoint presentation was used to illustrate the SMART ERA project, its opportunities, and workplan, together with inspirational examples of Smart Innovation Packages (SIPs) for rural development. The presentation was followed by a free **brainstorming session** to further explore the priorities of current needs and gaps related to the development of that local rural area. Several themes and sectors emerged as important for the development of the Valle: young people abandoning their home villages, a phenomenon related to different motivations; the consequent abandonment of traditional activities related to land use and maintenance, causing the degradation of landscape quality from the one side and the increase of environmental risks from the other side; the difficulties of creating attractive opportunities for young people to stay, both at the educational level and at entrepreneurial level; the tense cohabitation of communities and big carnivores; the underdevelopment of the agri-food sector, which is very much related to a larger vision encompassing sectors like the protection and valorisation of the environment, the landscape, ecology, health, and innovative forms of entrepreneurship; the need for new sustainable models of tourism that flexibly adapt to climate change; the deterioration of the built environment with high costs for renovating old houses in the centre of villages.

●.1.4. Sector identification and mission statement (May 2024)

The joint meeting above was followed by an **internal discussion and reflection by local mayors about the sector to focus on for the SMART ERA investigation**. As an output, the assembly of mayors produced a brief document with a mission statement that (i) presents the cruciality of landscape and environment for the multi-systemic development of Valle di Sole and (ii) the commitment of Valle di Sole to engage in the SMART ERA project with pilot activities in this sector.

●.1.5. Local core group formation and deeper needs analysis (Mid-May - Mid-June 2024)

The assembly of mayors of the Community of Valle agreed on selecting **three mayors to be part of a core working group**, namely the mayors of the municipalities of Caldes, Pellizzano and Dimaro-Folgarida.

The nominated core working group was invited to a follow-up brainstorming in collaboration with PAT and FBK to deepen the analysis of needs and gaps related to the chosen environment-related sector (28 May 2024). The brainstorming was moderated by FBK to stimulate the discussion of a general swot analysis and the reasoning on specific challenges related to the environment-related sector that attract the stakeholders' interests and expectations.

The material collected along this multistep journey was elaborated by PAT and FBK for the initial description of the Valle di Sole pilot.

Annex A2 – Statistics for Valle di Sole

	UNIT	VALUE (YEAR*, SOURCE) *If no information for 2023 is available, the most recent value was used	Value for comparison (Historical data, national-wide values or similar)	Source																																										
TERRITORY																																														
Surface	In km ²	Valle di sole : 611,53 km² Valle di Sole is organized in 13 Municipalities: <table border="1" style="margin-left: 20px;"> <thead> <tr> <th>Municipality</th> <th>Population (2022)</th> <th>Surface km2 (2024)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>Cavizzana</td><td>236</td><td>3.38</td></tr> <tr><td>Caldes</td><td>1103</td><td>20.81</td></tr> <tr><td>Terzolas</td><td>632</td><td>5.59</td></tr> <tr><td>Male'</td><td>2267</td><td>26.53</td></tr> <tr><td>Rabbi</td><td>1355</td><td>132.79</td></tr> <tr><td>Croviana</td><td>697</td><td>4.99</td></tr> <tr><td>Dimaro Folgarida</td><td>2089</td><td>36.53</td></tr> <tr><td>Commezzadura</td><td>1010</td><td>22.02</td></tr> <tr><td>Mezzana</td><td>878</td><td>27.35</td></tr> <tr><td>Pellizzano</td><td>790</td><td>48.36</td></tr> <tr><td>Ossana</td><td>818</td><td>25.25</td></tr> <tr><td>Peio</td><td>1819</td><td>162.3</td></tr> <tr><td>Vermiglio</td><td>1776</td><td>95.63</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	Municipality	Population (2022)	Surface km2 (2024)	Cavizzana	236	3.38	Caldes	1103	20.81	Terzolas	632	5.59	Male'	2267	26.53	Rabbi	1355	132.79	Croviana	697	4.99	Dimaro Folgarida	2089	36.53	Commezzadura	1010	22.02	Mezzana	878	27.35	Pellizzano	790	48.36	Ossana	818	25.25	Peio	1819	162.3	Vermiglio	1776	95.63	9,85% of the total surface of the province or Trento (Trentino)	Ispat
Municipality	Population (2022)	Surface km2 (2024)																																												
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POPULATION																																														
Population size	Number of inhabitants	15.470 (2022)	Province of Trento: 542.996 (2022)	Istat																																										
Population density	Number of inhabitants /km ²	25,3 (2022)	Average province of Trento: 87,3 (2021)	Ispat																																										
Age average	Total Age of inhabitants /Number of inhabitants	total age average: 46,7 Male age average: 45,6 Female age average: 47,7	Total age average province of Trento: 45,5 (2022)	Ispat																																										
Age distribution	Percentage or count within each age group,	0-5: 4,44% 6-15: 8,87% 6-18: 12,0% 19-49: 35,2%		Ispat																																										

	e.g. <16, 16-64, >64	50-64: 23,7% > 75: 12,2% > 85: 3,9%		
Ageing index	Number of people > 64 / Number of people 0-14) * 100	199,2 (2022) Ageing index. Comparison between Valle di Sole (in blue ink) and the overall Province of Trento (black ink)	Was 108,4 in 1990 Ageing index of the Province of Trento in 172,1 (2022) Ageing index of Italy in 187,6 (2022)	Ispat, Istat
Dependency ratio	(Number of residents > 65 + number of residents < 14 / number of residents 15 - 64) * 100	59,1 (2022)	Was 48,0 in 1990 Province of Trento: 58,1 (2022) Italy: 57,5 (2022)	Ispat
Gender distribution	Percentage or count of female/male (diverse)	Female: 50,6% Male: 49,4% (2022)	Province of Trento: Female: 50,7% Male: 49,3% (2022)	Ispat
Birth rate	Number of births recorded in one year/1.000 inhabitants	7,1 (2021)	Was 10,9 in 1990 Province of Trento: 7,7 (2021)	Ispat

		<p>Number of births per year. The dotted line highlights the negative trend</p>		
Mortality rate	Number of Deaths recorded in one year/1.000 inhabitants	9,5 (2021)		Ispat
Rate of natural increase (RNI) per 1.000 inhabitants	(Live Births-Deaths/Inhabitants)/1.000	-2,4 (2021)	Province of Trento: -2,2 (2021)	Ispat
Foreign population	In % of total population	% of foreign population: 6,8% (2022) Average number of foreign residents population in a year: 1064,5 (2022)	Province of Trento: 8,4% (2022) Average number of foreign residents in 1990: 28,5 Index of variation of the foreign population, base year 2000: 264,8	Ispat
Immigration/Emigration	Registrations and deregistrations in the register due to change of municipality of residence	Index of variation of registered residents (Number of registered residents over the number of registered residents in the year 1981 * 100): 209,2 (2022) Index of variation of deregistered individuals from the registry (Number of individuals deregistered from the registry over the number of individuals deregistered from the registry in the year 1981 * 100): 138,4 (2022)		Ispat

Marital status distribution	Percentage or count of single, married, divorced, etc.	Average number of families: 7075,0 Average number of family members: 2,3 Percentage of married individuals 43,6 % Percentage of unmarried individuals: 45,4 % Percentage of divorced individuals: 3,2 % Percentage of widowed individuals: 7,8 % (2022)	Average number of families in province of Trento: 241.941 (2022)	Ispat
ECONOMY				
Gross domestic product (GDP) per capita	€/inhabitant	data not available at the local level	GDP per capita for the overall Province of Trento = 43.320 euros (2022)	
Gross disposable income per household	€/household	data not available at the local level	Average gross disposable income per household in the Province of Trento in 2021 = 38.526 euros (43.650 when including imputed rents)	Istat
Primary sources of income from household disposable income		data not available at the local level		
Registered companies (Total)		1.645 (2022)		
Registered companies (Sector of activity)		Agriculture 366 Industry 120 Construction 290 Third sector 878		
Employment status and occupation types	Number of employed individuals over the population aged 15 and over in the census * 100	Employment rate among the resident population 51,3 (2011)	was 49,7 in 1991 Province of Trento: 52,9 (2011)	

TOURISM					
Accommodation index	Total number of beds in accommodations for tourists / total number of residents	(2022) Caldes 0,2 Terzolas 0,3 Croviana 0,4 Malé 0,4 Pellizzano 0,7 Rabbi 0,9 Commezzadura 1,1 Ossana 1,7 Peio 1,7 Vermiglio 2,0 Dimaro Folg. 2,3 Mezzana 6,8	Cavizzana 0,1	0,1	Higher values are associated to higher importance of tourism for the municipality economy
Average tourism intensity	Average number of tourists in accommodations per day / total number of residents	(2022) Caldes 0,0 Cavizzana 0,0 Croviana 0,0 Malé 0,1 Pellizzano 0,1 Terzolas 0,1 Rabbi 0,2 Ossana 0,3 Commezzadura 0,4 Peio 0,4 Vermiglio 0,6 Dimaro Folg. 0,7 Mezzana 1,3	Caldes 0,0	0,0	The value expresses the average concentration of tourists with respect to the local community.
Maximum tourism intensity	Maximum number of tourists per day / total number of residents	(2022) Caldes 0,1 Croviana 0,2 Terzolas 0,2 Malé 0,4 Pellizzano 0,4 Rabbi 0,7 Commezzadura 1,1 Ossana 1,1	Cavizzana 0,0	0,0	High values indicate stressful conditions (peaks of overtourism)

		Peio 1,5 Vermiglio 1,8 Dimaro Folg. 2,2 Mezzana 4,2		
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AGRICULTURE AND ENVIRONMENT

Type of land use	hectare	<table border="1" data-bbox="443 828 1061 869"> <thead> <tr> <th>Type of use</th> <th>hectares</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Arable crops</td> <td>70.16</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Fruit trees, grapevine</td> <td>380.04</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Grassland</td> <td>1365.61</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Pasture</td> <td>10722.36</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Cultivated land</td> <td>12538.17</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Land for forestry</td> <td>19201.65</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Other</td> <td>2474.28</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Type of use	hectares	Arable crops	70.16	Fruit trees, grapevine	380.04	Grassland	1365.61	Pasture	10722.36	Cultivated land	12538.17	Land for forestry	19201.65	Other	2474.28	<p>Percentage of used land with respect to provincial surface of the same type (2010): (e.g. Valle di Sole crops / Trentino crops * 100)</p> <p>Arable crops 2,13% Fruit trees, grapevine 1,67% Grassland 6.7% Pasture 11,8% Cultivated land 9,14% Land for forestry 7,64% Other 12,18%</p>	
Type of use	hectares																			
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Cultivated land	12538.17																			
Land for forestry	19201.65																			
Other	2474.28																			

Protected areas	Surface of protected areas / total surface	45,5 (2022)	Province of Trento: 28,4 (2022)	
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Annex A3 – Datasets available in Valle di Sole

Kind of Data	Data Owner	Sensitivity	Access Model	Short Description	Purpose of usage	Data format	Frequency of acquisition
Statistical indicators for the Province of Trento, segmented by districts (Communities of Valley) and municipalities	ISPAT	Public	Data tables can be exported from the web (web access for district data) (web access for municipality data)	The provincial office for statistical data provides a large range of detailed indicators that model the socio-economic context of the Province of Trento. Several indicators are segmented by district (Communities of Valley) and municipality. Annual time series are available. The following sectors are covered: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land usage • Environmental issues (e.g. waste production and recycling) • Build environment • Population • Households and social behaviour • Education and training • Culture, sports, free time • Health • Work Market • Business structure and competitiveness • Agriculture, forestry and fishery • Industry • Constructions • Commerce • Tourism • Transportation 	Statistical indicators can be used to assess various socio-economic aspects of local districts and to draw comparisons with respect to previous periods.	Tables can be exported in .csv (to be checked whether data can be accessed through REST API calls for research purposes)	Indicators have different update timings according to the raw data they refer to. (Annual or decennial when the raw data comes from census)

				• Financial services			
Predictive models for selected indicators for the Province of Trento, segmented by districts (Communities of Valley)	ISPAT	Public	Data tables can be exported from the web (web access) For some data segmentation, data is available on request	For a selected set of indicators, predictive models envisage the value of the indices in 10 years' time. Currently, available indicators are related to population evolution.	Predictions of statistical indicators can be used to better assess the criticality of certain phenomena in the medium term. They can also be used as a term of reference when evaluating the efficacy of certain policies.	Tables can be exported in .csv, .json, .xls (to be checked whether data can be accessed through REST API calls for research purposes)	Annual update
Comparison of statistical indicators of the Province of Trento with other areas in Italy	ISPAT	Public	Data tables can be exported from the web (web access)	For a selected set of indicators, comparison is offered between the data of (i) Trentino, (ii) the adjacent province of Alto Adige and the region of Veneto, (iii) the overall area of Northern-East Italy, (iv) the region of Lombardia, (v) Northern Italy and (vi) Italy.	Statistical indicators can be used to assess various socio-economic aspects of the overall Province of Trento in comparison to nearby regions and Italy overall. They could be used to assess the more general context with which Valle di Sole compares.	Tables can be exported in .csv (to be checked whether data can be accessed through REST API calls for research purposes)	Annual update

General statistical data for different socio-economic sectors and environmental aspects for the Province of Trento, inner districts and municipalities	ISPAT	Public	Data tables can be exported from the web (web access)	Different sorts of socio-economic and environmental data related to Trentino and its inner districts. Annual time series are available	These are statistical data that complement the indicators by providing further information useful for the assessment of the territory (e.g. environmental aspects, safety, mobility, quality of life, etc.)	Tables can be exported in .csv (to be checked whether data can be accessed through REST API calls for research purposes)	Annual update
List of public services	OpenData Trentino	Public	via API (open data)	The information included in the official websites of the municipalities of Valle di Sole has been published as open data. It includes information about available public services like schools, social and health services, associations, and legal services, ...	Open data on local services could be used to automatically assess certain dimensions of territorial development.	.json	static information, infrequently updated by municipalities
List of points of interest and public services	OpenStreetMap	Public	via export	Information about points of interest and public services available in Valle di Sole have been annotated inside the Open Street Map and are available for export.	Data from OpenStreetMap can be used to automatically assess certain dimensions of territorial development.	.osm	periodically updated by volunteer contributors
Data on transportation services	Gestione MITT (Mobilità)	Public	(data set)	Information about public transport infrastructure. (bus lines, timetable, geo-	Open data on local services could be used to	GTFS in zipped files	

	Integrata Trasporti Trentino)			referenced bus stops)	automatically assess certain dimensions of territorial development.		
Mobility data	Trentino Digitale	Restricted	On request, via API (Available for research purposes upon negotiation)	Information about the actual usage of public transportation means, subscribed passes, ticket selling channels	Daily mobility data, aggregated by bus line or ticket selling channel. Data extracted from onboard ticket check-in.		Daily update
Real-time statistical data for the Tourism sector	ISPAT	Restricted / Public	Daily data has restricted access. (Available for research purposes only upon negotiation)	Different types of data are available for the tourism sector: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - data updated daily on arrivals and overnight stays (databases with restricted access) - monthly and seasonal statistics (web access) - general statistics on the tourism sector (web access) 	This type of data can be used to assess the seasonality of socio-economic phenomena affecting Valle di Sole		Daily update
Real estate registry and land registry	Trentino Digitale	Restricted	On request, via API (Available for research	Data on urbanization and fractionation of the land, parcels	Data is aggregated at municipal		

			purposes only upon negotiation)	in land and buildings registry, destination/cultivation of land parcels.,	level and type of use. Data may support decision making		
Weather	Meteotrentino / OpenData Trentino	Public	Via API (open data)	Different types of region-specific weather data, including current data (temperature, precipitation, air humidity, and wind data), forecasts and historical analysis	Weather information to be utilised in field operations planning (cultivation, harvest), in tourism planning or in decision making for risk prevention	.json / .xml / .csv / .geojson	location-based weather data is updated every 15 minutes

Annex A4 – Results of brainstorming with mayors

In the following we present the main themes emerged from the brainstorming of the 13 mayors of the Valle di Sole:

- *Abandonment of the home villages by young people* and the difficulties of creating attractive opportunities for them to stay, both at the educational level and at entrepreneurial level. While there are no major economic development problems and the area has professional growth potential, retaining young people is a challenge across the territory. In this regard, it would be valuable for the mayors to identify the reasons why the area does not meet young people's expectations.
- *Abandonment of traditional activities related to land use and maintenance*, also related to the above mentioned issue. The abandonment has severe implications for the areas, such as the degradation of landscape quality and the increase of environmental risks (such as landslides and mudslides). Related to this issue is also the deterioration of the built environment because of the high costs for renovating old houses in the centre of villages.
- *Coexistence with large carnivores*, such as bears and wolves, is a significant issue in this area. Overall the area has seen an increase in the presence and activity of these species which can lead to conflicts with human activities and livestock. Bear presence is affecting the area's attractiveness and the safety of the resident population.
- *Lack of attractiveness of the territory in terms of training and employment*. The area has limited job opportunities, with many low-profile occupations available.
- *Underdevelopment of the agri-food sector*, which is very much related to a larger vision encompassing sectors like the protection and valorisation of the environment, the landscape, ecology, health, and innovative forms of entrepreneurship. The area was once dedicated to livestock farming, which ensured regular maintenance and care of the land. However, with the decline in this practice, the land now suffers from neglect, leading to increased vulnerability to rockfalls, landslides, and other natural hazards. It is therefore crucial to restore the landscape to its former state of beauty and utility, and to enhance safety through risk monitoring and management.
- *New models for sustainable tourism* are needed that flexibly adapt to climate change. At the moment winter tourism is strongly dependent on skiing and the area offers several skiing opportunities with numerous ski resorts. However, different models of tourism are needed to ensure the long-term sustainability of the area's tourism industry while protecting its natural and cultural heritage

Annex A5. Document elaborated by the mayors of Valle di Sole

TITLE: The Value of Ecosystem Services in Agricultural and Forest Areas of Val di Sole: The Green Balance of Alpine Communities

For the Val di Sole region, it is a priority to include in systemic thinking the value of agriculture and forestry, as well as the value of protected areas under conservation. The mountains today face phenomena of depopulation in some areas and over-tourism in others. Both can be potentially harmful but also have positive aspects if carefully managed. Achieving social, environmental, and economic balance is essential in both situations to mitigate these phenomena.

The project aims to define an economic value - not exclusively monetary - to the natural and semi-natural environment of Val di Sole. This analysis should focus particularly on the contribution of the landscape, composed by forests, the biodiversity of species and habitats, and the direct work of those in the agro-forestry-pastoral sector who maintain these areas in an optimal state. The proper maintenance of the territory ensures numerous services, such as environmental protection, climate change mitigation, human health and well-being, and recreational activities. Considering the modern use of the mountains influenced by urban lifestyles, can local communities achieve a sustainable economic, social, and environmental balance that allows them to be resilient to climate change and centered on the authentic and real quality of life?

To address this question with an inclusive and innovative governance model, we believe it is important to start by identifying the ecosystem services related to the cultivated and forested areas of Val di Sole. These areas are characteristic of the region and form the basis of a well-established cultural model that is currently unstable. Assigning them significance in the decision-making process for conservation and enhancement actions, supported by public authorities, is crucial. Increasing understanding of their function allows the local population to develop awareness of the role sustainably managed rural areas play in improving quality of life. This awareness also helps to clarify the individual willingness to contribute to their conservation and to explore alternative management or development methods. This transforms the costs of active conservation into investments in enhancement. Balancing biodiversity protection with sustainable local development, starting from an appropriate recognition of economic and social activities, ensures that current and future generations can enjoy a quality of life that, according to climate change data, seems more feasible in mountainous areas than in other contexts.

Expected Results

- The general objective of the project is to incorporate the environmental balance into the strategic decisions of local public administrations and major private players to ensure authentic sustainability for local communities and businesses operating in the area. The tourism and crafts sectors, which drive the local economy, can thus include risk assessments related to the value of these often overlooked but crucial assets in their development plans.

Potential Outcomes

- Improve the management of agricultural and pastoral areas.
- Encourage active participation of local communities in the strategic decisions of relevant authorities, enabling stakeholders to weigh diverse inputs and contribute to the socio-economic balance of the territories from a sustainability perspective.
- Quantify the direct and indirect impacts of conservation, monitoring, research, enhancement, maintenance, and use actions on silvo-agricultural-pastoral areas to generally improve the quality of life.
- Develop a methodology that allows comparison with other projects in different sectors evaluated with economic parameters and market prices.
- Consider environmental costs as investments whose benefits accrue to current and future local communities.

- The economic evaluation of ecosystem services provided by agricultural and forest areas will increase local population awareness of their role in improving quality of life. This will lead to a better understanding and acceptance of conservation measures and greater responsibility in their present and future management. The expected impact of the research is the enhancement of sustainability in its environmental, social, and economic dimensions, considering the entire territory of Val di Sole.

ANNEXES B - P2 TRAMUNTANA/SÓLLER

- Annex B1. Results of survey campaign
- Annex B2. Results of first workshop
- Annex B3. Statistics of Sóller
- Annex B4. Datasets available in Sóller

Annex B1 – Results of P2 Survey Campaign

RESULTS OF QUESTIONNAIRE ABOUT STATUS, NEEDS AND CHALLENGES OF DIGITALIZATION IN SÖLLER

PRESENTATION

In May 2024, in the frame of the SMART ERA project, a questionnaire was conducted in Söllér to better understand about the reality and current status, needs and challenges of the local community in terms of digitalization with the aim to define the action plan of the pilot. The questionnaire was shared with the main local stakeholders (companies, associations, public administrations...).

The questionnaire was divided in three sections:

- A section to collect general information about the persons and entities that have answered the questionnaire
- A section dedicated to the technology use and digitalization level of participants
- A section related to the needs and challenges of participants

The obtained results are shown here below:

GENERAL INFORMATION

General information of those who have answered the questionnaire:

TECHNOLOGY AND DIGITALIZATION

1. How would you rate the level of digitalization of your organization?

- **LEVEL 1 - Analog or paper.** Operations are mainly carried out manually or on paper. There is no significant digital integration and communications are usually face-to-face or through traditional methods.
- **LEVEL 2 - Basic Digitalization:** Basic digital technologies have been adopted to a limited extent (accounting or customer management software), but most processes are still carried out manually.
- **LEVEL 3 - Functional Digitalization:** Digital systems have been implemented in specific areas (e.g. CRM or inventory management system). However, there may still be gaps in integration between these manual systems and processes.
- **LEVEL 4 - Integrated Digitalization:** Digital systems have been integrated in most operational areas. There is greater automation of processes and better connectivity between different systems. Data is shared more easily between departments and there is greater efficiency overall.
- **LEVEL 5 - Digital Transformation:** the organization has carried out a complete digital transformation in the way it operates. Processes are highly automated, there is full integration of systems and emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, machine learning or the Internet of Things (IoT) are used to improve efficiency and innovation.

2. Are any of these new technologies used in your organization?

3. What digital media, or what communication channels, are mainly used to communicate with your customers and to sell and/or promote your products and/or services online?

4. In your organization, how would you say data is treated?

- **LEVEL 0 - Non-existent.** No data is collected.
- **LEVEL 1 - Manual.** Data is collected sporadically and manually without an established formal process. Data is usually stored informally, such as in spreadsheets, and analysis is performed manually.
- **LEVEL 2 - Standardized.** Basic systems have been implemented to collect data consistently and store it in a centralized database. Analysis remains primarily manual.
- **LEVEL 3 - Integrated.** More advanced tools have been implemented to collect data automatically and in real time, allowing for more agile decision-making. The analysis begins to become more sophisticated, using basic data analysis techniques.
- **LEVEL 4 - Analytical.** More sophisticated tools and techniques have been implemented to perform more advanced data analysis and extract meaningful insights.
- **LEVEL 5 - Data-Driven and Automated.** Highest level of maturity in data collection and analysis. Decision making is based on data analysis and advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence and machine learning are used to automate processes and generate information in real time.

5. What level of data sharing does your organization have?

- **LEVEL 0 – No data sharing**
- **LEVEL 1 - Internal sharing.** Data is shared only internally.
- **LEVEL 2 - External sharing with selected partners.** Data is manually shared with selected external partners, such as suppliers, customers or strategic business partners. Agreements and protocols are established to ensure the security and protection of shared data.
- **LEVEL 3 - Expanded external sharing.** Data is shared with a broader audience outside the organization, such as the general public, external researchers, or the online community. Publicly accessible platforms or online portals are used to facilitate this sharing.
- **LEVEL 4 - Open and Collaborative Sharing.** Data is shared openly and collaboratively with any interested person or entity. Transparency and public participation in the use and analysis of data are encouraged.

6. If you are not already doing so, would you as an organization be willing to share (non-personal) data with the objective of improving decision making and operational efficiency, among others?

CHALLENGES AND NEEDS

1. According to you, what are the main challenges of Sóller in terms of digitalization?

2. According to you, what are the main socioeconomic challenges of Sóller?

3. What type of digital service(s) would you like to have or improve?

Annex B2 – Results of P2 First Workshop

WORKSHOP ON CO-DEFINITION OF CHALLENGES AND DIGITAL SOLUTIONS FOR SÓLLER

Date: 22/05/2024
Location: Centro Capvespre, Sóller
Number of participants: 15 (see list of participants)
Organizers: AnySolution (ANYSOL) and MésCultura (+CULTURA)

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1 INTRODUCTION

Within the framework of the European project SMART ERA and its pilot action in the municipality of Söllern, a workshop was held on May 22nd, 2024, with the participation of several local actors. The objectives of this workshop were:

- Involve and bring together the different socio-economic actors of the municipality to strengthen or establish **new relationships, alliances and synergies** between actors and sectors that do not usually share much between them.
- Identify the **main challenges in Söllern** (concerning digitalisation, socio-economic and cultural issues)
- Identify and co-define possible **solutions and initiatives** to improve the competitiveness, quality of life, sustainability and resilience of the territory.

The workshop was structured as follows:

Brief overview of the SMART ERA project

- Presentation of the workshop, its objectives and methodology
- Conducting the group activity
- Sharing of the results

The participants were divided into two groups: one working on the topics of **tourism and mobility**, and the other on the topics of **agriculture and culture**. Each group was asked to work together on the consensual and detailed identification of the problems, and on the definition of desired solutions and scenarios.

The results obtained are described below.

2 DESCRIPTION OF THE PROBLEMS

2.1 GROUP 1: TOURISM AND MOBILITY

There is no centralized tool for collecting tourism data. All establishments are required by law (and due to heavy bureaucracy) to provide data and statistics, but there is no uniform system in place, resulting in a lack of standardized data collection. Therefore, there is no disaggregated tourism data for Sóller available (only at the regional level). Furthermore, no data is cross-referenced or shared, either between sectors or between actors in the same sector.

There exists a significant deficiency in understanding regarding the value, potential, and utilization of data among local actors, as well as a lack of awareness regarding existing technologies and solutions. This lack of knowledge is also related to a lack of competence of the workers in technology-related matters.

Mass tourism in the valley of Sóller leads to discontent among both tourists and residents. The overcrowding results in mobility issues throughout the municipality, including a lack of parking opportunities and traffic jams. The presence of illegal vacation rentals further aggravates the situation. While the services and infrastructure of Sóller are designed based on the population quota and hotel capacity, the significant prevalence of illegal vacation rentals disrupts the balance, estimated to represent almost 30% of the tourist offer. To address this issue, the public administration recently assigned 25 people to inspect and regulate vacation rentals. However, it has been observed that the operational procedures of these inspectors are inefficient, failing to address the root of the problem and allowing illegal vacation rentals to persist.

The mobility problem that Sóller is experiencing is partly due to the deficiency of public transport in Mallorca, which has an impact on a rate of cars per inhabitant much higher than the national and European average (Mallorca: 902 cars/1,000 inhabitants; Balearic Islands: 756 cars/1,000 inhabitants; Spain/EU: around 520 cars/1,000 inhabitants).

Another factor contributing to overcrowding and mobility problems stems from the behaviour of tourists themselves. Tourists often lack awareness of local realities and are unwilling to adapt their behaviour; they tend to exhibit impatience and high expectations, desiring instant access to everything.

Additionally, there is a lack of effectiveness on the part of local and regional administrations in monitoring and managing tourist flows. Although there have been initiatives to develop apps aimed at helping tourists make the most of the island's resources while avoiding overcrowding, such solutions have yet to yield significant results and remain under development (e.g., Palma App).

The Sóller City Council initiated a project to install traffic information screens at the main entrances to the municipality, aiming to indicate the level of congestion in parking lots and roads. However, despite the physical implementation of the screens, the system never functioned properly.

2.2 GROUP 2: AGRICULTURE AND CULTURE

On the topic of agriculture, the following challenges and barriers have been identified:

- The ageing of farmers and the lack of generational renewal pose pressing challenges. Currently, the average age of farmers in Sóller is over 60 years old. Within 5 years, the vast majority of local farmers will be retired, with no one to replace them.
- Due to the topography of Sóller, many agricultural plots are of small dimensions and are not classified as production areas but as 'urban gardens.' As a consequence, these farmers cannot be considered professionals in the sector, are ineligible for subsidies, and cannot legally sell their products. This reality hampers the promotion of agriculture among young people, as the few who engage in it must also pursue other parallel occupations (often as gardeners for foreigners with second homes on the island). Furthermore, it exacerbates the prevalence of an underground economy (with a significant amount of work conducted off the books).
- Given the extensive subdivision of agricultural plots in the municipality, the Agricultural Cooperative of Sóller plays a crucial role in supporting local agriculture. However, the cooperative itself lacks the resources to adequately supply and prepare for each season.
- With climate change, the shortage and scarcity of water have become particularly concerning issues directly impacting the quality, productivity, and profitability of crops.
- In order to adequately supply local products to all individuals within the municipality (both residents and tourists), it's essential for the Agricultural Cooperative of Sóller to have forecasts and estimations (cross-referenced with real-time data) of the population capacity in Sóller. This allows for advance orders of oranges and other local products from farmers, ensuring better service delivery.

At a cultural level, the following challenges and barriers have been mentioned:

- There is a lack of centralized cultural information. Within the municipality itself, there are several websites, platforms, calendars, and cultural agendas. However, the information is not cross-referenced or integrated; it is scattered. This results in some cultural sites in the municipality lacking visitors (e.g., museums of Sóller, botanical garden), while others experience overcrowding and tourist saturation (e.g., Sóller railway/train).
- Even the local population scarcely visits the museums of the municipality, and outside of the high season, these museums receive minimal foot traffic.
- Furthermore, there are not many workshops being organized apart from a few regular ones such as those organized by the Agriculture Cooperative of Sóller during the orange or olive seasons. There is potential to increase and distribute the number of workshops and socio-cultural activities throughout the year.

3 DESIRED SOLUTIONS/SCENARIOS

3.1 DATA & TOURISM

- Implement an integrated and more automated system/tool for collecting and monitoring tourist data in Sóller (to obtain standardized and disaggregated data).
- Implement training programs or courses for companies and other local actors on data and technologies.
- To be able to understand more precisely how tourists 'consume' the destination of Sóller (what they visit, what they buy, who, when, how...).
- Implement more personalized activities, particularly activities for children (children's activities are the primary demand of tourists since tourism in Sóller is family-oriented). There are two main types of tourists in Sóller: (i) those who spend their entire vacation in the municipality in one of the hotels or vacation rentals; (ii) tourists who only come for the day. Day-trip tourists request locker services to store their bags/backpacks while they enjoy the beach.

3.2 MOBILITY

- Having a system in place to predict traffic congestion and parking saturation in advance within the municipality. This system should be integrated with an app for tourists, allowing them to adjust their travels accordingly to avoid traffic jams and queues (it can also be linked with the currently unused traffic information screen system).
- At the same time, there is a need to provide more information to tourists about the reality of tourism in Sóller/Mallorca, so that they can adjust their behaviour and enjoy their stay without exacerbating the existing overcrowding issues.
- From the authorities and public administrations, there is a need to learn to better manage overcrowding and to have more data and information to efficiently redirect the flow of tourists throughout the territory.

3.3 AGRICULTURE

- Implement training courses and workshops to provide guidance to smallholders and urban garden owners on improving orchard/garden management practices and effectively commercialize their products. These would be courses on 'farming for non-farmers', aimed at individuals who tend to a garden in a non-professional and/or recreational capacity. Topics covered would include how to maximize yield from the garden, identifying tasks suitable for amateurs versus those best left to professionals, common plant diseases during summer and winter seasons, and more.
- Cross-referencing data from the few farmers engaged in direct sales and sales of organic products, and creating a website that maps active farmers in Sóller.
- Propose creating a list of urban gardens and entrusting them to young farmers. The idea is to reverse the significant fragmentation of the plots by combining as many

gardens as necessary to obtain the required square meters to convert them into an official production field eligible for subsidies and assistance. Alternatively, propose a change in regulations specifically for the Valley of Söller.

- Ensuring better integration of data between supply and demand, with this information accessible in a visual and user-friendly manner through an app or platform. This allows both farmers and the cooperative to better anticipate the demand for local products.
- For addressing the issue of water scarcity, it is crucial to have more data on the availability and usage of water in the municipality. Particularly, there is a need to conduct studies to understand firsthand how much water currently enters Söller from its various sources. Through sensors, it would be possible to monitor the rate at which different water reserves located in the municipality (such as wells, *s'afareig*, etc.) are being filled.

3.4 CULTURE

- Implement a 'cultural package' that includes access to the train, railway, and museums in Söller. There is already a successful package combining the train, railway, and a boat trip to Sa Calobra, which is very popular among tourists. This cultural package would build on the 'art train' initiative, using the train to transport visitors to various museums and cultural sites in the municipality (Can Prunera, Casal de Cultura, Balearic Museum of Natural Sciences, Botanical Garden, Museum of the Sea, etc.). This package would provide good alternatives for tourists on rainy days and help diversify the tourist offer, making it more comprehensive and sustainable (reducing car traffic within the municipality).
- Develop agreements between museums and local schools to organize visits and promote the museums among the local population.
- It is essential to create a website or an app that integrates and centralizes all tourist, leisure, and cultural offerings for both tourists and residents. This system should provide real-time information to offer personalized recommendations to users (based on their profile, availability, weather, etc.). In addition to socio-cultural offerings, this system could provide information on the condition of the beaches, where to buy local products, and places to visit.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The workshop highlighted several issues facing the municipality, caused by mass tourism, the lack of digitalization, data sharing, knowledge, and cooperation among local entities and actors.

Despite the relatively low participation in the workshop, the event was considered a success as it managed to bring together representatives from all the main sectors of the municipality. In particular, it is worth noting the participation of some representatives of the primary sector (farmers), who are usually reluctant to participate in this type of event.

The workshop made it possible to identify specific problems as well as possible solutions. It should be noted that in all the topics dealt with by the 2 working groups (tourism/mobility and agriculture/culture), the types of problems and solutions were very similar:

- Lack of data to improve decision-making and/or to be able to develop new products/services. Need for sensor deployment.
- Need for training of local actors on digitalization, technologies and innovation issues.
- Need for integrated systems, both for the collection and analysis of data (tourism, mobility), and for the marketing and promotion of products and services (agriculture, culture).
- Need for public policies and services adapted to the reality of Sóller (control of vacation rentals, classification of urban orchards/gardens, management of the flow of tourists and mobility within the municipality...).
- An intangible point that was mentioned on multiple occasions during the workshop, although it was not highlighted either as a problem or as solutions, is the need to better inform tourists about the reality of the tourist destination of Sóller, in order to influence their behaviour and improve coexistence with residents. Therefore, communication and awareness-raising campaigns are still very necessary.

Thus, the results of this workshop contribute to defining the main lines of action of the pilot of the SMART ERA project in the Valley of Sóller:

- Encourage cooperation and data sharing among local actors.
- Provide training and improve the competencies of local actors in digitalization.
- Carry out a technological deployment (sensors, platforms, apps, dashboards, digital services, etc.).
- Develop policy recommendations.
- Implement communication and dissemination activities and events for residents and tourists.

Annex B3 – Statistics of Sóller

	UNIT	VALUE (YEAR*) *If no information for 2023 is available, use the most recent value and indicate the year	Value for comparison (Historical data, national-wide values or similar)	Source
TERRITORY				
Surface	In km ²	Municipality of Sóller: 42,8 km² The municipality of Sóller has four main nuclei: Sóller, Port de Sóller, L’Horta and Biniaraix (data from 2015)	0,86 % of the total surface of the Balearic Islands and 1,17% of the surface of Mallorca.	Ibestat
POPULATION				
Population size	Number of inhabitants	13.454 (2022) Population distribution: Sóller (67 %) , Port de Sóller (18 %), L’Horta (12 %) and Biniaraix (3 %) population decreased by 5% since 2012 (14.150 inhabitants) but has risen by around 1,1 % since 2002 (12.118) due to a higher percentage of foreigners moving to Sóller from 2008 until 2013 (from 13% in 2002 to around 20%). In 2013 Sóllers population reached its highest number yet, counting 14.229 inhabitants.	Mallorca: 876.147 (2022)	Ibestat
Population density	Number of inhabitants/km ²	315 / km ² (2022)	330 / km ² (Sóller, 2012) Average Mallorca (2022): 252 / km²	Ibestat
Age Average		44,62 (2022)	Average Mallorca (2022): 42,11	Ibestat
Age distribution	Percentage or count within each age group,	0-15: 14% 15-65: 65% >64: 21% (2022)	Average Mallorca (2022): 0-15: 16% 15-65: 67% >64: 17%	Ibestat
Dependency ratio	(Number of people < 16 + Number of people > 64 / Number of people 16-64)*100	55% (2022)	49,5% (2012)	Ibestat
Longevity Index		0,18	0,15 for Mallorca	Ibestat

Gender distribution	Percentage or count of female/male	49,5 % (male) 50,5 % (female) (2022)	50 % (male) 50 % (female) (2012)	lbestat
Birth rate	(Number of live births / Total population) * 1,000	= (94/13.454)*1.000 = 7 (2022)	= (105/14.150)*1.000 = 7,4 (2012)	lbestat
Mortality rate	Number of Deaths recorded in one year*1.000 inhabitants	= (140/13.454)*1.000 = 10,4 (2022)	= (116/14.150)*1.000 = 8,2 (2012)	lbestat
Spanish nationality/Other Nationality	In % of total population	Spanish: 82% Other Nationalities: 18% (2022) From the 18% <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 6,4 % are from UE-15 countries ▪ 3,2 % from South America ▪ 3 % from Europe (but not UE) ▪ 2 % from Africa ▪ 2 % from other UE countries ▪ 1,4 % from the rest of America or others 	Spanish: 80% Other Nationalities: 20% (2012) Spanish: 86% Other Nationalities: 14% (2002) Spanish: 90% Other Nationalities: 10% (1998)	lbestat
ECONOMY				
Gross disposable income of households per capita.		17.227 € (2021)	Mallorca: 16.615 € (2021) Sóller: 14.817 € (2012) raised 16 % (from 2012 until 2021)	lbestat
Main sources of income from household disposable income.		Compensation of employees (incl. salaries, wages, allowances, and other forms of remuneration): 38,2 % Mixed Income/Gross operating surplus: 30,5 % Social benefits: 19,9 % Other current transfers: 7,9 % Property income: 3,4 % Total in thousands of €: 347.431		lbestat
Registered companies (Total)		n/a		
Registered companies - Gastronomy	Nº	Date: 31.5.2024, Municipality of Sóller 192 in total: 28 bar-cafeteria 40 bars 24 cafeterias 100 restaurants	10.314 (Balearic Islands)	Open data catalog of the Balearic Government

		max. capacity 10.721 guests		
Unemployment		<p>Unemployed with benefits: 141 (M7 2023) 208 (M12 2023)</p> <p>192, 1,4% (M7 2022, % calculated with the population value from 2022) 233, 1,7% (M12 2022, % calculated with the population value from 2022)</p> <p>Unemployed without benefits: 359, 2,7% (M7 2022, % calculated with the population value from 2022) 1.540, 1,1% (M12 2022, % calculated with the population value from 2022)</p> <p>In general: 55+ is the group with highest unemployment rates (around 30%) 16-24 is the group with the lowest unemployment rates (around 10%). Men and women are in general balanced.</p>	<p>Unemployed with benefits: 321 (M7 2023) 1.598 (M12 2023)</p> <p>544, 3,8% (M7 2012, % calculated with the population value from 2012) 765, 5,4% (M12 2012, % calculated with the population value from 2012)</p> <p>Unemployed without benefits: 745, 5,2% (M7 2012, % calculated with the population value from 2012) 1.580, 11,1% (M12 2012, % calculated with the population value from 2012)</p>	lbestat
TOURISM				
Tourist accommodation	Nº	<p>Municipality of Sóller (2024): 12 Agrotourism Accommodations 1 Hostel 2 Tourist apartments 1 Guesthouse 2 1-star Boarding houses 1 2-star Boarding house 1 1-star hotel 2 2-star hotels 1 3-star hotel 8 4-star hotels 3 4-star hotels Superior 1 5-star hotel 1 5-star hotel (Great luxury) 1 4-star apartment hotel 25 of the subgroup “Inland Tourism”</p> <p>A total of 1.547 rooms and 3.159 beds 19 Tourist accommodations in Port de Sóller, 42 in Sóller and 1 in Biniaraix (Total: 62)</p>		Open data catalog of the Balearic Government
Tourist Housing (Estancias turísticas en viviendas (ETV))	Nº	<p>Date: 3.6.2024, Municipality of Sóller 623 houses (uni- or plurifamiliar): 58% Sóller 33% Port de Sóller 9% Other Areas of the Valley 3.313 beds in 1.761 units</p>		Open data catalog of the Balearic Government

Official Tourist Guides (Normal “Active Tourism”)	Nº	Date: 3.6.2024, Municipality of Sóller 25 + 7		Open data catalog of the Balearic Government
Travel Agencies	Nº	Date: 3.6.2024, Municipality of Sóller 3		Open data catalog of the Balearic Government
Reservation Agencies (rental of vacation homes)	Nº	Date: 3.6.2024, Municipality of Sóller 7		Open data catalog of the Balearic Government
Car rentals	Nº	4 Car rental companies	Balearic Islands: 189	Open data catalog of the Balearic Government
Tourists arrived to <u>Mallorca</u>	Nº	2022: 11.474.345 tourists* Around 1/3 were german. And around 1/5 were english. *at least one night stay		AETIB (Agencia d’estratègia turística a illes balears)
MOBILITY				
No open data		In the process of data collection from different sources (TIB, Historical train Sóller, Municipality)		
AGRICULTURE (basados en agricultural census 2020), Source: National Institute of statistics, Spain (Censo Agrario 2020 (ine.es))				
Number of exploitations (total)	Nº	169 2 % of all farms of Mallorca	Mallorca: 7.928	
Cultivated land (total)	ha	668,86 0,5% of the cultivated surface of Mallorca	Mallorca: 128.946	
Average farm size	ha	4	Mallorca: 16	
Arable land	Nº of farms, ha	30, 28,37 18% of the farms in Sóller cultivate 28,34 hectares of arable land, which accounts for 4,3 % of the total of cultivated land.	Mallorca: 5.364, 76.224,03	

Woody crops	Nº of farms, ha	164, 595 97% of the farms in Sóller cultivate 595 hectares of woody crops, which accounts for 89% of the total cultivated land.	Mallorca: 6.571, 42.672,03	
Permanent grassland	Nº of farms, ha	21, 43,35 12,4 % of the farms in Sóller cultivate 43,35 hectares of permanent grassland, which accounts for 6,5% of the total cultivated land.	Mallorca: 2.059, 9.803,08	
Kitchen gardens personal use	Nº of gardens	40, 1,14 24% of the farms in Sóller cultivate a kitchen garden for personal use. The area is 1,14 hectares, which represents 0.2% of the total cultivated land.	Mallorca: 149, 206	
Farms with livestock	Nº of farms, Nº of individuals	47, 1.175 Around one quarter of all farms in Sóller have livestock.	Mallorca: 3.857, 595.902	
Sheep/Goats	Nº of farms, Nº of individuals	39, 1.003 23 % of all farms in Sóller	Mallorca: 2.454, 267.787	
Pigs	Nº of farms, Nº of individuals	3, 13 1,7 % of all farms in Sóller	Mallorca: 938, 77.074	
Poultry	Nº of farms, Nº of individuals	5, 159 3 % of all farms in Sóller	Mallorca: 264, 242.318	
Bovine	Nº of farms, Nº of individuals	0, 0	Mallorca: 201, 8.723	
Farm manager		170	Mallorca: 7.980, 63	
Gender distribution		124 men (73 %) 46 women (27 %)	Mallorca: 5.907 men (74%) 2.073 women (26%)	
Average age		65 men: 64 women: 67	Mallorca: 64 men: 63 women: 65	
Age distribution		< 25: 1% 25-34: 2% 35-44: 4 % 45-54: 15 % 55-64: 26 % > 65: 52 % Close to 80% of the farm managers are older than 55, 52% older than 65	Mallorca: < 25: 0,5 % 25-34: 3 % 35-44: 8 % 45-54: 17 % 55-64: 23 % > 65: 48 %	

		and not even 10% are younger than 44.		
Education of the farm manager		81,8 % agricultural experience exclusively 15,9 % agricultural training courses 0,6 % agricultural vocational training 1,8 % university and/or higher agricultural studies	Mallorca: 73,6 % 21,3 % 2,2 % 2,9 %	
Organic certified farms	Nº	8 Vegetables, Olives, Citrics, pistachio and other fruits (2024)		

Annex B4 – Datasets available in Sóller

Kind of Data	Data Owner	Sensitivity	Access Model	Short Description	Purpose of usage	Data format	Average size of the data item	Volume of data	Frequency of acquisition
Mallorca Tourist Accommodations	Council of Mallorca - Insular Directorate of Transition and Tourist Planning	Public	Web site , no fee	Data set of tourist accommodation registered on the island of Mallorca. Includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name • Subgroup (e.g. agrotourism, camping, apartment) • Stars category • Date of first activity • Status (Open-Closed) • Municipality and village • Address • UTM and coordinates • Max. capacity • N° of rooms • Beneficiary 	Mapping of tourist accommodations in Sóller/Tra muntana.	Download formats: csv, rdf, rss, xml, csv/tsv for excel, KML, KMZ, GEOJson Access-API (limited to 1.000 rows): csv, JSON, GeoJSON	depends on filter	depends on filter	daily
Mallorca Tourist Housing	Council of Mallorca - Insular Directorate of Transition and Tourist Planning		Web site , no fee	Data set of tourist housing registered on the island of Mallorca. Includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name • Subgroup • Date of first activity • Status (Open-Closed) • Municipality and village 	Mapping of tourist housing in Sóller/Tra muntana.	Download formats: csv, rdf, rss, xml, csv/tsv for excel, KML, KMZ, GEOJson Access-API (limited to 1.000 rows): csv, JSON, GeoJSON	depends on filter	depends on filter	daily

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Address • UTM and coordinates • Season length in month • Type of housing • N° of rooms and bathrooms • Beneficiary 					
Mallorca Tourist Centers	Council of Mallorca - Insular Directorate of Transition and Tourist Planning	Public	Web site , no fee	<p>Dataset of registered tourist centers on the island of Mallorca. Includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name • Subgroup (e.g. culture, sports, wellness, complementary) • Date of first activity • Status (Open-Closed) • Municipality and village • Address • UTM and coordinates • Service description • Website • Beneficiary 	Mapping of tourist centers in Sóller/Tra muntana.	<p>Download formats:</p> <p>csv, rdf, rss, xml, csv/tsv for excel, KML, KMZ, GEOJson</p> <p>Access-API (limited to 1.000 rows):</p> <p>csv, JSON, GeoJSON</p>	depends on filter	depends on filter	daily
Mallorca Gastronomy and Entertainment	Council of Mallorca - Insular Directorate of Transition and Tourist Planning	Public	Web site , no fee	<p>Dataset of registered tourist centers on the island of Mallorca. Includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name • Subgroup (e.g. Bar, 	Mapping of gastronomy and entertainment possibilities in	<p>Download formats:</p> <p>csv, rdf, rss, xml, csv/tsv for excel, KML, KMZ, GEOJson</p>	depends on filter	depends on filter	daily

				<p>Cafeteria, Restaurant, boat-restaurant ,...)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Date of first activity • Status (Open-Closed) • Municipality and village • Address • UTM and coordinates • Opening hours • Pick up points for activities • Capacity • Beneficiary 	Sóller/Tramuntana.	<p>Access-API (limited to 1.000 rows):</p> <p>csv, JSON, GeoJSON</p>			
Mallorca Car Rental	Council of Mallorca - Insular Directorate of Transition and Tourist Planning	Public	Web site , no fee	<p>Dataset of driverless vehicle rental companies registered on the island of Mallorca.</p> <p>Includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name of the company • Municipality • Address • N° of vehicles • Beneficiary with NIF/CIF 	Mapping of car rental possibilities in Sóller/Tramuntana but also Mallorca	<p>Download formats:</p> <p>csv, rdf, rss, xml, csv/tsv for excel</p> <p>Access-API (limited to 1.000 rows):</p> <p>csv, JSON</p>	depends on filter	depends on filter	This dataset contains information up to the year 2021.
Mallorca Tourist Guides	Council of Mallorca - Insular Directorate of Transition and Tourist Planning	Public	Web site , no fee	<p>Dataset of people qualified to exercise the activity of tourist guide in the Balearic Islands.</p> <p>Includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name of the guide • Start of activity 	Mapping of tourist guides in Sóller/Tramuntana	<p>Download formats:</p> <p>csv, rdf, rss, xml, csv/tsv for excel</p> <p>Access-API (limited to 1.000 rows):</p> <p>csv, JSON</p>	depends on filter	depends on filter	daily

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Status (Active, not active) • Languages spoken 					
Mallorca “Active Tourism” companies	Council of Mallorca - Insular Directorate of Transition and Tourist Planning	Public	Web site , no fee	<p>Dataset of the companies that carry out recreational, sports and adventure activities registered on the island of Mallorca. Includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name of the establishment • Date of first activity • Status (Open-Closed) • Municipality • Address • UTM and coordinates • Website • Service description • Beneficiary 	Mapping of “active” tourism activities in Sóller/Tramuntana	<p>Download formats:</p> <p>csv, rdf, rss, xml, csv/tsv for excel, KML, KMZ, GEOJson</p> <p>Access-API (limited to 1.000 rows):</p> <p>csv, JSON, GeoJSON</p>	depends on filter	depends on filter	daily
Tourist Intermediation Companies Mallorca	Council of Mallorca - Insular Directorate of Transition and Tourist Planning	Public	Web site , no fee	<p>Dataset of travel agencies, tourist mediators and reservation centers on the island of Mallorca. Includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name of the establishment • Subgroup (Travel agency, Reservation hotlines, etc.) 	Mapping of tourist intermediation companies in Sóller/Tramuntana	<p>Download formats:</p> <p>csv, rdf, rss, xml, csv/tsv for excel, KML, KMZ, GEOJson</p> <p>Access-API (limited to 1.000 rows):</p> <p>csv, JSON, GeoJSON</p>	depends on filter	depends on filter	not sure, last update: 23.2.2023

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Date of first activity • Status (Open-Closed) • Municipality • Address or virtual • UTM and coordinates • Website • Service description • Beneficiary 					
tib (transporte islas baleares) - Public transport			Mapa interactivo de paradas - CTM (tib.org)		Mapping real-time data concerning schedules				
Air Quality in Sóller	Sóller per l'Aire	Public	Sensor data Solle r_per lAire		Real-time and historical sensor data concerning potential air pollution caused by burning of garden waste, traffic and chimneys				

ANNEXES C - P3 NORTHERN OSTROBOTHNIA

- Annex C1. Socioeconomic and demographic data of P3
- Annex C2. Data available in P3

Annex C1 – Socio-economic and demographic data of P3

	UNIT	VALUE (YEAR*, SOURCE) *If no information for 2023 is available, use the most recent value and indicate the year	Value for comparison? Scale over the years/time periods? National-wide?																									
TERRITORY																												
Surface	In km ²	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Land</th> <th>Fresh water</th> <th>Seawater</th> <th>Total</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Alavieska</td> <td>251.5</td> <td>1.52</td> <td>0</td> <td>253.1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Kalajoki</td> <td>924.1</td> <td>6.9</td> <td>1460.3</td> <td>2391.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Nivala</td> <td>527.3</td> <td>9.1</td> <td>0</td> <td>536.4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total</td> <td>1702.9</td> <td>17.5</td> <td>1460.3</td> <td>3180.7</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Source: Surface area by municipality, National Land Survey of Finland 2024 https://www.maanmittauslaitos.fi/sites/maanmittauslaitos.fi/files/attachments/2024/01/Vuoden_2024_pinta-alatilasto_kunnat_maakunnat.xlsx</p>		Land	Fresh water	Seawater	Total	Alavieska	251.5	1.52	0	253.1	Kalajoki	924.1	6.9	1460.3	2391.3	Nivala	527.3	9.1	0	536.4	Total	1702.9	17.5	1460.3	3180.7	
	Land	Fresh water	Seawater	Total																								
Alavieska	251.5	1.52	0	253.1																								
Kalajoki	924.1	6.9	1460.3	2391.3																								
Nivala	527.3	9.1	0	536.4																								
Total	1702.9	17.5	1460.3	3180.7																								
POPULATION																												
Population size	Number of inhabitants	<p>Alavieska 2437 Kalajoki 12372 Nivala 10454 Total 25263</p> <p>Source: Population figures by region, Statistics Finland https://pxdata.stat.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/fi/StatFin/StatFin_vaerak/statfin_vaerak_pxt_11ra.px/</p>	<p>Population change 2022-2023</p> <p>Alavieska -1.8 % Kalajoki -0.6 % Nivala 0.2 % Finland 0.3 %</p>																									
Population density	Number of inhabitants/km ²	<p>Alavieska 9.7 Kalajoki 13.4 Nivala 19.8 Total 14.8</p> <p>Source: Calculated from sources above</p>	Finland 18,4																									
Age Average	Total Age of inhabitants/ Number of inhabitants	<p>Alavieska 44.8 Kalajoki 45.3 Nivala 41.5 Total N/A</p> <p>Source: Population figures by region, Statistics Finland https://pxdata.stat.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/fi/StatFin/StatFin__vaerak/statfin_vaerak_pxt_11ra.px/</p>	Finland 43.8																									
Age distribution	Percentage or count within each age group, e.g. <16, 16-64, >64	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>0-14 years %</th> <th>15-64 years %</th> <th>65+ years %</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Alavieska</td> <td>18.3</td> <td>54.9</td> <td>26.9</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Kalajoki</td> <td>17.2</td> <td>55.2</td> <td>27.6</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Nivala</td> <td>21.3</td> <td>54.7</td> <td>24.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total</td> <td>N/A</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Source: Population figures by region, Statistics Finland https://pxdata.stat.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/fi/StatFin/StatFin_vaerak/statfin_vaerak_pxt_11ra.px/</p>		0-14 years %	15-64 years %	65+ years %	Alavieska	18.3	54.9	26.9	Kalajoki	17.2	55.2	27.6	Nivala	21.3	54.7	24.0	Total	N/A			Finland 14.9 / 61.8 / 23.4					
	0-14 years %	15-64 years %	65+ years %																									
Alavieska	18.3	54.9	26.9																									
Kalajoki	17.2	55.2	27.6																									
Nivala	21.3	54.7	24.0																									
Total	N/A																											

Dependancy ratio	(Number of people < 16 + Number of people > 64 / Number of people 16-64)*100	Alavieska 82.3 Kalajoki 81.1 Nivala 82.8 Total N/A Source: Population figures by region, Statistics Finland https://pxdata.stat.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/fi/StatFin/StatFin_vaerak/statfin_vaerak_pxt_11ra.px/																					
Gender distribution	Percentage or count of female/male (diverse)	<table> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Female %</th> <th>Male %</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Alavieska</td> <td>47.2</td> <td>52.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Kalajoki</td> <td>49.6</td> <td>50.4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Nivala</td> <td>48.9</td> <td>51.1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total</td> <td>49.3</td> <td>50.7</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> Source: Citizenship by gender and municipality, Statistics Finland https://pxdata.stat.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/fi/StatFin/StatFin_vaerak/statfin_vaerak_pxt_11rh.px/		Female %	Male %	Alavieska	47.2	52.8	Kalajoki	49.6	50.4	Nivala	48.9	51.1	Total	49.3	50.7						
	Female %	Male %																					
Alavieska	47.2	52.8																					
Kalajoki	49.6	50.4																					
Nivala	48.9	51.1																					
Total	49.3	50.7																					
Birth rate	Number of births recorded in one year/1.000 inhabitants	Alavieska 8.2 Kalajoki 9.0 Nivala 10.1 Total 9.4 Source: 2022 Population changes and population by region, Statistics Finland https://pxdata.stat.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/fi/StatFin/StatFin_ssaaty/statfin_ssaaty_pxt_121w.px/																					
Mortality rate	Number of Deaths recorded in one year/1.000 inhabitants	Alavieska 12.3 Kalajoki 12.8 Nivala 10.6 Total 11.8 Source: 2022 Population changes and population by region, Statistics Finland https://pxdata.stat.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/fi/StatFin/StatFin_ssaaty/statfin_ssaaty_pxt_121w.px/																					
Rate of natural increase (RNI) per 1.000 inhabitants	(Live Births-Deaths/Inhabitants) /1.000	Alavieska -4.1 Kalajoki -3.8 Nivala -0.5 Total -2.5 Source: 2022 Population changes and population by region, Statistics Finland https://pxdata.stat.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/fi/StatFin/StatFin_ssaaty/statfin_ssaaty_pxt_121w.px/																					
Nationalities	In % of total population	<table> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Finnish %</th> <th>European %</th> <th>Outside europe %</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Alavieska</td> <td>98.2</td> <td>1.8</td> <td>1.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Kalajoki</td> <td>96.7</td> <td>3.3</td> <td>2.7</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Nivala</td> <td>98.8</td> <td>1.2</td> <td>1.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total</td> <td>97.7</td> <td>2.3</td> <td>1.9</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> Source: Citizenship by gender and municipality, 1990-2023, Statistics Finland https://pxdata.stat.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/fi/StatFin/StatFin_vaerak/statfin_vaerak_pxt_11rh.px/		Finnish %	European %	Outside europe %	Alavieska	98.2	1.8	1.5	Kalajoki	96.7	3.3	2.7	Nivala	98.8	1.2	1.0	Total	97.7	2.3	1.9	
	Finnish %	European %	Outside europe %																				
Alavieska	98.2	1.8	1.5																				
Kalajoki	96.7	3.3	2.7																				
Nivala	98.8	1.2	1.0																				
Total	97.7	2.3	1.9																				

Immigration/Emigration	Registrations and deregistrations in the register due to change of municipality of residence	Intermunicipal In-migration / Intermunicipal out-migration / Immigration / Emigration / Net migration Alavieska 137 / 172 / 3 / 2 / -34 Kalajoki 475 555 58 7 / -29 Nivala 403 / 405 / 25 / 5 / 18 Total 1015 / 1132 / 86 / 14 / -45 Source: 2022 Population changes and population by region, Statistics Finland https://pxdata.stat.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/fi/StatFin/StatFin_ssaaty/statfin_ssaaty_pxt_121w.px/																					
Marital status distribution	Percentage or count of single, married, divorced, etc.	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Single %</th> <th>Married %</th> <th>Divorced %</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Alavieska</td> <td>48.4</td> <td>37.6</td> <td>7.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Kalajoki</td> <td>45.5</td> <td>40.5</td> <td>8.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Nivala</td> <td>51.7</td> <td>35.4</td> <td>7.9</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total</td> <td>48.4</td> <td>38.1</td> <td>8.1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Source: Marital status by age, language and gender, by region, Statistics Finland https://pxdata.stat.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/fi/StatFin/StatFin_vaerak/statfin_vaerak_pxt_11rz.px/</p>		Single %	Married %	Divorced %	Alavieska	48.4	37.6	7.8	Kalajoki	45.5	40.5	8.3	Nivala	51.7	35.4	7.9	Total	48.4	38.1	8.1	
	Single %	Married %	Divorced %																				
Alavieska	48.4	37.6	7.8																				
Kalajoki	45.5	40.5	8.3																				
Nivala	51.7	35.4	7.9																				
Total	48.4	38.1	8.1																				
ECONOMY																							
Gross domestic product (GDP) per capita	€/inhabitant	Nivala-Haapajärvi sub-region 32 314.2 (includes Nivala) Ylivieska sub-region 36 155.9 (includes Alavieska and Kalajoki) Source: 2021 Gross domestic product per capita by region, by year as variables Region, Year and Data, Statistics Finland https://pxdata.stat.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/fi/StatFin/StatFin_altp/statfin_altp_pxt_12bc.px/																					
Gross disposable income per household	€/household	Alavieska 44657 Kalajoki 45308 Nivala 43550 Total N/A Source: 2022 Income and income structure of household-dwelling units by region, 1995-2022, Statistics Finland https://pxdata.stat.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/en/StatFin/StatFin_tjt/statfin_tjt_pxt_118w.px/																					
Primary sources of income from household disposable income		Earned income / Entrepreneurial income / Property income / Current transfers Alavieska 30261 / 5137 / 6161 / 15883 Kalajoki 31036 / 4293 / 6032 / 16833 Nivala 31877 / 4248 / 4084 / 15916 Source: 2022 Income and income structure of household-dwelling units by region, 1995-2022, Statistics Finland https://pxdata.stat.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/en/StatFin/StatFin_tjt/statfin_tjt_pxt_118w.px/																					
Registered companies (Total)		Alavieska 348 Kalajoki 1632 Nivala 1171 Source: 2022 Microenterprise Statistics, MY Tilastot, University of Oulu, Kerttu Saalasti Institute., Data Statistics Finland https://www.oulu.fi/my_tilastot/2024/avainluvut.html																					

Registered companies (Sector of activity)		<p>Industry % (Northern Ostrobothnia in total)</p> <p>A Agriculture, forestry and fishing 30.8</p> <p>B Mining and quarrying 0.5</p> <p>C Manufacturing 5.1</p> <p>D Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply 0.4</p> <p>E Water supply; sewerage, waste management and remediation activities 0.5</p> <p>F Construction 9.6</p> <p>G Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles 9.0</p> <p>H Transportation and storage 4.2</p> <p>I Accommodation and food service activities 2.6</p> <p>J Information and communication 3.0</p> <p>K Financial and insurance activities 2.0</p> <p>L Real estate activities 4,5</p> <p>M Professional, scientific and technical activities 9.8</p> <p>N Administrative and support service activities 3.3</p> <p>P Education 1.5</p> <p>Q Human health and social work activities 5.6</p> <p>R Arts, entertainment and recreation 2.6</p> <p>S Other service activities 5.1</p> <p>Source: Data available from FIRM_ENTER micro data of Statistics Finland licensed to research use for University of Oulu. Analysis, University of Oulu. Can be updated potentially to municipal level.</p> <p>https://stat.fi/media/uploads/tup/mikroaineistot_2019.pdf</p>																					
Employment status and occupation types (%)		<p>Primary p. A, Sec. prod. B-F, Services G-U, Unknown</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Alavieska</td> <td>23.8</td> <td>22.9</td> <td>52.7</td> <td>0.6</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Kalajoki</td> <td>11.2</td> <td>32.9</td> <td>54.6</td> <td>1.2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Nivala</td> <td>11.8</td> <td>34.6</td> <td>52.5</td> <td>1.1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total</td> <td>12.4</td> <td>32.9</td> <td>53.6</td> <td>1.1</td> </tr> </table> <p>Source: 2022 Income and income structure of household-dwelling units by region, 1995-2022, Statistics Finland</p> <p>https://pxdata.stat.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/en/StatFin/StatFin_tyokay/statfin_tyokay_pxt_115h.px/</p>	Alavieska	23.8	22.9	52.7	0.6	Kalajoki	11.2	32.9	54.6	1.2	Nivala	11.8	34.6	52.5	1.1	Total	12.4	32.9	53.6	1.1	
Alavieska	23.8	22.9	52.7	0.6																			
Kalajoki	11.2	32.9	54.6	1.2																			
Nivala	11.8	34.6	52.5	1.1																			
Total	12.4	32.9	53.6	1.1																			

Annex C2 – Data available in P3

Kind of Data	Data Owner	Sensitivity	Access Model	Short Description	Purpose of usage	Data format	Average size of the data item	Volume of data	Frequency of acquisition
Road network data	Traficom	Public	Open access	Road network data publicly provided by The Finnish Transport and Communications Agency Traficom. Data is available as Esri Shapefile and GeoPackage data dumps https://ava.vaylapilvi.fi/ava/Tie/Digitalroad/Aineistojulkaisut and via WFS interface https://avoinapi.vaylapilvi.fi/vaylatiedot/digitalroad/ows?service=wfs&request=getCapabilities	Road network data with high accuracy and coverage enabling vehicle routing, logistics planning and optimisation as well as location allocation analyses.	WFS interface, Esri Shapefile and GeoPackage		100 MB to 2 GB	Four annual updates
Public transports	Finttraffic	Public	Open access	The route and timetable data of the major public transport authorities, long distance connections and major transport	The route and timetable data enables public transports and multimodal passenger routing to	General Transit Feed Specification GTFS		1 GB	Annual or more frequent

				<p>service operators. Data is collected and shared by Fintraffic. Fintraffic controls and manages traffic on the land, in the air and at sea in Finland.</p> <p>https://developer.matka.fi/pages/en/home.php</p>	<p>analyse, optimise public transports based travels and accessibility.</p>				
Enterprises	Statistics Finland	Public	<p>Fee (e.g. 15 00-1999 enterprises with a fee of 1000 € + VAT)</p>	<p>Business Register of Statistics Finland contains information on all enterprises with a Business ID for which data are available from the Tax Administration. The data includes also private practitioners of trade (i.e. person having a trade name) as well general government and non-profit institutions serving households.</p> <p>https://stat.fi/tup/yritysr</p>	<p>Business register data enables to collect, contact and potentially collaborate with local enterprises.</p>	Spreadsheet		10 MB to 200 MB	Annual

				ekisteri/index_en.html					
Population grid data 1x1 km	Statistics Finland	Public	Open access	Population grid data with 1x1 km resolution. Includes population, number of female and male, population by age (0-14, 15-64, 65- WFS https://geo.stat.fi/geoserver/vaestoruutu/wfs	Population grid cell data with age structure enables to analyse and model customer potential for companies, plan and allocate that reach the people at home and optimise service logistics and transports.	WFS		100 MB	Annual
Second houses		Licensed use, restrictions, not for commercial use	Fee	Number of second houses i.e. summer cottages at spatial data in 1x1 km and 250mx250 m resolutions. https://geoportal.ymparisto.fi/meta/julkisen/dokumentit/YKR_tiedot.pdf	The data can be used to estimate the number and spatial distribution of holiday season populations and rural tourists, and to provide general information on the location of second homes for maintenance.	dBase with coordinates		100 MB	
Mobility	Telia Finland	Licensed use,	Fee	Mobile phone tracking	The data can be used to	csv		1 MB	Daily

	nd Oyj	restrictions due to privacy protection		data by base stations, grid data from 500 m to 32 km depending from	monitor mobility hotspots and population flows in local and regional context at different days, weeks, months as well as more specific moments of time, when proper aggregation levels in time and space (areal units) are used. Data enables to accurately estimate the number and spatial distribution of holiday season populations and rural tourists.				
Enterprise contact details	NIHAK (Nivala), Kalajoki and Alavieska BSOs	Licensed use	Available via mutual collaboration	Local public business support organisations' (BSOs) customer relationship management (CRM) data	CRM data enables to collect, contact and potentially collaborate with local enterprises.	Spreadsheet		1 MB	Monthly

ANNEXES D – P4 EAST HERZEGOVINA

- Annex D1. Survey 1
- Annex D2. Survey 2
- Annex D3. Survey 3
- Annex D4. Survey 4
- Annex D5. Socioeconomic and demographic data of P4

Annex D1 – Survey 1**SURVEY**

of buyers of Slow Food products from Eastern Herzegovina
Digitalization needs of rural areas

1. Gender (circle the answer): M / F

2. How old are you: _____

3. Have you ever bought products from small producers over the Internet (circle the answer)? YES NO

If the answer is YES, through which page: _____

4. Through which online platform would you buy a product from a small producer:

Social networks (Facebook, Instagram...)

Producer's Webshop (online store)

Olx.ba (largest Bosnian online store)

Other _____

5. Do you have any idea how to use the Internet and the so-called smart solutions to help small producers of food?

6. Would you like to know the producers personally and buy from them? (circle the answer) YES NO

7. Which product would you prefer to buy from local/small producers: cheese, kaymak, potatoes, peas, fruit, honey or all of the above? _____

8. How long are you willing to wait for the delivery of a domestic product?

9. Are you ready to pay more for a verified domestic authentic product? (circle the answer) YES / NO

10. Would you visit one of the producers as a tourist and buy a product "on a doorstep"? (circle the answer) YES / NO

11. Do you know any cultural-historical or natural landmarks from the rural areas of Eastern Herzegovina (not from larger cities)? YES NO

If yes, which landmark have you heard of? _____

12. Would you like to visit the sights from the rural areas of Eastern Herzegovina? (circle the answer) YES NO

Thank you for taking your valuable time. By completing this survey, you have helped the development of remote rural areas and rural households.

Sarajevo, _____ 2024

Annex D2 – Survey 2**SURVEY**

of buyers of small producers' products from Eastern Herzegovina

Digitalization needs of rural areas

- For needs of the SMARTERA project –
WP5, T 5.1

1. Gender (circle the answer): M / F

2. How old are you: _____

3. Have you ever bought products from small producers over the Internet (circle the answer)?

YES NO

If the answer is YES, through which page: _____

4. Through which online platform would you buy a product from a small producer:

Social networks (Facebook, Instagram...)

Producer's Webshop (online store)

Olx.ba (largest Bosnian online store)

Other _____

5. Do you have any idea how to use the Internet and the so-called smart solutions to help small producers of food?

6. Would you like to know the producers personally and buy from them? (circle the answer)

YES NO

7. Which product would you prefer to buy from local/small producers: cheese, kaymak, potatoes, peas, fruit, honey or all of the above? _____

8. How long are you willing to wait for the delivery of a domestic product?

9. Are you ready to pay more for a verified domestic authentic product? (circle the answer)
YES / NO

10. Would you visit one of the producers as a tourist and buy a product "on a doorstep"? (circle the answer) YES / NO

11. Do you know any cultural-historical or natural landmarks from the rural areas of Eastern Herzegovina (not from larger cities)? YES NO

If yes, which landmark have you heard of? _____

12. Would you like to visit the sights from the rural areas of Eastern Herzegovina? (circle the answer) YES NO

Thank you for taking your valuable time. By completing this survey, you have helped the development of remote rural areas and rural households.

Annex D3 – Survey 3**QUESTIONNAIRE**

For the purpose of defining the state and development needs of rural tourism in Eastern Herzegovina (WP 5, T 5.1, T5.2)

Project Implementers: Tourist Organization of the Republic of Srpska
and NGO Slow Food Trebinje Herzegovina

- 1. In your opinion, what are the biggest problems in the rural areas of your municipality/city and in Eastern Herzegovina as a whole?**

- 2. What do you think are the biggest challenges for the development of rural tourism in your municipality/city and in Eastern Herzegovina as a whole?**

- 3. Who is most affected by these problems of underdevelopment in rural areas of Eastern Herzegovina?**

- 4. Which sectors are affected by this problem?**

- 5. In your opinion, what actions do you think need to be taken to solve these problems?**

- 6. What do you consider to be the main causes that have led to these problems?**

- 7. Is anything currently being done to overcome these problems?**

- 8. What scenario would you like to see in rural tourism in Eastern Herzegovina in the future?**

- 9. If you were to achieve the desired scenario, how would life change in the rural areas of Eastern Herzegovina?**

- 10. What obstacles do you think we will encounter when starting to address the problems of rural tourism development in your municipality/city?**

- 11. Which resources that you currently have could help us in solving the problems?**

- 12. Where do you see the greatest opportunities for solving the problems?**

13. What do you think are the biggest obstacles (challenges) we need to overcome to solve these problems?

14. Your other suggestions regarding rural development?

Annex D4 – Survey 4**QUESTIONNAIRE**

for the purpose of defining the state and development needs of rural tourism in Eastern Herzegovina (WP 5, T 5.1, T5.2)

**Project Implementers: Tourist Organization of the Republic of Srpska
and NGO Slow Food Trebinje Herzegovina**

- 1. In your opinion, what are the biggest problems in the rural areas of your municipality/city and in Eastern Herzegovina as a whole?**
- 2. Do you think rural tourism has potential in Eastern Herzegovina?**
- 3. Would it be useful for you if you could sell local products to tourists?**
- 4. Have you ever received any training on providing services in rural tourism?**
- 5. Have you ever had tourists visit your farm/home?**
- 6. Are you interested in offering rural tourism services on your farm/home (accommodation, food, farm activities)?**
- 7. In your opinion, what would help retain young people in the village?**
- 8. How often do you use digital technologies (apps, Google search, GPS)?**
- 9. Do you use social media (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter-X, TikTok, etc.)? For what purposes?**
- 10. Do you sell your products online?**
- 11. Do you have any ideas, suggestions, or recommendations that could help improve life in the village?**

Annex D5 – Socioeconomic and demographic data of P4

DATA	Trebinje	Nevesinje	Gacko	Bileća	Berkovići	Kalinovik	Ljubinje	Istočni Mostar	Total/Average	Percentage
Surface	854.5	877.08	735.88	632.33	249.69	681.15	319.07	85.24	4434.94	
Population (total)	28239	12542	8710	10607	2041	1962	3319	244	67664	6.04015582
Population density (st/km2)	33.0474	14.29972	11.83617	16.774469	8.1741359	2.880422814	10.402106	2.862506	15.2570272	
Male population	13760	6236	4423	5346	1032	950	1633	138	33518	49.5359423
Female population	14479	6306	4287	5261	1009	1012	1686	106	34146	50.4640577
Up to 19 years	5850	2637	1999	2334	447	281	620	44	14212	
19 - 64 years	17183	7430	5277	6241	1077	1145	2025	133	40511	
Over 64 years	5206	2475	1434	2032	517	536	674	67	12941	
Age average	42.2	42.67	41.16	41.96	44.25	48.27	44.1	46.12	43.84	
Average n. of household members	2.99	3.15	3.15	3.21	3.21	2.5	3.08	2.94	3.02	
Natural increase	-167	-93	-25	-79	-23	-42	-46	-1	-59.5	
Nationalities Bosniacs	3.40%	4.10%	4.10%	0.20%	7.50%	2.80%	0.30%	30.40%	6.60%	
Nationalities Serbs	93.50%	95.30%	95.20%	98.50%	91.90%	96%	98.80%	64.60%	91.72%	
Nationalities Croatians	1%	0.20%	0.20%	0.20%	0.50%	0.40%	0.30%	4.30%	0.88%	
Nationalities Others	2.10%	0.40%	0.60%	1.10%	0.10%	0.80%	0.60%	8%	1.71%	
Marital status distribution aged 15 and over - single	6,799.00	3,318.00	2,285.00	2,973.00	420.00	559.00	857.00	66.00	17,277.00	25.5335186
Marital status distribution aged 15 and over-widowed	2,931.00	1,374.00	850.00	1,049.00	248.00	269.00	375.00	36.00	7,132.00	10.5403169
Marital status distribution aged 15 and over - married	13,737.00	5,863.00	4,080.00	4,916.00	1,003.00	917.00	1,652.00	108.00	32,276.00	47.700402
Marital status distribution aged 15 and over- divorced	515.00	119.00	122.00	98.00	13.00	25.00	14.00	3.00	909.00	1.3434027

Net migration (N. of immigrants to municipalities of Republika Srpska – N. of emigrants from municipalities of Republika Srpska)	196	-15	-51	-58	-22	-3	-23	-4		
Average net wages (in KM expl 1EUR=1,95583KM)	1207	1104	1304	940	1011	988	1094	1192	1105	
Employed persons by sex - male	4687	982	2113	1119	196	260	281	11	9649	
Employed persons by sex - female	4385	766	1077	880	101	162	240	4	7615	
N. of business entities (Total)	1269	275	160	291	84	63	145	5	2292	
Registered companies - A - Agriculture, forestry and fishing	35	16	4	12	6	10	23	1	107	
Registered companies - C - Manufacturing	95	32	14	38	11	10	24	1	225	
Registered companies - I - Accommodation and food service	43	2	2	4	0	0	1	1	53	
Registered companies - J - Information and communication	28	3	1	4	0	1	1	0	38	
N. of employed persons	9072	1748	3190	1999	297	422	521	15	17264	
N. of persons seeking employment	2053	1883	600	1300	334	163	427	0	6760	
N. of tourist arrivals/total 2022	78370	316	0	762	0	213	0	0	79661	18.11 37885
N. of tourist overnights/total 2022	147738	888	0	2389	0	804	0	0	151819	14.64 62995
Average length of stay /year 2022	1.885135	2.810127	0	3.1351706	0	3.774647887	0	0	1.90581338	
N. of registered beds/year 2023 TOTAL	2594	75	142	32	0	82	0	0	2925	

N. of registered agritourism	4	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	6	
N. of beds in registered agritourism	2	0	6	0	0	15	0	0	23	
N. of registered family farms	101	611	305	205	160	108	120	6	1616	
N. of registered agricultural associations and companies	6	3	2	2	1	1	6	0	21	
Total of registered stakeholders	107	614	307	207	161	109	126	6	1637	
Average surface of land in possession of family farm ha	3.32	7.18	6.2	4.69	11.28	5.33	7.75	14.29	7.5	
Data sources: Cenzus 2013 in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Intermediary Agency for IT and financial services ad Banja Luka (abbreviated APIF) , Institute for statistics of Republic of Srpska, Institute for statistics in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Data collected and analysed by Tourist organisation of Republic of Srpska, Ministry of Agriculture in Republic of Srpska										

ANNEXES E – P5 ŠMARJE-PADNA

- Annex E1. Results of the Carpe Digem territorial digital assessment tool for Šmarje
- Annex E2. Results of the Carpe Digem territorial digital assessment tool for Padna
- Annex E3. Environmental education (EE) questionnaire and analysis
- Annex E4. Number of rentals of the 6 e-bikes at the Tourist Information center of Padna
- Annex E5. Socioeconomic and demographic data of P5
- Annex E6. Datasets available in P5
- Annex E7. Stakeholder identification table

Annex E1: Results of the Carpe Digem territorial digital assessment tool for Šmarje

Dimension I: Infrastructure. Grade: 3/3

The broadband infrastructure as well as the coverage of public places is adequate. There is a good use of intelligent sensors, setting a good base for territory's individual and organisational operations.

Dimension II: Open Data. Grade: 2/3

The availability and use of open data can be used/exploited better to have a greater influence on policy making processes. There is room for improvement of open data use in businesses, to exchange data with other institutions (from other regions/cities).

Dimension III: Digital education and training. Grade: 3/3

Digital education and training in schools is at a good level. The integration of digital tools in educational institutions and also outside of the school environment enables equal opportunities for young people and adults to obtain their digital skills.

Dimension IV: Attraction/retention of IT talent. Grade: 3/3

The attraction of IT talent in companies/business is at a good level, so is the number of employees working in digital sector companies. Companies/businesses have a good access to relevant local IT solution providers.

Dimension V: Digital competencies of companies. Grade: 3/3

Companies are investing in their employees by offering them training to improve their digital skills. Companies are also paying attention to their web presence and they offer digitally supported services. Most of the sectors are doing well in digitalization of their processes.

Dimension VI: Community of a Digital Innovation Ecosystem. Grade: 2/3

From the community aspect, the establishment of a tech-community can be used in order to improve collaboration between different sectors. More adequate networking events related to this matter are needed which will at the same time bring digital and non-digital sector companies together.

Dimension VII: Finance. Grade: 2/3

Territory’s financing activities could be further improved. Territory’s activities should do more in terms of encouraging companies to provide grants/tax incentives for digital projects; the territory’s banks need to do more in providing bank loans to territories’ non-digital sector companies for developing their digital projects, including for the digital sector companies as well. The territory needs to do more in encouraging private investors to be willing to invest in digital sector companies and more attention needs to be given to developing alternative financing practices (e.g.: crowdfunding, angel investor, venture capital) to fund digital projects.

Dimension VIII: Support services. Grade: 2/3

The territory should focus on increasing/improving support services for enhancement of processes of digital transformation. In this manner, local stakeholders should take actions to raise the awareness of the importance of digital transformation of SMEs and provide better support to non-digital sector companies.

Dimension IX: Governance and Leadership. Grade: 2/3

Governance and management of digital transformation could be improved by developing a clear digital strategy for the territory, based on well-defined identified goals and adequate management, i.e., assigning adequate authorities who will be able to monitor implementation of digital transformation’s objectives regularly. Additionally, adequate infrastructure should be established, e.g., digital innovation hubs, or rural digital innovation hubs in rural areas

Annex E2: Results of the Carpe Digem territorial digital assessment tool for Padna

Dimension I: Infrastructure. Grade: 3/3

The broadband infrastructure as well as the coverage of public places is adequate. There is a good use of intelligent sensors, setting a good base for territory’s individual and organisational operations

Dimension II: Open Data. Grade: 2/3

The availability and use of open data can be used/exploited better to have a greater influence on policy making processes. There is room for improvement of open data use in businesses, to exchange data with other institutions (from other regions/cities).

Dimension III: Digital education and training. Grade: 2/3

Digital education and training in schools should be further improved. Better integration of digital tools and opportunities to acquire digital skills for young people and adults, both in educational institutions and in out-of-school courses, should be considered.

Dimension IV: Attraction/retention of IT talent. Grade: 3/3

The attraction of IT talent in companies/business is at a good level, so is the number of employees working in digital sector companies. Companies/businesses have good access to relevant local IT solution providers.

Dimension V: Digital competencies of companies. Grade: 3/3

Companies are investing in their employees by offering them training to improve their digital skills. Companies are also paying attention to their web presence and they offer digitally supported services. Most of the sectors are doing well in digitalization of their processes.

Dimension VI: Community of a Digital Innovation Ecosystem. Grade: 2/3

From the community aspect, the establishment of a tech-community can be used in order to improve collaboration between different sectors. More adequate networking events related to this matter are needed which will at the same time bring digital and non-digital sector companies together.

Dimension VII: Finance. Grade: 2/3

Territory’s financing activities could be further improved. Territory’s activities should do more in terms of encouraging companies to provide grants/tax incentives for digital projects; the territory’s banks need to do more in providing bank loans to territories’ non-digital sector companies for developing their digital projects, including for the digital sector companies as well. The territory needs to do more in encouraging private investors to be willing to invest in digital sector companies and more attention needs to be given to developing alternative financing practices (e.g.: crowdfunding, angel investor, venture capital) to fund digital projects.

Dimension VIII: Support services. Grade: 2/3

The territory should focus on increasing/improving support services for enhancement of processes of digital transformation. In this manner, local stakeholders should take actions to raise the awareness of the importance of digital transformation of SMEs and provide better support to non-digital sector companies.

Dimension IX: Governance and Leadership. Grade: 2/3

Governance and management of digital transformation could be improved by developing a clear digital strategy for the territory, based on well-defined identified goals and adequate management, i.e., assigning adequate authorities who will be able to monitor implementation of digital transformation’s objectives regularly. Additionally, adequate infrastructure should be established, e.g., digital innovation hubs, or rural digital innovation hubs in rural areas.

Annex E3: Environmental education (EE) questionnaire and analysis

Environmental education (EE) can be defined as a process in which individuals become aware of their environment and acquire knowledge, skills, values, and experiences that encourage individual and collective action to address current and future environmental challenges.

The integral parts of environmental education are: awareness of and sensitivity to the environment and environmental challenges, understanding of the environment and environmental challenges, relationship with the environment and motivation to improve or maintain environmental quality, skills for recognizing and helping to solve environmental challenges, and participation in activities that lead to solving environmental challenges.

I Demographic data

1. Number of replies: 20
2. Gender distribution: female 11, male 9
3. Age: 18-24 years old: 1
25-34 years old: 4
35-44 years old: 6
45-54 years old: 3
55-64 years old: 1
65-74 years old: 5
4. Highest level of education achieved:
Basic education (elementary): /
Secondary education: 2
Higher vocational education: 3
Short-term higher education: /
Professional higher education (first Bologna cycle): 3
Academic higher education (first Bologna cycle): 5
Master's education (second Bologna cycle): 5
Doctorate of science (third Bologna cycle): 2

II Review and self-assessment of the situation

1. What do you consider to be the most important environmental issue in your environment?

When asked about the most important environmental issue in their local environment, participants mentioned following:

- Excessive use of private motor vehicles for short distances (small occupancy of vehicles)
- Poor waste management
- Agriculture
- Inadequate water management and sewage systems
- Drinking water supply
- Traffic and traffic loads on roads (road infrastructure)
- Mobility and public transportation

Most of the participants mentioned inadequate water management and sewage systems as the most important issue (4), followed by poor waste management (3), traffic and traffic loads on roads, especially during tourist season (3), and lack of public transportation and adequate mobility solutions (3). Related to mobility issues, participants mention excessive use of private vehicles (cars) with small occupancy, even for short distances. Participants also recognize issues with drinking water supply, which becomes challenging mostly during summer months and dry seasons.

2. Which environmental initiatives do you think are most widespread in your environment?

You can circle multiple options:

- Recycling of waste and garbage (17)
- Water-related (10)
- Air pollution (2)
- Energy-related (4)
- Global warming (3)
- Other (briefly state if you chose this option):

Based on the answers provided by participants, in the region Šmarje-Padna, the most widespread environmental initiatives are the ones related to recycling, followed by water-related initiatives. In the next 2 questions, we will gain more insight into the quality of recycling initiatives and the views of participants regarding their importance.

3. How effective do you consider recycling to be?

Participants consider recycling to be mostly effective - with an equal number of answers stating that it is very effective or moderately effective. Remaining participants marked it as ineffective. Negative answers mostly state that the levels of awareness among people are not satisfactory, which is why initiatives often don't suffice.

Very effective (7)

Moderately effective (7)

Ineffective (5)

4. Do you think recycling waste is important?

When asked whether they think recycling is important, the majority of participants answered that it is (very) important, with only two answers stating that they are not sure - lack of trust that the final processing is done adequately by responsible institutions.

Yes (8)

Very important (10)

Not sure (doubts regarding the final recycling stages) (2)

5. How often do you try to reduce energy and water consumption at work? Circle one:

- Once a day or more often (14)
- Twice or more a week (3)
- Three times or less a month (1)
- Never
- Other (briefly state if you chose this option): (1)

Most of the participants (14) stated that they try to reduce energy and water consumption at work at least once a day (or more). Remaining answers stated they do it a couple of times a week or a couple of times a month, with only one answer stating that they don't pay a lot of attention to it.

6. In which of the following ways do you conserve water in your environment?

- Limit shower time (10)
- Turn off the water while brushing teeth, washing hands, shaving, etc. (16)
- Wash only full loads of laundry (16)
- Other (briefly state if you chose this option): collecting rain water (2)

Participants all exhibited solid water conservation habits, with the majority of them implementing at least one of the most common practices in their daily lives, predominantly turning water off while brushing teeth/washing hands/shaving and washing only full loads of laundry.

7. In which of the following ways do you conserve energy in your environment?

- Saving water (16)

- Saving energy (18)
- Alternative energy use (5)
- Low impact design (noise pollution, rain gardens, porous parking lots, etc.)
- Sustainable materials (recycled content, previously used materials, etc.) (5)
- Sustainable choice of location (e.g. use of abandoned areas) (1)
- Other (briefly state if you chose this option): organic farming (1) renovation of existing facilities (1)

As far as energy conservation is considered, participants again exhibit solid habits, with the majority of them implementing at least two most common practices, such as saving energy and water. Other most popular choices were alternative energy use and use of sustainable materials. In the following three sections, we will gain some insight into the situation regarding mobility, specifically, availability and use of public transportation.

8. How often do you use public transportation?

- Never (15)
- Seldom (1)
- Only my children use it (1)
- 1-2 times a year (only during vacations) (1)
- Often (at least once a day) (2)

9. How do you rate the availability of public transport in your area?

When asked about the availability of public transportation, the majority of participants replied that the availability was bad. Those that rated it as moderately good or good also pointed out that buses should be smaller (preferably electric), because regular sized buses always drive almost empty. Participants also mention inadequate timetables (in some villages buses drive only 2-3 times a day or not at all), which makes it impossible for them to use the bus to commute to work.

10. If you rated the availability of public transport as bad, can you suggest a service which could assist in resolving this issue?

In response to this question, most of the participants expressed the following opinion: existing public transportation should be improved, timetables should be revised and adjusted to actual needs of the inhabitants and buses driving in the area should be smaller - there is no need for large buses since they are always half-empty. Another suggestion was a car-sharing solution or group rides and also a solution that would improve the mobility of elderly population.

11. Do you practice circular economy (reduce, reuse, recycle)?

Yes (12)

No (8)

More than a half of participants regularly practice circularity (on a daily basis).

12. Do you think sustainable mobility, circular economy, tourism and care for the environment are interconnected?

Yes (20)

No (0)

All of the participants are aware that sustainable mobility, circular economy, tourism and care for the environment are interconnected.

UL has developed its own questionnaire on environmental education. The summary of results is the following. Environmental education (EE) can be defined as a process in which individuals become aware of their environment and acquire knowledge, skills, values, and experiences that encourage

individual and collective action to address current and future environmental challenges. In order to better understand this topic within the pilot Šmarje-Padna, we conducted a survey and collected 20 responses. The gender distribution was slightly skewed towards females (11 females, 9 males). The age distribution varied, with participants ranging from 18 to 74 years old, predominantly between 35-44 years (6 participants) and 65-74 years (5 participants). In terms of education, most respondents held higher education degrees, with 5 holding a Master's degree and 5 having completed academic higher education (first Bologna cycle).

Participants identified several pressing environmental issues in their local environment. The most frequently mentioned problems were inadequate water management and sewage systems (4 mentions), poor waste management (3 mentions), traffic congestion, especially during the tourist season (3 mentions), and the lack of public transportation (3 mentions). Additional concerns included the excessive use of private vehicles for short distances and drinking water supply challenges during dry seasons.

Recycling emerged as the most widespread environmental initiative, with 17 participants recognizing it as prevalent. Water-related initiatives followed, noted by 10 respondents. Other initiatives included energy-related (4 mentions) and global warming initiatives (3 mentions). Recycling was viewed as effective by most participants, with 7 considering it very effective and 7 moderately effective. However, 5 respondents deemed it ineffective due to inadequate public awareness. When asked about its importance, the majority (18 participants) affirmed its significance, although 2 expressed doubts about the final recycling processes.

A significant portion of participants (14) reported reducing energy and water consumption at work daily. Common water conservation practices included turning off the water while brushing teeth or washing hands (16 mentions) and washing only full loads of laundry (16 mentions). For energy conservation, most participants (18) saved energy, while 16 saved water. Other practices included using alternative energy sources (5 mentions) and sustainable materials (5 mentions).

Public transportation usage was low, with 15 participants never using it and only 2 using it often. The availability of public transportation was rated poorly by most, with suggestions for smaller, more frequent buses, adjusted timetables to suit the actual needs of inhabitants, and car-sharing solutions to improve mobility. Participants also expressed the need for mobility solutions for the elderly.

A majority of participants (12) practice circular economy principles (reduce, reuse, recycle) regularly. All participants (20) acknowledged the interconnectedness of sustainable mobility, circular economy, tourism, and environmental care, highlighting a solid understanding of these interdependencies.

This summary underscores the participants' awareness and engagement with environmental issues, highlighting areas for potential improvement in public transportation and community involvement in recycling initiatives.

In methodological terms, this questionnaire underlines the findings from the SEROI+ analysis, thus needs to be seen as an accompanying document. In the appendix, the overall analysis is provided.

Annex E4: Number of rentals of the 6 e-bikes at the Tourist Information center of Padna

Year	Number of rentals - regular	Number of rentals - agreements
2019	67	28
2020	85	6
2021	124	32
2022	69	46
2023	86	12

Annex E5: Socioeconomic and demographic data of P5

	UNIT Šmarje - Padna	VALUE (YEAR*, SOURCE) *If no information for 2023 is available, use the most recent value and indicate the year	Value for comparison? Scale over the years/time periods? Nation- wide?
TERRITORY (2023) Source: pxweb.stat.si			
Surface	In km ²	7, 2,91	20.271
POPULATION (2023) Source: pxweb.stat.si			
Population size	N. of inhabitants	915, 188 (local levels:Šmarje and Padna)	2.123.949
Population density	N. of inhabitants/km ²	238, 64,8 (local levels:Šmarje and Padna)	104,6
Age Average	Total Age of inhabitants/N. of inhabitants	44,5, 47 (local levels:Šmarje and Padna)	44,1
Age distribution	Percentage or count within each age group, e.g. <16, 16-64, >64	151, 563, 201 16,5%, 61,5%, 22% 16, 121, 51 8,5%, 64,4%, 27,1 (local levels:Šmarje and Padna)	14,9%, 63,5%, 21,6%
Dependency ratio	(N. of people < 16 + N. of people > 64 / N. of people 16-64)*100	62,5, 55,4 (local levels:Šmarje and Padna)	57,81
Gender distribution	Percentage or count of female/male (diverse)	450/465, 94/94 49,18%/50,82%, 50/50 (local levels:Šmarje and Padna)	1.068.429/1.055.520 50,3%/49,7%
Birth rate	N. of births recorded in one year/1.000 inhabitants	6,9 6,2 (municipality level Koper and Piran; no existing data for the level of the pilot)	8,4
Mortality rate	N. of Deaths recorded in one year/1.000 inhabitants	9,2 13,1 (municipality level Koper and Piran; no existing data for the level of the pilot)	10,7

Rate of natural increase (RNI) per 1.000 inhabitants	(Live Births-Deaths/Inhabitants)/1.000	-2,2 -6,9(municipality level Koper and Piran; no existing data for the level of the pilot)	-2,3
Nationalities	In % of total population	14,8 15,5 (municipality level Koper and Piran; no existing data for the level of the pilot)	9,6%
Immigration/Emigration	Registrations and deregistrations in the register due to change of municipality of residence	32, 114 (municipality level Koper and Piran; no existing data for the level of the pilot)	131.191
Marital status distribution	Percentage or count of single, married, divorced, etc.	no existing data	
ECONOMY (2023) Source: pxweb.stat.si			
Gross domestic product (GDP) per capita	€/inhabitant	26.074 (regional level; no existing data for the level of the pilot)	29.753
Gross disposable income per household	€/household	(municipality level; no existing data for the level of the pilot)	35.646
Primary sources of income from household disposable income		(municipality level; no existing data for the level of the pilot)	66,9 %
Registered companies (Total)		6.893, 2.670 (municipality level Koper and Piran; no existing data for the level of the pilot)	221.483
Registered companies (Sector of activity) Agriculture		3.468 farms (regional level; no existing data for the level of the pilot) eco farms 114 Koper 39 Piran	68.331
Employment status and occupation types		(municipality level; no existing data for the level of the pilot)	
overnight stays of local and foreign + tourists		1.824.898 Piran, 4.559 Padna (2023) Source: Tourist board Portorož)	15,6 million

(Tourism, Agrifood, Mobility)		356.964 Koper (municipality level) Source: Tourist organization Koper	
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Annex E6: Data available in P5

Kind of Data	Data Owner	Sensitivity	Access Model	Short Description	Purpose of usage	Data format	Average size of the data item	Volume of data	Frequency of acquisition
Tourist arrivals at accommodation in the village (commercial data)	Tourist board Portorož	Public	Free (on request)	Data (data collection starting from 2017) on tourist arrivals in accommodation in the village where we have three accommodation providers with a total of around 40 beds.	Data can be used as invaluable information for developing smart mobility service in connection to Šmarje	Excel	120 kb		yearly
Timetables of public transport	Bus provider firm Arriva	Public	Free	timetables of bus, arriving to Šmarje and Padna (from Koper)	Data can be used as invaluable information for developing smart mobility service in connection to Šmarje and Padna	Word document	Low value, one word sheet		yearly
Cycling areas in the Municipality of Piran: 8a122992-5afa-4ff3-8bf9-364b31170678/resource/220bb65e-7a24-4f8a-	Municipality	Public	Free	The link provides data for the whole municipality of Piran, but can be identified for Padna too	Data can be used as invaluable information for developing smart mobility service in connection to Šmarje and Padna	CSV, XML, XLS, XLSX, JSON, GEOJSON, slike (PNG, JPG, GIF)			Collected

8bcc-d15fdee f8cd7/download/ kolesars keopi.zip									
Cycling areas in the Municipality of Koper: https://podatki.gov.si/dataset/urejene-kolesarske-potiv-mestni-obcini-koper	Municipality	Public	Free	The link provides data for the whole municipality of Piran, but can be identified for Šmarje too	Data can be used as invaluable information for developing smart mobility service in connection to Šmarje and Padna	CSV, GEOJSON			Collected
Smart Agro Grape data - weather (temperature, moisture, wind) data, information from vineyard sensor infrastructure in pilot area Šmarje: https://smartagragrape.si/podrobnosti?objava=14	Data are collected within the national project of Smart Agro Grape	UL, project	UL is the owner	The link provides data, which are being collected via project's sensors	Data can be used as an insight into the Šmarje's agriculture area of a particular winemaker.	csv, json	15 Mb		Simultaneously collected

Annex E7: Stakeholders identification table

Name of the entity/person/etc.	Short description	Possible role in the project
villagers (wider category)*	understanding what is needed, they know the community, know the problems and challenges	knowledge, experience according to your age group, your point of view
tourists	the needs, expectations can be translated to the development of the service	promotion due to good experience
daily migrants	they understand very well the problematic of traffic for instance	knowledge, experience according to your age group, your point of view
senior citizens, young people without a driver's license, anyone without private transport, schoolchildren (extra-curricular activities)	boost initiative, motivate the execution of the project	insight into the problematic itself, stipulate social inclusion in this regard
Private carriers (e.g. taxis) + Carriers - public / private transport (firms: Arriva, Nomago, etc.)	experience, knowledge	man power and infrastructure (drivers and cars)
Volunteers	altruistic component: personal satisfaction, helping your fellow man; it is not just about the “money”, it is about helping each other, building on the principles of solidarity, stipulating sustainable development via commuting etc.	insight into the problematic itself, stipulate social inclusion in this regard
Local Councils Associations Municipality	knowing situation best; having political capacity	having administrative know-how; systematic approach - knowing where the financial support can be asked for
olive and wine makers	can contribute to circular economy as a modality within the developed service	boost circular economy, but also green environmental approach with being included into the developed service
public utility companies (water mitigation systems)	knowing the state of the existing infrastructure	construction of new infrastructure
Ministry of the Environment, Spatial Planning and Energy	coordinated planning and regulatory mitigation	regional planning
private individuals, providers	own investments	capital investment

restaurants, tourism service providers	cooperate with other institutions to solve advertising problems (signs on the road)	increasing prosperity
operators of tourist establishments - in particular tourist farms	expanding their offer, more visits, more overnight stays, more tourists in the villages - more profit	local community development visibility

ANNEXES F – P6 DEVETAKI PLATEAU

- Annex F1. Population and age distribution in P6
- Annex F2. Registered companies in P6

Annex F1 – Population and age distribution in the Devetaki Plateau, Bulgaria

Age distribution (2021)				
	0-19	20-34	35-64	65+
Agatovo	42	103	86	86
Brestovo	11	10	34	91
Gorsko Slivovo	62	43	167	194
Devetaki	6	6	37	86
Kramolin	50	38	88	128
Krushuna	53	43	119	116
Kakrina	7	8	43	122
Karpachevo	6	6	26	64
Tepava	0	1	11	29
Total Devetaki plateau	237	258	611	916

Gender (2021)				
	Male	Female	Total	Area (km2)
Agatovo	99	132	231	36.488
Brestovo	65	81	146	38.214
Gorsko Slivovo	245	221	466	70.028
Devetaki	69	66	135	51.472
Kramolin	137	167	304	44.873
Krushuna	153	178	331	19.981
Kakrina	84	96	180	31.656
Karpachevo	44	58	102	19.195
Tepava	20	21	41	18.438
Total Devetaki plateau	916	1020	1936	330.345

Annex F2 – Registered companies inf the Devetaki Plateau

Registered companies	
Agatovo	12
Brestovo	6
Gorsko Slivovo	23
Devetaki	3
Kramolin	11
Krushuna	19
Kakrina	5
Karpachevo	15
Tepava	1
Total Devetaki plateau	95

ANNEXES G – GENERAL ANNEXES

- Annex G1. Informed Consent Form

Annex G1. Informed Consent Form

SMART ERA

Informed Consent Form

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

SMART ERA Privacy Policy

Dear participant, we want to make sure that your rights are protected during this activity. Therefore, we prepared this form to give you more information about our project, this event, and **how your personal data will be protected**. As you know, personal data (e.g. your email address or what will be discussed during the activity) is protected under the European Law called the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). We, therefore, need to ensure that we have properly recorded your consent for the use of the data gathered from this activity.

We would kindly ask you to read the following information carefully. If you agree with the content, please provide us with your signature at the bottom of this form and return it to us. In case this is an online or hybrid event, please send the signed form via email to **[Partner responsible for the organisation of the activity or event will add here an email address]**.

1. The SMART ERA project

SMART ERA is a **4-year project (2024-2027)** funded by the **European Union's Horizon Europe programme**, aimed to **foster resilience in rural areas** by upgrading and codesigning, co-developing and co-validating with local communities a set of smart solutions, integrated within Smart Innovation Packages (SIPs) able to tackle pressing socio-economic and environmental challenges

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and to empower rural people to act for change. SMART ERA’s main ambitions are: a) building the first large-scale European-wide solution for systematic rural data screening and smartness analysis; b) using co-design methods and techniques to involve residents and stakeholders in the design and validation of SIPs, as well as in the collection of old and creation of new data sources; c) proposing a unified Smartness/Digital Maturity assessment method; d) providing unique and timely evidence-based and performance-focused recommendations to upgrade the new local, national and European policy instruments and enhance their efficiency and efficacy in supporting smart villages across the EU; e) fostering cooperation among pilot regions, as well as among the four EU macro-regional strategies and improve their rural communities’ ability to address socio-economic and environmental challenges.

Trentino (Italy), Tramuntana/Sóller (Spain), Northern Ostrobothnia (Finland), East Herzegovina (Bosnia and Herzegovina), Šmarje-Padna (Slovenia, Italy, Croatia), and Devetaki Plateau (Bulgaria) are the **6 SMART ERA rural pilot areas** across Europe. These sites aim to enhance their communities’ ability to address challenges and will actively participate to the co-design, co-development and co-validation of smart solutions within the project.

The project is carried out by a consortium of **25 partners, associated entities and associated partners from 10 different countries**. Among those, the following partners are identified as “**Pilot Orchestrators**” since they will coordinate the execution of the pilot activities in their own territories: the Coordinator Fondazione Bruno Kessler (IT), the University of Ljubljana (SI), the University of Oulu (FI), Anysolution (ES), Slow Food Trebinje Hercegovina (BA), Devetashko Plato Sdruzhenie (BG). The “Pilot orchestrators” operate in synergy with the partners identified as “**Community activators**”, who are responsible for the engagement of the local communities and their active participation in the activities: Provincia Autonoma di Trento (IT), Sredisce Rotunda (SI), Council of Oulu (FI), Mes Cultura (Spain), Turisticka Organizacija Republike Srpske (BA), Municipality of Sevlievo (BG). The other partners are involved with a technical/transversal role in the project execution: Software Competence Center Hagenberg (AT), Poliedra (IT), University of Maribor (SI), Engineering – Ingegneria Informatica (IT) with its affiliated entity Municipia (IT), Fondazione Icons (IT), Association Europeenne pour l’Innovation dans le Developpement Local (BE), Baltic Institute of Finland (FI), Fundingbox Accelerator (PL) with its affiliated entity Fundingbox Communities (ES), Schweizerische Arbeitsgemeinschaft für die Berggebiete (CH), Sluzba Vlade Republike Slovenije za razvoj in evropsko kohezijsko politiko (SI), Stadt Wien (AT).

2. Voluntary participation

Participation is not compulsory. You can decide for yourself whether you want to participate in the project SMART ERA or not. If you decide to participate, you will receive this privacy policy to keep and will be asked to sign a consent form and/or tick a box to indicate their agreement. You can withdraw your participation at any time and without giving any reason, without this affecting the benefits to which you are entitled or having any negative consequences (right to be forgotten).

3. What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

No risks are foreseen. You are only requested to be available to participate. All the information provided will be treated with the strictest confidentiality. Any concerns should be immediately notified to the organizer of the activities to facilitate resolution.

4. The Pilot

[Short description of the Pilot main objectives to be added here by the responsible partner].

5. Data Controller

The Data Controller is [the responsible Pilot Leader - name of the entity], with a registered office in, – phone. – e-mail

Contact information of the Data Protection Officer

Pursuant to art. 37 of the Regulation, the Data Protection Officer (DPO) designated by the Data Controller may be reached via the following channels: phone [add phone of the DPO or legal expert of the Pilot Leader organisation]..... - email [add email of the DPO or legal expert of the Pilot Leader organisation]

6. Types of data collected

The following personal data may be collected during the course of the SMART ERA research activities (interviews, workshops, focus groups, etc.) or events:

- Name
- Address
- Email
- Phone number
- Age
- Gender
- Image (photo or video)

- Education level
- Professional field and status
- Activity while using the digital solutions (e.g., logs)
- Other (please specify)

7. Purposes of processing

Your personal data is collected to allow the Data Controller to provide its service, comply with its legal obligations, respond to enforcement requests, protect its rights and interests (or those of its participants or third parties) and detect any malicious or fraudulent activity.

Personal data will be processed for the following purposes:

- To co-design the SMART ERA solutions taking into account users' needs and expectations.
- To evaluate and assess the impact of the SMART ERA solutions. To achieve this objective, the project will process personal data from citizens and stakeholders to assess participation and understand the socio-economic impact of the project. • To verify user's participation in the project: pictures/videos will be taken in order to verify that you participated in the SMART ERA activities.
- To register for the events and activities organised during the project.
- For dissemination and communications purposes.
- To review the project results and solutions taking into account the feedback received from external experts.

8. Methods of processing personal data

The data controller will take appropriate security measures to prevent unauthorised access, disclosure, modification, or unauthorised destruction of the data. The data processing is carried out using computers and/or IT enabled tools, following organisational procedures and modes strictly related to the purposes indicated.

Your personal data shall be processed through online/paper questionnaires, online/phone interviews, during workshops, focus groups or events in contexts that do not compromise your personal dignity and your decorum, ensuring the necessary precautions to guarantee the confidentiality of the use.

No automated decision-making process, nor any profiling activity is planned.

We collect your personal data directly from you when you are participating in the SMART ERA project.

9. Legal basis of processing

Participation in the SMART ERA project is accepted on the basis that you freely and independently sign a consent form and/or tick a check box to indicate your consent, in order to authorise us to process your personal data. You have the right to withdraw your consent to any further processing at any time.

10. Place of the processing

Your personal data is processed at the Data Controller’s operating offices and in any other places where the parties involved in the processing are located.

Depending on your location, data transfers may involve transferring your personal data to a country other than your own. Personal data may be processed in the countries where the SMART ERA partner organisations are located or in any other country of the European Union.

The activity of processing personal data takes place on the territory of the European Union, or with the help of IT tools involving processing in countries for which the European Commission has taken a decision on the adequacy of the protection of personal data or, alternatively, through the signing with the provider of Standard Contractual Clauses (SCC) of data protection adopted by the European Commission.

11. Data sharing

Your personal data may be transferred to and processed by other members of the SMART ERA consortium. More information regarding other members of the consortium can be found at the following address: <https://smartera-project.eu/>

Personal data shall not be disseminated, besides those used for dissemination and communication purposes (e.g., photos or videos taken with the explicit consent of participants).

For exclusive purpose of scientific dissemination of statistical and/or scientific results (for example through the publication of scientific articles and/or the creation of databases, also with open access methods, participation in conferences, etc.), the data may be shared among the scientific community and disclosed anonymously and aggregated and always in a way that does not make the interested party identifiable.

The Project Coordinator is moreover confident that any future processing is purpose specific and is permitted ONLY for the purposes of the project and facilitating the completion of the specified tasks.

12. Retention time

Personal data shall be processed and stored for as long as required by the purpose they have been collected for. The data controller may be allowed to retain personal data for a longer period whenever you have given consent to such processing, as long as such consent is not withdrawn. Furthermore, the data controller may be obliged to retain personal data for a longer period whenever required to do so for the performance of a legal obligation or upon order of an authority.

Once the retention period expires, personal data shall be anonymized and deleted. Therefore, the right of access, the right to erasure, the right to rectification and the right to data portability cannot be enforced after expiration of the retention period.

The retention period will run for five further years from the end of the SMART ERA project (December 2027).

13. Your rights

You may exercise certain rights regarding your personal data processed by the data controller. In particular, you have the right to do the following:

- Withdraw your consent at any time. You have the right to withdraw consent where you have previously given their consent to the processing of your personal data.
- Object to processing of your data. You have the right to object to the processing of their data if the processing is carried out on a legal basis other than consent. During the course of SMART ERA, all data is processed based on your consent.
- Access to your data. You have the right to learn if data is being processed by the data controller, obtain disclosure regarding certain aspects of the processing and obtain a copy of the data undergoing processing.
- Verify and seek rectification. You have the right to verify the accuracy of their data and ask for it to be updated or corrected.
- Restrict the processing of your data. You have the right, under certain circumstances, to restrict the processing of your data. In this case, the data controller will not process your data for any purpose other than storing it.
- Have your personal data deleted or otherwise removed. You have the right, under certain circumstances, to obtain the erasure of your data from the data controller.
- Receive your data and have it transferred to another controller. You have the right to receive your data in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format and, if technically feasible, to have it transmitted to another controller without any hindrance. This provision is applicable provided that the data is processed by automated means and that the processing is based on your consent, on a contract which you are part of or on pre-contractual obligations thereof.
- Lodge a complaint. You have the right to bring a claim before their competent data protection authority.

How to exercise these rights

Your request to exercise your rights can be directed to [add email Pilot Leader]. This request can be exercised free of charge and will be addressed by the data controller as early as possible and within one month (with extensions in some specific cases).

14. Benefits of the project

You will make a significant contribution to the achievement of the main objectives of the SMART ERA project. The project can help understand the main drivers for change in rural areas and empower their local communities to tackle the main socio-economic and environmental challenges.

15. Confidentiality

All the personal data collected during the course of the research will be kept strictly confidential. You will not be able to be identified in any publications (except for pictures or videos you have given your specific consent to be in). The results of this investigation may be published in reports, scientific journals or conferences and used in further studies, but it will not be possible to identify the source of the information. None of the provided data will be handled by third parties. The authorization for the use and access to personal data is valid until the end of the project, unless you decide to withdraw from the project. Your decision whether or not to give your authorization for the use and diffusion of your personal data is completely voluntary.

16. Future change in privacy policy

The Data Controller reserves the right to make, if necessary, the appropriate changes to this privacy policy – currently updated on <https://smartera-project.eu/> giving the widest visibility to the data subjects.

In any case, it is advisable to regularly check the project website and refer to the most up-to-date version.

The previous versions are available for consultation in the same dedicated page of the website.

17. Dispute resolution

Questions or complaints regarding the data collected, this privacy policy or other privacy matters can be addressed at SMART ERA consortium through the following address: [add email Pilot Leader].

You have the right to lodge a complaint also to the relevant national Data Protection Authority (indicate the relevant Data Protection Authority, e.g. for Italy: Italian Authority for Data Protection - Garante Privacy).

SMART ERA consent to the processing of personal data

We hereby ask your **consent to the processing of personal data** collected in the context of the SMART ERA project activities. Such processing is aimed at the execution of the Project itself.

We declare that the use of the personal data and images (photos or videos taken during the event) will be carried out exclusively in contexts that do not compromise your personal dignity and your decorum, ensuring the necessary precautions to guarantee the confidentiality of the use.

You have the right to obtain access, rectification, erasure ‘right to be forgotten’ of personal data, restriction of processing, objection to the processing due to legitimate reasons, data portability, and to advance a dispute to the Supervisory Authority (Privacy Authority) in compliance with Chapter III of GDPR.

Full information regarding the processing of personal data is provided before the participation at the Project and remains available upon your request to the SMART ERA consortium.

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By completing this form and with my signature at the bottom, within the meaning and for the purposes of the EU Regulation No. 2016/679 – General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and aware of the general objectives and characteristics of the project, as well as of the conditions and commitments I assume as a participant that I:

- freely consent to the participation in the project;
- am aware of being able to withdraw at any time, without having to give justifications or incurring in costs or penalties;
- understand that my data will be kept strictly confidential. I give permission for members of the research team to process the data I have shared to co-design the SMART

ERA solutions, as well as to evaluate their impacts;

am aware that information may be shared between any of the other researcher(s) and partners participating in this project. I understand that my name will not be linked with the research materials, and I will not be identified or identifiable in the publications that result from the research.

have no objection that my data is published in a way that does not reveal my identity, without my explicit consent. The researcher(s) will ensure to preserve my anonymity as much as technically possible. As described above, within the meaning and for the purposes described above, however respecting any other condition imposed by law.

have received a copy of this agreement.

[choose one option]

authorise the processing of photographic-video-audio recordings, if any.

do not authorise the processing of photographic-video-audio recordings, if any. For participants who select this option specific measures not to be photographed or filmed during the event will be taken.

[choose one option]

consent to the mailing of follow-up of events/informative materials/updates on next events.

do not consent to the mailing of follow-up of events/informative materials/updates on next events.

I do hereby agree and give my consent for the processing of my personal data

within the SMART ERA project.

The above authorizations have been granted free of charge, with no provision of fees and/or charges to be borne by the Controller and are also valid as a disclaimer. In the event of revocation of these authorizations, the image and materials will not be included in subsequent productions. I, the Undersigned, understand that it will not be possible to remove the image from materials already produced prior to the revocation.

Name of participant:

Date:

ONLY IN CASE OF MINOR PARTICIPANTS

Name of the Legal Representative of the Minor Participant of Research:

Date:

Signature:

Name of SMART ERA researcher:

Date:

Signature:

Thank you for having agreed to participate in this activity which is carried out as part of the **SMART ERA project**. Your cooperation is greatly appreciated and will be important for our consortium.